

DELIVERABLE D4.1 – V2.1

ESG DUE DILIGENCE OF THE COMBINED EXTRACTION OF CRMS AND ENERGY, INCL. UNFC/UNRMS COMPATIBLE REPORTING AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary:

Every project for the extraction of minerals has to be subject to a PESTEL (political, environmental, societal, technological, economic, legal) analysis to assess its viability. The combined extraction of heat and minerals is no exception even though it would not be a classical mining. This report, maps the relevant flows for the various metal extraction schemes investigated under CRM-geothermal. In addition, a comprehensive risk catalogue for combined extraction projects is developed. Together with the material flow analysis this allows also a comparative risk and impact assessment with other types of mineral extraction. The data for a PESTEL assessment are completed by an assessment of the regulatory schemes in a comprehensive selection of European countries plus Turkey.

Additionally, the report proposes an approach on UNFC compliant assessment of combined extraction that will be submitted to the UNECE for consideration.

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Funded by
the European Union

Title:	ESG due diligence of the combined extraction of CRMs and energy, incl. UNFC/UNRMS compatible reporting and policy recommendation		
Lead beneficiary:	INTRAW		
Due date:	30.09.2025		
Nature:	Public		
Diffusion:	EC, all project partners, General Public		
Status:	Final		
License information:	CC-BY-4.0		
DOI:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17235755		
Recommended Citation:	Falck, W. E. & Correia, V., The Horizon Europe CRM-geothermal project: Deliverable 4.1 – ESG due diligence of the combined extraction of CRMs and energy, incl. UNFC/UNRMS compatible reporting and policy recommendation, Zenodo, 2025, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17235755		
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Document code:	CRM-GEOTHERMAL_D.4.1		
Revision history	Author	Delivery date	Summary of changes and comments
Version 1.0	WEF	24.07.2025	Draft submitted to the project consortium for checking
Version 2.1	WEF	25.09.2025	Minor amendments and corrections

Approval status			
	Name	Function	Date
Deliverable responsible	W. Eberhard Falck	Task Leader 4.1	25.09.2025
WP leader	W. Eberhard Falck	WP leader WP4	25.09.2025
Reviewer	Vitor Correia		
Reviewer	Katrin Kieling	Project manager	25.09.2025
Project Coordinator	Simona Regenspurg	Project coordinator	30.09.2025

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or HADEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Acknowledgements

The authors thank Edmund Sides (PERC), Hendrik Falck (Chair UNECE Mineral Resources Working Group), and Gioia Falcone (Chair UNECE Geothermal Working Group) for their careful review of Chapter 5 in particular and their valuable contributions.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Every project for the extraction of minerals has to be subject to a PESTEL (political, environmental, societal, technological, economic, legal) analysis to assess its viability. The combined extraction of heat and minerals is no exception even though it would not be a classical mining project with respect to the impacts and legacies it may create.

To ensure the economic viability of a project, it is normally subject to a due diligence assessment according to CRIRSCO-aligned resource assessment and a classification according to UNFC. However, CRIRSCO-aligned assessments (according to PERC in Europe) cover only mineral resources and not energy resources, such as geothermal heat.

Starting from the hypothesis that all materials and energy flows are likely to cause impacts, this report set out to map the relevant flows for the various metal extraction schemes investigated under CRM-geothermal. In addition, a comprehensive risk catalogue for combined extraction projects was developed. Together with material flow analyses this allows also a comparative risk and impact assessment with other types of mineral extraction.

The data collated from the literature and through the experimental work under CRM-geothermal indicate that the environmental impacts and likely legacies from the combined extraction of metals and heat, are considerably lower than those arising from conventional mining. The environmental savings arise mainly from the absence of large-scale excavations and the associated energy consumption and the need to manage the resulting extractive wastes adequately.

A comparison of the potential environmental impacts between different lithium extraction methods was undertaken. Extraction from hard-rocks is likely to have the highest impacts, while extraction from salars can be comparable to combined extraction, but it ultimately depends on whether pre-concentration by evaporation or a direct lithium extraction (DLE) method is used.

The development of material flow diagrams for the different extraction technologies developed under CRM-geothermal, helped to reflect on potential direct and indirect environmental impacts, including CO₂-footprints. The still too low Technology Readiness Levels (TRL) of the technologies did not permit to make meaningful quantitative assessments, but the flow diagrams indicate areas for optimisation.

To date no specific guidance on UNFC compliant assessment of combined extraction exists and this report proposes an approach that has been submitted to the UNECE working groups on minerals and geothermal energy for consideration, where it started a process of deliberation. The proposal has also been discussed with the Pan-European Resource and Reserves Reporting Committee (PERC) as the European body of CRIRSCO.

The data for a PESTEL assessment are completed by an assessment of the regulatory schemes across European countries plus Turkey. However, in the majority of countries no specific regulations for combined extraction exist yet.

The societal and economic aspects feeding into the PESTEL assessment are subject of complementary CRM-geothermal reports, which are informed by the risk assessments laid out in this report.

1 OBJECTIVES

Every project for the extraction of minerals has to be subject to a PESTEL (political, environmental, societal, technological, economic, legal) analysis to assess its viability. While much of the work in CRM-geothermal project is concerned with the development of efficient technologies for the extraction of critical raw materials (CRM; CRMA, 2024) from geothermal fluids, work-package 4 of this project focused on the other aspects of a PESTEL assessment.

The **objective of the PESTEL assessments** is to demonstrate that extraction is not only technically feasible (T), but that it is environmentally benign (E), is acceptable to the local communities (S), makes economic sense (E), and can be carried out in line the applicable legal framework (L).

The **objective of this report** is to provide the tools for demonstrating that projects of combined extraction of heat and minerals have considerable environmental advantages over other forms of extracting (critical) minerals, namely compared to traditional mining techniques. The report also aims to provide an overview over the current regulatory framework that would govern combined extraction project in most European countries. The societal and economic aspects per the PESTEL assessment are covered by complementing reports, namely by Mitchell et al. (2025) on laying out successful stakeholder engagement processes, by Correia et al. (forthcoming) on the economic assessment from an investor and policy-making perspective, and by Micklovicz et al. (2025) on strategies for the market deployment of such systems for the combined extraction.

The method of choice for assessing overall environmental impacts are the well-established methods of Life-Cycle Impact Assessments (LCIA). The objective here was also to provide technology and project developers with a tool with which they can select the right methods and optimise them with a view to minimise environmental impacts. To this end, conceptual models for the proposed combined extraction schemes have been developed, and the potential impacts and risk assessed, considering three levels of analysis (**Chapter 2**):

- (a) the combined extraction was compared with other, conventional mining and processing options,
- (b) stakeholders' requirements and needs (cf. Mitchell, et al., 2025) form the second layer of the assessment, and
- (c) the analysis of legal and regulatory requirements in various European countries forms the third layer of the assessment.

It was not attempted to undertake a cradle to gate LCIA to compare all the different Li-value chains, as was undertaken for instance by Grant et al. (2020). The focus was on those elements of the value-chain that are different from Li-extraction from salars (natural brines) or hard-rocks. This LCIA then can serve as guidance to prospective operators for further improvement and for selecting the technology with the least embodied energy and carbon footprint. This procedure will ensure that ESG requirements are internalised from the planning stage onwards and respective guidance for operator self-assessment is given in **Chapter 3**.

The in most jurisdictions yet uncharted territories of regulating such combined extraction projects is discussed in **Chapter 4**, with a detailed assessment of pertinent EU Member State legislation provided in **Appendix 1**.

While the economic aspects are treated in detail in Correia et al. (forthcoming), the environmental, societal, and governance (ESG) aspects of proposed combined extraction projects have to be assessed with a view to developing investor due diligence and CRIRSCO/UNFC-compatible resource reporting respectively classification. This report reviews the currently available CRIRSCO guidance and proposes a UNFC-compliant scheme for classifying combined extraction projects (**Chapter 5**). A UNFC/UNRMS/CRIRSCO compliant assessment will reinforce confidence in resource estimates as a basis for the economic assessments (c.f. Correia et al., forthcoming).

2 CONCEPTUAL MODELS FOR COMBINED EXTRACTION SYSTEMS

2.1 WORKING HYPOTHESES

For each of the test-cases and for projected technical systems a mechanistic conceptual model will be developed in collaboration with the respective project partners. A detailed description of the different processes to be utilised and of the test-sites will be compiled. These conceptual models will functionally relate the different system components to each other. It allows the tracing of material and energy flows within the systems and across system boundaries. External energy supplies, process chemicals used, extractive waste disposal, etc. will be covered.

The **main working hypothesis** is that every flux of energy or mass constitutes a potential source of environmental risk. The material and energy flows will be one element contributing to the analyses of potential impacts and risks later in the project.

A **second working hypothesis** is that combined extraction is likely to have less impacts than conventional metal mining. So, the focus will be on the operational energy and carbon footprints, and less so on the ancillary ones (construction of the 'mine', extraction equipment and infrastructure, etc.), which would be considerable for conventional mining. Nevertheless, one has to look into the ancillary ones as well in order to detect, whether there are significant contributors to the energy and carbon footprints, such as synthesising ion-exchange resins and the likes. This also gives indications for further optimisation with a view to reduce these footprints. Along the same line, a materials flow analysis (MFA) looking at individual chemical elements and compounds will identify and track arisings of toxic or radioactive compounds through the combined extraction system to their final management option.

A **third working hypothesis** is, that lower mass movements are likely to result also in lower societal impacts, both objectively and subjectively. With a MFA one can demonstrate, that comparatively little amounts of waste are generated per unit quantity of metal extracted, for instance. One can also demonstrate the viability of the chosen extractive waste management route and, similarly, that e.g. road traffic would be limited, as only products, by-products and reactants would leave or enter the site. On the more subjective side, the visual impact from the surface installations would be limited and they could be integrated into the surrounding environment (e.g. style of building, etc.).

Sankey-diagrams (Sankey 1896) are a semi-quantitative way to illustrate the fluxes of energy or mass. Sankey-diagrams are built on a conceptual model of the system under

investigation (see below). They allow the tracing of material and energy flows within the systems and across system boundaries. Flows across the system boundaries include, for example, external energy supplies, process chemicals used, disposal of extractive wastes (that cannot be further valorised), etc., but also the energy (electricity and/or steam) and products (e.g., metals) sold.

Many components of the combined extraction systems under investigation in CRM-geothermal are modular and could be combined in different ways to suit the market and/or the geological system under exploitation. Thus, the conceptual models will functionally relate the different system components to each other and allow the assessment of different configurations from both, the environmental/societal and economic impact perspective. In this sense, these conceptual models will be an essential tool for optimising a combined extraction system and to assess the feasibility of implementation in a given socio-economic and regulatory context.

For each of the test-cases and for projected technical systems a mechanistic conceptual model was developed in collaboration with the respective project partners. A detailed description of both, the different processes utilised and of the test-sites was compiled to this end.

2.2 EMBODIED ENERGIES AND CARBON-FOOTPRINTS

Each product produced requires raw materials and energy, and in consequence the production process releases greenhouse gases, namely CO₂. Taking into account comprehensively all material and energy fluxes associated with a product or process would be a daunting task. This would need to include all ancillary processes and materials (such as e.g. chemical reagents, tools, etc.) and in turn the energy and materials needed to produce them etc. A comprehensive discussion of these complexities and challenges is provided e.g. by Gutowski et al. (2013). Thus, major differences that affect the embodied energies, are the quality and availability of the raw material, the raw material matrix, the complexity of conversion and production processes, the age of the technology used, and the degree of purity required in the final output. These factors can vary considerably around the world around a mean value easily by ±20% or more. Unlike the engineering properties of a material, such as strength or stiffness, which can be obtained under well-specified conditions, the embodied energy is a function not only of the material itself, but also of a larger system that surrounds the material and is often not well defined. Hence, this level of uncertainty is somewhat inherent to the type of large boundary analysis we are performing. It should be noted that the theoretical minima for the embodied energies of materials can be approximated by the respective Gibbs Free Energy of their formation. For simple chemical compounds and some other materials, such as minerals, these data are readily available from handbooks and other literature.

A surrogate indicator for **embodied energies** is the Energy Return on Investment (EROI). EROI is the ratio of the energy delivered to society over the energy required to produce that energy delivery and is a common analysis undertaken for all sorts of energy conversion systems (e.g. Southon & Krumdiek, 2013):

$$\text{EROI} = \text{Energy delivered by a system} / \text{Energy delivered to a system}$$

EROI is the net yield and used to compare the quality of different energy conversion systems, as it shows the magnitude of the yield from an investment in terms of energy.

Similar analyses can be undertaken for the materials investments in order to obtain more and different materials

Not all the external fluxes of energy and matter (for instances, those resulting from the production of chemical reagents) can be explicitly accounted for in the framework of CRM-geothermal, but one will need to rely on respective data that are available from databases or the published literature.

Embodied energy is usually expressed as MJ/kg of the material investigated.

Greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions to the atmosphere concern the seven GHGs covered under the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC, 1992) and more specifically the Kyoto Protocol (UNFCCC, 1997), namely carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), nitrous oxide (N₂O), hydrofluorocarbons (HFCs), perfluorocarbons (PFCs), sulphur hexafluoride (SF₆), and nitrogen trifluoride (NF₃). They are usually expressed as CO₂ equivalents per kg of the material investigated, i.e., kgCO₂-eq/kg. As will be discussed in the following, such emissions can arise at a wide variety of value-web elements and at various stages of the life-cycle. For accounting purposes, one usually distinguishes between three 'scopes' (WRI & WBCSD, 2004): "Developing a full emissions inventory – incorporating Scope 1, Scope 2 and Scope 3 emissions – enables companies to understand their full value chain emissions and focus their efforts on the greatest reduction opportunities". The 'scopes' are defined as:

Scope 1 emissions cover emissions from sources that an organisation owns or controls directly – for example from burning fuel in a fleet of vehicles or driving machinery.

Scope 2 emissions are emissions that a company causes indirectly and come from where the energy it purchases and uses is produced. For example, the emissions caused when generating the electricity that is used at a site falls into this category.

Scope 3 emissions encompass emissions that are not caused by the operation itself, but by those that it is indirectly responsible for up and down its value chains. An example of this are the use and disposal of products, such as chemical reagents or equipment from suppliers. Scope 3 emissions include all sources not covered by the other 'scopes'.

The reason for these distinctions is that abatement and mitigation strategies will differ depending on the degree of control an operation, such as the combined extraction of CRMs and energy, can exert over the them.

Any energy conversion or mineral extraction system is likely to generate GHG emissions under all three of the Scopes. Thus, the operators of a combined extraction system will use at least at some stage during the life-time of the system equipment and machinery that runs on fossil fuels, such as IC combustion engines, and hence generate **Scope 1** emissions. Although combined extraction systems may generate a significant amount of their stationary energy needs themselves, there is likely to be mains grid energy used at certain times, particularly when the system is off-line for maintenance. How much of **Scope 2** emissions would actually need to be accounted for would also depend on how the overall system is laid out, i.e. whether equipment is run directly of electricity generated on site, or whether this electricity is fed into the mains grid of which in turn the equipment is run. Accounting for these emissions would be further complicated, when the system mainly generates heat that is used in district heating systems. In this case, the emissions saved at the use-point of heating (saved Scope 2 emissions) would need to be balanced against Scope 2 emissions generated by using grid electricity for on-site operations. In the

following assessments **Scope 3** emissions will not be considered explicitly for the project, as we do not have any engineering layouts for operational combined extraction systems. However, it is supposed that such emission would be considerably lower for such systems, than those of conventional mining due to the less complex infrastructure required. When looking at the life-cycle carbon emissions of mining projects one aspect is easily overlooked is the initial carbon release from clearing vegetation at the mine site and the subsequent at least temporary loss of carbon sequestration capacity before revegetation of a mine site. The amount of carbon release and sequestration potential after revegetation depends on the prevailing eco- and soil-systems at the site. Combined extraction projects for heat and minerals have a very small physical footprint compared to a conventional mine, which is another advantage. However, given the wide variety of energy conversion technologies (wind, solar, hydro, nuclear, fossil fuel) and mining methods for energy and non-energy minerals, a generic quantitative comparison is difficult (see e.g. Ritchie, 2022, for some energy conversion related land-use data).

2.3 CONCEPTUAL MODEL FOR COMBINED EXTRACTION

Combined extraction systems can be represented as a network or series of interconnected box-models (input/output-model). Each box represents a system component, for instance a heat-exchanger, a reaction vessel, or a chemical process. In a Sankey-diagram the ‘weight’ of the connecting arrows represents (semi-)quantitatively the fluxes of energy or matter across the boundaries of these boxes. This representation allows to visualise the distribution of energy and matter between different system components. Numerical values for the fluxes can be added to the arrows in order to allow the calculation of quantitative mass balances for the various system components. These diagrams can be drawn for e.g., a single chemical element in order to trace its repartition in the system, which then allows the assessment of extraction efficiencies or to understand the fate of undesirable constituents, such as heavy metals, (toxic) metalloids, or Naturally Occurring Radioactive Materials (NORM).

Figure 1: Illustration of the principle of Sankey-diagrams

On the other hand, it is also possible to trace the repartition of a flux of Total Dissolved Solids (TDS), as it arises at the well-head of a geothermal bore-hole, into the various chemical components, which in turn will end up in different system components (boxes), such as sellable products, wastes to be managed, CO₂ released to the atmosphere, or waters to be re-injected/released into the environment. Likewise, external fluxes, such as process chemicals or energy to operate equipment, can be taken into account, when

calculating the materials and energy balances. In Figure 1 above the principle is illustrated in an arbitrary example.

In order to make assessments comparable and taking into account that a chemical element might appear in the form of different species, the units for the mass-fluxes will have to be moles (mol/l), the unit for energy fluxes e.g. MWh.

A key issue in such studies is to adequately delineate the system boundaries (see Figure 2). In CRM-geothermal we would like to understand, how combined extraction changes the EROI, embodied energies and carbon-footprints of geothermal energy systems and how energy requirements, embodied energies and carbon-footprints of CRM extraction compares with other methods for their extraction.

Figure 2: MFA conceptualisation of a combined extraction system.

We will have to account for two scenarios, one in which CRM-extraction is added to existing geothermal systems and one in which a new system is set up with combined extraction being an integral part of the value proposition.

In principle, a combined extraction system is made up of three elements (cf. Figure 2):

1. The **geothermal system** as such: namely the well(s), surface installations (well-heads, pumps, water treatment plants, facilities for re-injection) etc.);
2. The **energy extraction plant**: heat-exchangers etc. to the point of delivering energy off-site, residues management facilities; and
3. The **materials extraction plant**: the extraction plant itself can consist of several components, depending on the extraction technology chosen and the desired end-product.

In reality, it may not be so straightforward to delineate the three system boundaries. Thus, to prevent scaling and silting of the energy extraction system, a treatment plant may be inserted into the line before the heat exchanger. This will give rise to residues that may contain chemical compounds of interest, that in turn can add to the metal value extracted. The metal extraction system will also alter the properties of the water to be re-injected, due to changes in the original water composition, its temperature and pressure, and

hence also the gas content. These changes to chemical equilibria can lead to corrosion or scaling. The metal extraction plant may actually replace a water treatment system that would otherwise need to be installed. In this sense, the materials extraction could be fully integrated into the flow-scheme, rather than being a mere add-on to an existing geothermal energy system.

As Goldberg et al. (2022) have pointed out, the water flow in certain geothermal systems may be too large to be handled in a materials extraction plant due to the potentially long reaction times needed, so that only a part of the flow might be used for extraction. In Figure 2 a short-cut from the heat-extraction to re-injection would need to be drawn.

CRM-geothermal investigated a number of extraction techniques and how they could be integrated best, also with a view to the marketable end-product, for instance the chemical form of lithium.

The purpose of Material Flow Accounting (MFA) is to make the environmental and economic assessment of combined extraction of heat and metal value comparable with other methods of metal and energy production. This is to calculate the energy required and CO₂-footprint generated by each mol of metal extracted.

In the following the processes and methods being investigated in CRM-geothermal are listed and conceptual Sankey-diagrams for each of them are drawn.

In CRM-geothermal the focus is on the actual extraction of the CRMs, i.e. lithium in the first instance, and the MFA focuses on this aspect (cf. Figure 2). Materials and energy flows for the 'geothermal' side of the system will strongly depend on the local situation (e.g. depth of the boreholes) and the engineering solution chosen. While these are important for an overall comparison of different lithium mining methods, CRM-geothermal intends to contribute to better understand the efficiency and impacts of lithium separation per se. For the purpose of the project, therefore, a boundary for the analyses is drawn where the brine enters the separation system.

2.4 GEOTHERMAL AND ENERGY EXTRACTION SYSTEMS

CRM-geothermal is primarily concerned with the extraction part (the green box in Figure 2). Different extraction methods for metals and He are discussed in Section 2.5 and respective CRM-geothermal Deliverables referenced there.

As indicated in Figure 2, a typical geothermal system consists of a pump to bring the geothermal fluids to the surface, a heat-exchanger, and a pump for re-injection of the cooled-down water, if it is not released to surface water courses. The heat-exchanger is coupled to a secondary circuit. Its design depends on the temperature of the geothermal fluid and the intended use of the contained heat, i.e. conversion of the fluids into steam to drive a turbine for electricity generation or to use the hot water for district or industrial heating etc. There may be additional circuits, for instance to inject flow-enhancing chemicals etc. For each of these circuits a conceptual flow model may need to be drawn. One also needs information about any substances used for this purpose in order to be able to calculate the total embodied energy and material intensities.

For a complete life-cycle balance of the material and energy flows, one also needs data on the site preparation and well construction, as well as those arising from any other infrastructure (e.g. the extraction plant) needed. In line with other low-carbon emitting energy conversion systems, these elements of the life-cycle can be major life-time contributors to the CO₂ balance and wastes generated (cf. Figure 3; McCay et al. 2019;

Sullivan et al. 2010). Of course, total carbon emissions are typically only a fraction compared to what is emitted by fossil fuel-based energy conversion systems, particularly the life-time emissions of coal- or lignite-fired power plants. Data for these ancillary life-cycle elements, which are outside the scope of CRM-geothermal, would come from established MFA-databases, such as Ecoinvent (<https://ecoinvent.org>), or the published literature, e.g. Ducoli et al. (2022).

Figure 3: CO₂-emission from different life-cycle elements of geothermal systems
(McCay et al., 2019).

Certain geothermal systems may emit not insignificant amounts of GHG (e.g. Fridriksson et al. 2017, McCay et al. 2019), particularly CO₂, but literature data appear to be relatively scarce. For none of the geothermal systems that are investigated by CRM-geothermal, neither for the pilot-sites such data are readily available. Where no actual data are available on the materials and energy used during site preparation, well construction and completion, literature can be used (e.g. McCay et al. 2019).

On the other hand and as noted earlier, it has not been the objective of CRM-geothermal to provide a complete assessment of the embodied energy and GHG emission of a geothermal energy systems, but rather to highlight the variables to be considered when making comparative assessments to aid decisions. In the context of this project the additional amounts of embodied energy and GHG arising from the processes and their infrastructure to extract metal value are of main interest.

2.5 MATERIALS EXTRACTION SYSTEMS TESTED

2.5.1 Approach

At the core of the project CRM-geothermal is the development of processes for the direct lithium extraction (DLE) and of other constituents. The extraction systems may involve significant amounts of process materials, such as ion exchange resins, precipitation agents and other chemical reactants. These materials need to be included into the mass, energy, and carbon balances, particularly, when they are consumed during the process. A full MFA would be very onerous and will not be necessary, if the purpose is mainly to demonstrate the competitiveness of combined extraction compared with other methods of extracting the respective constituents. For many common materials used as reactants and other process materials the data for their embedded energy and carbon footprint can be obtained from the literature and specialised data providers. For materials synthesised for the purpose, such data may need to be determined. However, as most of the processes investigated in CRM-geothermal are at the 'proof-of-concept'-stage with correspondingly low TRL, there is no point in undertaking such calculations now. Once the processes have reached a sufficiently high TRL, these calculations can be undertaken to provide hard data for the purpose of comparison as noted earlier.

Figure 4 is a generic representation of mass flows in an extraction system. The process box represents the various extraction systems that were investigated (see Sections 2.5.3 to 2.5.8). The process box will be further subdivided into the relevant steps, depending on the actual extraction system. Likewise, there will be many more different flows, which need to be identified individually in order to achieve the proper mass-balance.

Figure 4: Conceptual representation of mass flows in an extraction system.

It should be noted that the conceptual mass- and energy-flow models also need to cover process steps that may be carried out 'off-line' and in batches, such as desorption from organic or inorganic substrates.

In the sections below the results of the experiments with various extraction methods carried out within CRM-geothermal are briefly discussed with respect to the materials flows. A full discussion of the respective techniques can be found in deliverables cited there. As noted already, the TRL of most of the techniques is still too low to perform meaningful assessments of mass-, energy- and carbon-flows. Therefore, at this stage of development, the mass flow-diagrams are only indicative and qualitative. They can also

change in function of the chosen marketable form of the product extracted. The majority of processes investigated concern the extraction of lithium, with one process also targeting helium.

The section immediately below concerns a somewhat more complete assessment of the processes used by Cornish Lithium at their extraction plant in the current configuration.

2.5.2 Direct Lithium Extraction (DLE) at Cornish Lithium CCL

Direct extraction refers to the fact that the target element, here the lithium, is extracted from the geothermal brine using some sort of direct separation process (cf. Kaymakci & Kölbl, 2022), rather than extracting it as a compound, e.g. a precipitate, from which it has to be separated in further steps. A number of different kinds of technologies can be used for DLE, such as ion exchange, adsorption, electro chemistry, solvent extraction, membrane filtration, and biological treatment. The process will leave behind a brine depleted in lithium specifically. Some of these processes are being experimentally further developed as part of CRM-geothermal (see the following sections).

Figure 5 illustrates the fluid flows in the system currently operated by Cornish Lithium in form of a semi-quantitative Sankey-diagram. The red box on the left represents the conventional geothermal energy conversion system, while the green box on the right shows the steps used to extract the metal value.

Figure 5: Semi-quantitative diagram for the aqueous flows in the DLE at CLL
(percentages indicate normalised fluid mass flows)

One should note that in the above diagram the boundary between the 'energy' and the 'materials' extraction systems could also have been drawn between the filtration and the reverse osmosis steps. This is a matter of what quality criteria for the re-injection waters are imposed on the operator, whether the reverse osmosis is considered a purification or a pre-concentration step. It also depends on the actual extraction technique used, whether such pre-concentration may be required or not.

Ancillary process materials - As indicated in Figure 5, both the energy extraction and the lithium extraction require the use of various process materials. The production of these process materials themselves have ancillary energy and materials (including those considered waste) associated with them. Table 1 illustrates data for embodied energy and carbon for the reactants used as can be found in the literature.

Table 1: Embodied energy and carbon.

Material	Embodied energy	Unit	Embodied carbon	Unit	Reference
HCl	17.50	MJ/kg	0.90	kgCO ₂ -eq/kg	Ducoli et al., 2022
NaOH	12.54	MJ/kg	3.20	kgCO ₂ -eq/kg	Ducoli et al., 2022
NaCl	2.4	MJ/kg	0.18	kgCO ₂ -eq/kg	Ducoli et al., 2022
CaCl ₂			1.53	kgCO ₂ -eq/kg	apps.carboncloud.com
IX-resin	88	MJ/kg	2.92	kgCO ₂ -eq/kg	Franklin Assoc., 2022

Notes on the data in Table 1 above:

NaOH - The embodied energy and carbon refer to 1 kg NaOH (solid), which translates into ca. 1,3 MJ and 0,3 kgCO₂-eq/kg for 1 l of 10% NaOH aqueous solution.

NaCl and CaCl₂ - Precipitated as a white solid during evaporation

LiCl - product is a 40 weight% solution

Ion-exchange resin - proprietary information for the specific DLE process

Ion-exchange resin for DLE - There are many different types of ion-exchange resins used in DLE on the market and one will need the specific data on the one actually used. On the other hand, it appears the many of such resins are based cross-linked polystyrene to which the desired functional groups are added, that provide the ion-exchange capacity (cf. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ion-exchange_resin). As a first approximation, one can assume that most of the embodied energy and carbon are stored in the polystyrene, for which the respective data are available (e.g. Franklin Assoc., 2022, Table 1). One should note, however, that unlike the process chemicals, the resin is not consumed during the process, but backwashed to recover the lithium and re-used. There may be certain losses nevertheless and the resin may need to be replaced periodically. Backwashing means that the resin is returned to its protonated form, meaning that the bound metal cations are replaced by H⁺, for which HCl is used (see Figure 5 and Table 1). The ion-exchange resin as stationary phase, therefore, perhaps should be considered together with the infrastructure of the extraction plant.

Figure 6 and 7 provide an overview over the embodied energy and carbon contributions respectively to the production of LiCl as end-product.

Figure 6: Semi-quantitative diagram for the embodied energy in the DLE at CLL
(percentages indicate normalised fluid mass flows)

Figure 7: Semi-quantitative diagram for the embodied carbon in the DLE at CLL
(percentages indicate normalised fluid mass flows)

2.5.3 Adsorptive extraction by ion sieves

Mn-oxide based ion-sieves

Manganese dioxide-based lithium ion-sieve (LIS) sorbents were used to extract lithium from geothermal brine. The performance of the sorbent was tested in the laboratory and at Tuzla geothermal power plant (Turkey).

The LIS in its protonated state was permeated with the geothermal brine (synthetic or natural). Lithium ions are adsorbed and protons released, so that the LIS in its 'lithiated' state is obtained. The loaded LIS is washed, resulting in the release of some wastewater and is then treated with acid in a flow-through process to displace the Li. A primary extract is obtained as well as waste acid and the LIS is returned to the protonated state. The LIS is then washed to remove excess acid, resulting in a regenerated LIS that can be re-used for the next extraction step.

The primary extract also contains Mn(II) ions, which will have to be removed. A sufficient amount of Na₂CO₃-solution is added in steps to precipitate-out MnCO₃, which is removed by filtering. Then the purified extract is treated with more Na₂CO₃-solution to precipitate purified lithium carbonate.

Figure 8: Materials flows for Li-extraction using MnO₂ ion sieves

This acid treatment and purification is realised by a stepwise batch process: Cumulative desorption was applied to enrich the desorption solution with lithium, and the lithium concentration was increased from 500 ppm to 3000 ppm.

When eventually undertaking an assessment of the materials- and energy-footprints one will need to consider the embodied energies in the MO_2 and the Na_2CO_3 used in the processes.

The flow diagram above serves as an illustration of the process. More details can be found in the forthcoming deliverable D3.1 (Zotzmann et al., forthcoming).

Zeolite-based ion-sieves

10-micron natural zeolite (Clinoptilolite) is treated with geothermal brine from the re-injection line in Tuzla (Turkey). After running the brine for about 1 hour through the zeolite-packed column, the column is taken to the laboratory for desorption and recovery of Sr. Brine-treated zeolites are back-washed with a 1M ammonium acetate solution to desorb the Sr. The first cycle of backwashing yields about 100 ppm Sr concentration. Further enrichment is achieved by treating the enriched solution with fresh zeolite and backwash it again. A step that is repeated nine times, so that concentration is increased to about 450-500 ppm Sr. The Sr-rich solution then is heated to about 95°C and added into a 15% Na_2SO_4 -solution to effect selective Sr precipitation over Ca and Ba. After 2 minutes, the hot solution is filtered with vacuum filtration to obtain a colourless SrSO_4 precipitate.

The flow diagram below serves only as an illustration of the process. More details on the process can be found in the forthcoming deliverable D3.1 (Zotzmann et al., forthcoming).

Figure 9: Materials flows for Sr-extraction using zeolites

2.5.4 Selective ion exchange membranes

The basic extraction process on selective ion-exchange membranes is performed in five steps:

1. sPEEK resin beads extract M^+ and M^{2+} cations from the brine
2. The beads are backwashed with concentrated HCl to remove the M^+ and M^{2+} cations;
3. M^+ and M^{2+} cations are precipitated as chlorides by evaporating the HCl solution;
4. LiCl is dissolved from the mixed chlorides with anhydrous ethanol, the remaining mixed chlorides could be further processed to obtain other metals;
5. The anhydrous ethanol is evaporated and collected for recycling, obtaining 97% pure LiCl.

Over the course of CRM-geothermal experiments were carried out to optimise the recovery rate, to reduce the specific consumption of reactants and energy. The flow diagram below serves only as an illustration of the process. More details on the process can be found in the forthcoming deliverable D3.2 (Di Noto & Negro, forthcoming).

Figure 10: Materials flows for Li extraction by ion-exchange membranes

2.5.5 Selective reversible extraction by modified (bio-)polymers

Various crown ether (CE)-modified (bio-)polymers (P) were prepared as exchange substrates and tested for their selectivity in adsorption of certain critical metals (Mg^{2+} , Rb^+ , and Sr^{2+}) in synthetic brines with NaCl or CaCl_2 as matrix at an ionic strength in the range of $I = 0.1$ to 2 M at temperatures up to 70°C . The adsorbents were backwashed with HNO_3 to bring the extracted cations back into solution. The aim was to investigate the extent to which the ability to selectively absorb the metals is influenced by the competing behaviour of the matrix cations and subsequently to evaluate the potential application of these adsorbents in a large-scale application at a geothermal plant.

Given the multitude of experiments to achieve better recovery and the rather low TRL, the flow diagram below serves only as an illustration of the process in principle. More details on the process can be found in the forthcoming deliverable D3.3 (Feldbusch, forthcoming).

Figure 11: Materials flows for selective reversible extraction by modified (bio)polymers

2.5.6 Bioextraction

Two paths were initially explored, which eventually may be combined: a) Li recovery as Li_2CO_3 via an oxalogenesis-oxalotrophy pathway, and b) Li biosorption.

In the first path, two microbial steps were used: 1 - fungal oxalogenesis, i.e. the ability to produce and secrete oxalic acid, and 2 - bacterial oxalotrophy, i.e. the ability to oxidise oxalic acid/oxalate into carbonic acid to generate adenosine triphosphate (ATP) and biomass. In step 1, fungal oxalic acid is produced *ex situ* and is further added to the geothermal brine. By doing so, oxalic acid turns into oxalate ($\text{pKa}_1 = 1.27$ and $\text{pKa}_2 = 4.28$) given that the brine's pH is above 4.5. Oxalate further combines with most elements in the brine, including Ca, Mg, Sr, Mn, Al, leading to the precipitation of metal-oxalate salts. However, this does not happen with Li, Na, K, and Ti which remain in solution. As a result, addition of fungal oxalic acid allows to clean the fluid from a number of so-called 'impurities' which prevent the recovery of a clean Li fraction. In step 2, bacterial oxalotrophy is then applied to this cleaned fluid. For this second step to work, fungal oxalic acid needs to be applied in excess (or again to the cleaned fluid) so that not all oxalic acid precipitates with 'impurities' in step 1. The oxidation of oxalic acid/oxalate by the oxalotrophic bacterium will lead to an increase in pH. This increase needs to reach at least a pH of 10 in order to enable Li_2CO_3 precipitation as a finale phase. For this, adding an extra step of microbial ureolysis, where urea is degraded to NH_3 and CO_2 along with fluid alkalisation may be considered, depending on the initial fluid pH. Another critical point for Li_2CO_3 precipitation to occur is the Li concentration in the 'cleaned' brine, which needs to be at least 400 ppm. For this, several approaches to enrich Li in this brine may be considered, including DLE techniques, reverse osmosis, as well as biosorption. In the latter, microbial biomass is used to selectively and efficiently sorb Li, in order to be desorbed later and concentrate it in a fluid to be fed to the oxalotrophy step.

Figure 12: Materials flows for Li bioextraction via the oxalate-carbonate pathway

The flow diagram above serves only as an illustration of the process. More details on the process can be found in the deliverable D3.4 (Bindschedler et al., 2025) and the forthcoming deliverable D3.5 (Bindschedler et al., 2025).

2.5.7 Gas (He) extraction

Helium (He) is a crucial resource for medical and high-tech applications, and currently produced as a by-product of natural gas, mainly in Qatar and the USA. In Europe, relatively high concentrations of helium have been found associated with crystalline rocks with nitrogen (N_2) as the main gas component. Such a He- N_2 -rich gas phase was also found as a by-product of geothermal fluids during a pump test in a drill hole of Cornish Lithium Ltd. in summer 2023.

Based on laboratory investigations in batch type experiments with various membrane materials and gas extracting techniques, a two-step process for the extraction of helium from geothermal fluids is proposed by CRM-geothermal:

1. First, a gas-water separation is performed using a membrane gas-separation technique. Based on laboratory experiments and field results, two similarly suitable tubular polymeric membrane materials, namely polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) and polytetrafluorethylene (PTFE), were identified. Free and dissolved gases in the geothermal brine are extracted from the production fluid by inserting tubular membranes into a bypass without interruption of the pumping process.
2. Secondly, the extracted nitrogen-dominated gas, with minor amounts of water vapour, CO_2 and helium is processed with the aim of enriching the helium component in the final gas extract. This involves the removal of water vapour and CO_2 using cryogenic techniques, such as freezing in a liquid nitrogen trap. Further enrichment of helium is achieved by removal of N_2 using titanium getter-sponges or specific molecular sieves. This can be done as a cyclic process to increase the helium concentration in the final extract. Laboratory experiments on the latter are ongoing to gain information on the performance and efficiency of the techniques.

Figure 13: Materials flows for helium extraction

The flow diagram above serves only as an illustration of the process. More details on the process can be found in CRM-geothermal deliverable D3.5 (Strauch & Zimmer, 2025).

2.5.8 Gas-diffusion electrocrystallisation (GDEx)

GDEx is an electrochemical process of reactive precipitation of metals in solution with oxidising or reducing agents produced *in situ* by the electrochemical reduction of a gas in a gas-diffusion electrode. In the porous electrode a triple phase boundary is established between the solution, the gas, and an electrically conducting electrode. The solution containing dissolved metal ions passes through an electrochemical cell equipped with the gas diffusion electrode, making contact with its electrically conducting part (typically a porous layer). The gas (here pure O₂) percolates through a hydrophobic layer on the gas diffusion electrode, acting as a cathode. As the gas diffuses to the electrically conducting layer acting as an electrocatalyst (e.g., hydrophilic activated carbon), the gas is electrochemically reduced to hydroxyl (OH⁻) and hyperperoxyl (HO₂⁻) ions, leading to the formation of metal oxides and hydroxides. The OH⁻ then reacts with metal ions to form solid metal hydroxides that settle out.

Figure 14: Materials flows for Li extraction by Gas-Diffusion Electrocrystallisation

Figure 14 illustrates the extraction of Li⁺ ions in the form of LDH (layered double hydroxides) from natural geothermal brine using the GDEx process. Also, a selective lithium recovery method from Li-Al layered double hydroxides (LDH) can be achieved via leaching with concentrated formic acid. This process preferentially extracts lithium, with

less than 5% of other metals being co-leached. The reaction forms lithium-aluminium formate, metal formates (impurities), oxygen, and water. The formic acid involved can be recovered through distillation, supporting a closed-loop and environmentally sustainable extraction system. The lithium-aluminium formate product is subjected to a two-step thermal treatment in a muffle furnace to form lithium carbonate and aluminum oxides, while releasing CO₂ and water. Further purification is carried out by dispersing the powder in deionised water. Due to the solubility difference—lithium carbonate being soluble up to 13–15 g/L while metal oxides are insoluble—lithium is effectively separated from impurities. This method enables up to 100% lithium leaching from various layered hydroxide/oxide materials and has achieved a 75% lithium recovery efficiency from a solution containing 45 mg/L of lithium.

The flow diagram in Figure 14 serves only as an illustration of the process. More details on the process can be found in the forthcoming deliverable D3.7 (Prasannachandran & Thayumanasundaram, forthcoming).

2.5.9 By-product from scale-formation and -prevention

When geothermal waters are depressurised and cooled down, this may lead to the formation of different types of scales in the pipework, heat-exchangers and other elements of the combined extraction system. Apart from the technical issues they cause, the scales can also act as a trap for metals of potential interest. To overcome this problem, some operators run their systems fully pressurised, from extraction to re-injection of the geothermal fluids.

While the mechanisms of scale-formation and, hence, conceptual solutions to counteract it, were investigated for the pilot sites in CRM-geothermal, it was beyond the scope of the project to propose concrete technical solutions. In consequence, the MFA and LCIA could not cover this aspect of combined extraction of heat and minerals.

Depending on the target metal, the technical step of preventing scale-formation and possible inhibitors (e.g., complexing agents) and other materials used will need to be included as separate elements in the MFA (cf. Figure 5).

If the chosen solution involves the controlled formation of precipitates, e.g., in a reaction tank, the recovery of metals from these scales will need to be treated in a dedicated MFA and LCIA, including possible solid wastes generated.

2.5.10 Conclusions from the laboratory tests performed

A range of successful extraction methods have been developed or are still in course of development at the time of concluding this report. However, the TRL achieved so far is too low for a meaningful comparative assessment with respect to the embodied energies and the carbon-footprint. While the stationary phases for extraction have been identified and laboratory-scale processes have been designed, a meaningful assessment would require at least upscale to a pilot-plant scale. As certain stationary phases will have to be synthesised for the purpose, the ancillary data that enter the balance sheets can only be determined, when the scale of the operation is known.

The comparative assessment of the different extraction methods will not need to only cover their effectiveness and selectivity for the target element, but also the associated costs (see CRM-geothermal Deliverable D4.3; Correia et al., forthcoming) as well as

embodied energies and carbon-footprints. This will help to decide on the overall most efficient extraction system.

However, there will not be a 'one size fits all'-method, but the operational parameters of the produced waters, namely the amount of total dissolved solids, the ionic composition and the temperature may make one or the other extraction more suitable. It may be a case-by-case decision.

2.6 BASELINE ASSESSMENT OF CONVENTIONAL LITHIUM MINING AND PROCESSING

There is a wide variety of metal mining and processing techniques that have a wide range of environmental or carbon footprints and potential societal impacts. For the purpose of this comparative assessment, we will only look at lithium, which is the main target metal for combined extraction in the current project.

In 2020 the German Bundesanstalt für Geowissenschaften und Rohstoffe (BGR) published a concise flyer that aims to summarise the sustainability aspects of current lithium value-chains (Drobe, 2020). Various existing Li value-chains were also examined by Grant et al. (2020). The current SCRREEN2 fact-sheet does not provide any more recent data: the SCRREEN-project produced a range of fact-sheets on CRMs including Li, which were published in March 2023 (https://screen.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/SCRREEN2_factsheets_LITHIUM-update.pdf).

For the present baseline assessment, additional information on energy requirements, carbon footprints and other environmental and societal impacts were sought. However, in many cases the data are proprietary company data and not published, or are listed per company and not per process(-step). Nevertheless, qualitative estimates are possible, as certain process steps for the two main types of lithium mineralisation that are currently explored and exploited, namely brines and pegmatitic rocks, are both very energy or water intensive.

It must also be noted that a full comparison of the LCIs requires in some cases to make assumptions about further processing steps in order to arrive at the same final marketable product for comparison. However, as battery technology is evolving, it is not clear whether this would be Li_2CO_3 , $\text{LiOH} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, or LiCl_2 in a given case. The choice of cathode material for battery production will have a significant impact on the overall carbon-balance of using Li-Ion-Batteries (LIBs). In market reports, data for this reason often are normalised to lithium-carbonate equivalents (LCE), i.e. as mass calculated as if the lithium delivered were Li_2CO_3 .

2.6.1 Lithium extraction from natural brines

Lithium, being an alkali metal, occurs in mineable brine deposits, such as the salars of Chile or Argentina, together with other salts. The basic process steps to be considered in a materials and energy flow assessment are:

Production of Brine: Brine is produced by drilling wells into the brine-bearing strata containing high concentrations of dissolved lithium salts beneath the evaporites of the salars. The brine is then pumped to the surface for processing.

Pre-Treatment: The brine is pre-treated to remove impurities, such as calcium and magnesium ions that can interfere with the subsequent steps of the process. Pre-treatment may involve steps such as pH adjustment, precipitation, and/or filtration.

Concentration: The brine is then pumped into large, shallow evaporation ponds, allowing the water to evaporate under atmospheric conditions and thus the lithium concentration to increase. This step can take several months to a year, depending on the climate and the concentration of lithium in the original brine.

Separation: The concentrated brine is then processed using a combination of separation techniques similar to those used in the CRM-geothermal to further remove impurities and isolate the lithium. Common separation techniques include precipitation, adsorption, ion exchange, and membrane filtration.

Conversion: Finally, the lithium is converted into a battery-grade compound, typically lithium carbonate or lithium hydroxide. This is done using a combination of chemical processes, including calcination and acidification.

As Nguyen and Lee (2018) illustrate in their review, a multitude of processes and combinations thereof are applied in practice, depending on the type of brine encountered. The separation techniques under consideration in CRM-geothermal are among these, so that their respective energy requirements and carbon-footprints do not need to be treated here again.

Figure 15: Conceptual flow-chart for the processing of salar brines
Associated energy requirements are indicated.

Figure 15 provides a conceptual layout of the Li extraction process from the well-head to LiCl. This figure will need to be re-drawn for different processes at different locations.

Beneficiation of the salar brines may allow the recovery of a variety of by-products to Li-production (or they may be the main product, depending on brine composition and market conditions) as Mills (2011) illustrates in Figure 16 below. These by-products would influence the relative energy requirements and carbon-footprint of Li as product, and would also influence the economics of the project.

Figure 16: Hypothetical brine beneficiation flow-sheet (Mills, 2011).

A major energetic advantage of the current exploitation of salars in Chile and Argentina is that the concentration step takes place in open ponds, using solar radiation as energy source. This limits the external energy requirements that otherwise would be considerable. In temperate climate zones this option will not normally be available, although it is used e.g. in Brittany (Guerande) to produce table-salt. As indeed the major energy requirement is in concentrating the brines, this leads to the – justified – claim that more than 90% of the energy consumption of the overall production process comes from renewable sources, namely the direct solar radiation (SQM, 2021). The geographical footprint of the evaporation ponds is not insignificant. Those of SQM amount to 19 km² compared to a total area of the salars of 3000 km², but there is little use competition.

Increased production by existing operations in Chile and Argentina raised concern over the impact on the regional water balances. While the brines in the salars would not have any other use, large-scale pumping can have an effect on the regional water-balance and the adjacent fresh-water aquifers that are used for human consumption. There is also a risk that the draw-down affects the natural salt-lakes that are home to flamingo colonies. All producers actively work on reducing their net extraction and on re-using process waters. See Schmidt (2023, p. 19-21) for a summary of the water-related environmental footprints and the respective societal discourses. Schomberg et al. (2021) assessed the water stress per catchment areas and globally from these Li production systems.

The large-scale lithium projects, existing and planned, in a region with weak infrastructure and economic possibilities gave rise to societal debates mainly in the context of environmental justice claims (e.g. Drobe, 2020; Marchegiani et al., 2019). The latter paper illustrates the complexity of the problem, although the situation is less confrontational than for many other mining projects (cf. Ch. 3).

Depending on the compositions of the respective brines, the various steps to separate other alkali (e.g., Na, K) and the earth alkaline metals (e.g., Mg, Ca) result in residues or by-products, that can be further used for instance as feedstocks in the fertiliser industry. This has a number of positive effects, such the reduction of the amount of extractive waste to be managed, and a reduction of the effective carbon-footprint and energy requirements for the production of Li, which would be repartitioned partly to the by-products. This improves the net environmental and economic balance of the operation (cf. SQM, 2021).

Calculations of the embedded energies in the precipitation agents is difficult, as the amounts used per ton of Li produced is proprietary company information for which the granularity of annual sustainability reporting (e.g., SQM, 2021) is not sufficient.

In Chile an additional CO₂-footprint arises from the fact that the concentrated solutions are transported by tanker-lorries from the Salar in the Atacama Desert to the coastal town of Antofagasta for further processing there. The reasons for this choice are not known, but the alternative would be to construct a processing plant including all the supporting infrastructure in a remote and rather hostile environment. On the other hand, this region would be an ideal environment for photovoltaic solar energy harvesting, although the environmental footprint of these can be higher than that of diesel-generators (Mousavinezhad et al. 2024).

To avoid the environmental impacts, particularly those associated with the extraction and evaporation of brines from the salars, the use of direct lithium extraction methods (cf. Section 2.5) are being explored (e.g. Mousavinezhad et al. 2024). These systems are very similar to the combined extraction systems, except that near-surface brines are used and no heat is being harvested (Figure 17).

Figure 17: Comparison of evaporation with DLE in the exploitation of salars
(Mousavinezhad et al. 2024).

2.6.2 Lithium extraction from pegmatites

Pegmatites are igneous rocks, mainly granites, that are particularly rich in rare minerals, including lithium-bearing minerals, such as spodumene, lepidolite and others. Li-extraction follows a complex sequence of extraction and beneficiation steps to arrive at battery-grade Li products, which will vary in detail, depending on the target minerals and gangue in feedstock from the mine (cf. Figure 18):

Mining: The Li-rich minerals are extracted using standard underground or open-cast mining techniques, although alternative techniques, such as blasting and *in situ* leaching from boreholes, have been discussed.

Crushing and grinding: The feedstock is crushed and ground into small particles to increase its surface area, facilitating the extraction of the lithium.

Froth flotation: The crushed feedstock is mixed with water and flotation chemicals to create a slurry, which is then subjected to froth flotation. In this process, air bubbles are introduced into the slurry, which attach to e.g. the spodumene particles, causing them to float to the surface. The spodumene is skimmed off the top and dried. Alternatively, dense media separation can be used, which separates ores and gangue due to their different specific density.

Roasting: The spodumene concentrate is then roasted/calcined at high temperatures to convert the lithium-bearing minerals into a form that is easier to digest.

Digestion: The roasted spodumene is mixed with sulfuric acid to produce a lithium sulfate solution.

Filtration: The lithium sulfate solution is filtered to remove suspended solids.

Conversion: Finally, the lithium is converted into a battery-grade compound, typically lithium carbonate or lithium hydroxide. The filtered solution is treated to precipitate the lithium as lithium carbonate, which can then be further processed into lithium hydroxide, depending on market requirements.

Figure 18: Mass and energy flow for the extraction of Li from hard rocks

As Nguyen and Lee (2018) have pointed out, hydrometallurgical processes are preferred today over pyrometallurgical processes due to likely lower environmental impacts from e.g. less air emissions and lower energy requirements. For a comparison, however, one would need to include the energy embedded in the chemical reactants and associated carbon-footprints into assessments. Sulfuric acid is typically produced on site of the ore processing plant from elemental sulfur using the so called 'contact process'. Today most

elemental sulfur on the markets originates in desulfurication processes, particularly of the oil and gas industry.

The various options for the beneficiation (crushing/grinding and flotation etc.) of hard-rock ores has recently been reviewed by Tadesse et al. (2019), aiming to consolidate the respective literature. Dense media separation and (froth) flotation are the main techniques used. Typically, dense media used in mineral separation include benzene, bromoform, tetrabromethane, methylene iodide, or Clerici's solution (an aqueous solution of equal parts of thallium formate ($\text{Tl}(\text{HCO}_2)$) and thallium malonate ($\text{Tl}(\text{C}_3\text{H}_3\text{O}_4)$). Most of these chemicals are toxic and of environmental concern. The potential environmental impacts of froth flotation agents have been reviewed in European Commission *et al.* (2021). Given the wide variety of these supporting materials, it is difficult to compile data for comparing energy requirements and environmental impacts. It would need to be done on a case by case, when the actual compounds (to be) used are known. However, this processing step does not exist in extraction of lithium from brines and constitutes an additional energy requirement for both, producing the necessary reagents and their application, plus the possible environmental risks.

Karrech et al. (2020) reviewed the well-established processing options, such as calcination, roasting, chlorination, carbonate pressure leaching, caustic/acidic digestion and others in order to assess their significance in the modern lithium value-chains. In addition, emerging processes that involve direct mechano-chemical activation, bioleaching, acidic or caustic leaching were evaluated and compared to proven approaches in terms of economic and environmental viability. All pyrometallurgical processes are very energy intensive, have a large CO_2 -footprint, and their off-gases can be of environmental concern. Lithium ores are not sulfidic, so acid waste drainage is not normally a concern. Hydrometallurgical and bioleaching processes may have energy requirements closer to the processes of lithium extraction from geothermal fluids. The energies embedded in the necessary reactions would need to be assessed.

In the current value-webs for Li production from hard-rocks, the production of ore concentrates and the final, marketable product (Li_2CO_3 or $\text{LiOH} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$) are geographically widely separated, in Australia and China respectively. This results in significant transport-related CO_2 -footprints. China imports annually around 1.6 Mio tonnes of concentrates that contain 6% Li_2O , which means that China has to manage about 1.5 Mio tonnes (dry mass) of tailings. According to Schmidt (2023) there are developments in Germany to bring more of these value-web elements to Europe and to reduce their environmental footprints by utilising the tailings and captured CO_2 for the conversion into Li_2CO_3 .

The preparation of a mine site, the construction of the mine, and its operation can have significant environmental risks and impacts (e.g. Eco-Efficiency et al. 2023). Thus, land clearance for a conventional pegmatite mine and its associated extractive waste management facilities will lead to an initial release of carbon from the removed vegetation and a loss of carbon sequestration capacity until the respective sites have been successfully remediated and revegetated.

2.6.3 Lithium extraction from oil-field brines

While brines are an undesirable by-product from oil-fields, they may constitute an interesting Li resource in depleted and unproductive oil-fields. Such oil-fields are usually well-characterised with respect to their reservoir properties, reducing considerably the up-front exploration costs. Volt Lithium Corp. in Alberta, Canada, recently completed a pilot project (Volt, 2023) and achieved all-in operating costs of less than USD 2900/t of LCE (<https://voltlithium.com/projects-and-assets/>). The company did not disclose the Direct Lithium Extraction (DLE) method used (Figure 19).

Figure 19: Lithium extraction from oil-field brines in Alberta, Canada (Volt, 2023)

As oil is being produced as by-product, this will have a negative impact on the overall carbon footprint of the operation, although it potentially replaces oil produced on purpose elsewhere. This oil-production may partially off-set the fossil fuels needed in the relatively remote locations to pump the brines and to run the treatment plant.

2.7 SUSTAINABILITY ASSESSMENTS FOR LITHIUM PRODUCTION

As Pell & Lindsay (2021) have pointed out: “Moving to SSBs [Solid State Batteries] as the norm will put huge supply pressure on the lithium chain to produce even more than currently used for LIB applications. The difference between brine, geothermal, sedimentary clay and spodumene impacts is therefore hugely important to discuss for all battery manufacturers, and opportunities exist for low-impact products by engaging this supply chain.”

Undertaking comprehensive material flow assessments as guidance to compare different technical options for e.g. the production of lithium from different types of sources is therefore needed, but extremely complex as discussed above. The main reason is the wide variety of ancillary processes and materials, such as reactants, used and their respective embodied energies and associated carbon-footprints.

The SCRREEN Fact-Sheet (op. cit.) reviewed some recently published literature: “The CO₂ emissions from LiOH · H₂O production range from 5.0 tonnes per tonne of LiOH · H₂O (case of Chilean brine) to 14.8 tonnes of CO₂ per tonne of LiOH · H₂O (Australian source of spodumene, processed in China; Grant et al., 2020). These results are in reasonable alignment with those of Kelly et al. (2021), who calculate a greenhouse gas footprint of 6.9 - 7.3 tonnes CO₂-eq/tonne LiOH · H₂O from lithium extracted from brine, and of 15.7 tonnes CO₂-eq/tonne LiOH · H₂O for lithium extracted from ore processed in Australia with LiOH · H₂O production in China. Moreover, ‘water’ stands for a high-risk regarding lithium exploitation (Lèbre et al., 2020), still with differences depending on the production routes.” It should be noted that the CO₂-footprint calculated by Grant et al. (2020) also included various transport steps, as for instance Australia produces ore concentrate, but not the final Li-product. In addition, a transport step to Rotterdam harbour was included for European consumers. On the other hand, Pell & Lindsay (2021) considered the impact from transport negligible compared to other factors.

Razmjou (2024) in his review of DLE also looked at the sustainability aspects, notably the CO₂ footprint and the energy and water consumption. The main issue with published data is that they are incomplete and not comparable with respect to their systemic LCA coverage. Thus, ancillary processes and embedded carbon or energy may not be reported. Different reports thus may present contradictory or discrepant information.

Without knowing the exact supply sources and production methods for the ancillary materials only estimates can be provided on the basis of literature data. Grant et al. (2020) faced the same problem, but arrived at the values for the specific CO₂-footprint in Figure 20. Again, one should note that these calculations included various transportation steps.

Kelly et al. (2021) arrive at a similar picture, indicating that the Li₂CO₃-production with production in China from Australian spodumene concentrates that uses coal as the main energy source is highly energy intensive and has a significant carbon footprint (Figure 21).

Figure 20: CO₂-intensity of different value-chains of LiOH·H₂O (Grant et al. 2020).

Figure 21: Cradle-to-Delivery-Gate GHG emissions for different Li₂CO₃ value chains (Kelly et al., 2021)

Pell & Lindsay (2021) use a Global Warming Potential (GWP) as metric for comparison for Lithium ferrous phosphate (LFP) batteries and arrive at similar pictures for Li₂CO₃ from different sources. Clearly, the production from geothermal systems has the lowest overall impacts in terms of CO₂ equivalents emitted from this component in battery production (Figure 22).

Figure 22: Global warming potential of sulfide SSBs in function of Li source. ,Baseline' refers to the 70:30 global spodumene:brine split (Pell & Lindsay, 2021)

Vulcan Energy Resources Ltd. concluded a lower environmental impact for its 'Zero Carbon Lithium™' project, extracting Li as hydroxide monohydrate from geothermal fluids, currently developed in the Upper Rhine Graben, Germany (ERM, 2024; Mouchot et al., 2023), in comparison to the hard rock mining and evaporation ponds as other sources of Li (Figure 23).

Per tonne of lithium hydroxide produced

Figure 23: Comparison environmental impacts from different Li production routes (<https://v-er.eu/zero-carbon-lithium/>).

Figure 24 (below) shows a ballpark sustainability analysis of DLE compared to solar evaporation and hard rock mining undertaken by Razmjou (2024). The freshwater consumption and water footprint of lithium production should not be conflated, as the water footprint considers additional hidden waters, such as those used to make reagents. Likewise, the carbon footprint and carbon emission, which are partially linked to energy consumption, should not be confused. As noted in previous sections, the carbon footprint encompasses various forms of carbon, including Scope 1-3 emissions. Also, the water and carbon footprint and consumption/emission of Li₂CO₃ and LiOH is different, however great care is needed when considering these factors since there can be discrepancies in measurement criteria, making like-for-like comparisons difficult.

Figure 24: Environmental footprint comparison of different extraction methods (Razmjou, 2024)

Thus, adequate definition of system boundaries, ancillary data and standards are key in LCA of systems and to fairly compare various Li production technologies.

One needs to read with caution claims made by various commercial projects with respect to their CO₂-footprint. These are not necessarily ‘cradle-to-delivery gate’ calculations and may not include all the embodied energies and CO₂-footprints. It is rather unlikely that the overall total life-cycle CO₂-footprint is actually negative, considering the embodied energy in the infrastructure and the transport of the extracted lithium.

Figure 25: Climate change impact by process stage for 1 kg CO₂ eq. LiOH·H₂O
(Vulcan Energy, 2023)

The global warming potential (GWP) of Vulcan’s Lithium Hydroxide Monohydrate product has been assessed by Minviro Ltd. in February 2023 with a cradle-to-gate approach, meaning the product’s life cycle impact has been assessed from the point of resource extraction to the final product. This LCA has been conducted according to ISO-14040:2006 (ISO, 2006a) and ISO-14044:2006 (ISO, 2006b), using for emission factors the Ecoinvent 3.9 (<https://ecoinvent.org>) database. Capital goods and infrastructure, such as production of machinery and construction of buildings, were omitted from the system analysis, as well as reagents and product packaging materials. According to ISO-14044:2006, the negative carbon emissions highlighted in Figure 25 are allocated to the overall CO₂ avoidance that results from feeding renewable energy into the grid and decarbonising the heating system of the plant.

It should also be noted that the geothermal waters are normally re-injected into the ground, unlike for the natural brine systems in S-America, where the water is let to evaporate, thus contributing to regional water stresses (cf. Schomberg et al., 2021).

Razmjou (2024) notes indeed that re-injection of the geothermal waters, as it is envisaged for the combined extraction systems under investigation by CRM-geothermal, would reduce the effective water-footprint of DLE of combined extraction systems to nearly zero.

As noted above, obtaining data for all the embodied energies, CO₂-footprints, and materials is rather onerous, even when drawing on generic life-cycle inventory databases. For this reason, the boundaries around the systems to be compared were drawn in a way to exclude steps common or comparable for all production routes. The purpose was to arrive at an assessment of the net balances for each system considered in this project and to compare them with alternative systems for lithium extraction.

The MFA had three main purposes: i) to provide a solid basis for comparing combined extraction with other sources for lithium, ii) to allow the comparison of different Li removal approaches in combined extraction, and iii) to demonstrate the limited environmental impacts from adding metal extraction to geothermal energy systems.

Literature data show clearly that extracting Li from geothermal waters has significant advantages with respect to embodied energy and the carbon footprint compared to other sources of lithium such as pegmatites or natural brines, unless the latter also employs DLE systems.

The information collected during the project for different extraction systems (see Section 2.5) seem to corroborate these views, but their TRL still is too low to provide hard data for a real comparison.

The low additional embodied energy and carbon footprint from extracting Li from geothermal waters as well as the low amounts of extractive waste generated will be plusses in the discussion with stakeholders. Their possible reaction to these data is discussed in more detail in Deliverable D4.2 (Mitchell et al., 2025). However, the observed attitudes have to be separated from the more general attitude towards geothermal plants. Here the discussion is dominated by the fear of seismic events caused by the extraction and re-injection of fluids. More details on the respective narratives are given Deliverable D4.2 (Mitchell et al., 2025).

In the framework of CRM-geothermal, a conceptual framework was provided and highlighting the materials and processes that are typically particularly energy-intensive and thus may have a significant carbon-footprint. At the same time, it was attempted to conceptually reduce the different processes investigated to those aspects that are different. In this way, when deciding on the most appropriate technology, the common aspects can be ignored. This may be for instance anything below the well-head.

In a practical case, low embedded energies and a low carbon footprint will not be the only viability criteria, but also the unit cost in comparison to other sources of lithium. This unit cost needs to remain below that of other sources of lithium as discussed in CRM-geothermal deliverable D4.3 (Correia et al., forthcoming).

It should be noted that the final decision may be guided by other aspects, in addition to energy efficiency and carbon-footprint, such as the applicability of certain processes to a given geothermal water composition, flow-rates that have to be accommodated, integrability into an existing geothermal energy extraction system and others.

3 INTERNALISATION OF ESG REQUIREMENTS

3.1 WHAT ARE ESG REQUIREMENTS?

Environmental, Societal and Governance (ESG) requirements are borne out of the need to address issues around risks, impacts, expectations and company behaviour in the context of any extractive operation, including combined extraction. In other words, it revolves around how companies go about addressing environmental and socio-economic risks and how these risks shape the extraction strategy and processes in all relevant dimensions. In order to define such requirements, it is necessary to define the system boundaries and to specify for what purpose these requirements are formulated. From a project perspective the ESG requirements can be used to assess and mitigate any risks that may adversely affect project implementation. On the other hand, projects may need to be assessed with respect to their sustainability in a wider sense in order to justify, whether to go ahead with it at all or in the chosen form. Of course, the two aspects are linked and are building on the same set of data and information. A difficulty arises from the fact that 'sustainability' is an only loosely defined concept and may be used and interpreted differently by different stakeholders. While we are in CRM-geothermal concerned about the overall 'sustainability' of combined extraction of heat and mineral raw materials as such, we want to give practitioners a tool that can help them to assess the potential impacts and risks of their projects and thus to identify possible mitigation strategies. This in turn will provide project promoters with arguments in any sustainability or stakeholder acceptance debate that may arise from the project.

Over the past decades a large body of literature on ESG requirements and how to implement them in extraction projects has been accumulated. The importance of ESG aspects for the successful implementation of extraction projects has been acknowledged by including them into the resources and reserves reporting processes for investors (see. Ch. 5 for details). The viability of extraction projects is assessed on the basis of reporting standards, such as CRIRSCO or UNFC. In the first instance, these describe a mineral occurrence from its geological perspective and the feasibility of extraction and processing from a mining and process engineering perspective with a view to provide investors decision-making information. However, a range of so-called 'modifying factors' are introduced that describe the context of a potential extractive operation, which may help or hinder its implementation.

For the (self-)assessment of operations with respect to their sustainability and with a view to disclose such information in annual reports to the public together with corporate financial and social responsibility reporting (CSR) various standards have been developed, namely those by the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI, <https://www.globalreporting.org>) or the Sustainability Accounting Standards Board, SSAB, <https://sasb.org/>. In 2014, amending earlier Directives, the EU put in place the more comprehensive CSR Directive 2014/95/EU (CEU, 2014b), which applies, however, only to enterprises with more than 500 employees. In 2023 a Regulation was put into place that details the scope of assessments and reporting at a European level for those entities to which Directive 2014/95/EU applies (EC, 2023). A more detailed review of the complex of social responsibility and sustainability reporting initiatives, schemes, and regulations, however, is beyond the scope and purpose of this report. The focus of this report is on the comparison of the potential impacts of

combined extraction of heat and metals with that of other extraction methods and not on developing methods of comprehensive sustainability reporting for such undertakings. It is also likely that the respective enterprises will not fall under the Directive 2014/95/EU, which does not preclude them, of course, to voluntarily comply with these requirements. The **societal dimension** is complex and, therefore, has been the subject of a separate Task under CRM-geothermal (see Deliverable D4.2; Mitchell et al. 2025). The complexity is illustrated by societal discourses around brine extraction from salars in Argentina and Chile. Although the mining companies in Argentina seem to have acted largely in good faith, the societal processes did not result in an agreement with the local (indigenous) communities because the process was perceived to be framed and imposed on them by the mining companies (Marchegiani et al, 2019). It is therefore important not only to enter into a societal dialogue with the local communities, but to also enable these communities to shape it in a way that it serves their needs. This is in fact in line with the MIREU recommendations for obtaining social licensing for operation (SLO) in the mining industry (Tost et al., 2021). The recommendations for internalising societal aspects (Section 3.3) take this into consideration.

In Section 3.2 below the environmental aspects are discussed in more detail. The need for taking ESG aspects into the (economic) equation of extractive operations to avoid risks becoming issues has been nicely summed up by Steele-Schober et al. (2020):

- 1. Not applying the same level of rigour to understanding ESG considerations as we do for other technical disciplines e.g., mine-planning. Because Sustainability is not a clearly delineated discipline, and has an inherently high level of uncertainty – much of which is qualitative, it has not always received the same focus and input as more quantitative disciplines, where we can get a number and know that it's right or wrong to fair, or at least quantifiable, level of certainty.*
- 2. Historically, ESG has been seen as a separate section of a project, aimed at providing some qualitative risk input. The financial impacts of the ESG risks have not always been quantified and the information used to determine appropriate action.*
- 3. Due to a lack of rigour or possible uncertainties, the tendency is to be overly optimistic regarding ESG risk impacts to balance out risk conservatism in other areas, providing a “more spread” picture. Belief in the Board Room and amongst experts from more quantitative disciplines that all ESG risks can be mitigated at the operational phase.*
- 4. ESG issues are often only considered as qualitative risks for too long and therefore projects are unable to mitigate or implement change once these evolve from risks to issues.*
- 5. In many cases, ESG risks become issues that are often project stoppers or significant eroders of value. Earlier and better understanding of the risk case reduces the chances of this occurring, and allows for better up-front decisions to be made.*

3.2 LIFE-CYCLE RISKS AND IMPACTS - ASSESSMENT AND MITIGATION

3.2.1 Risk categories

Basis for risk assessment here are the *Guidelines for Risk Assessment in the Extractive Industries* recently developed on behalf of DG ENV (Eco-Efficiency et al., 2023). These guidelines include a comprehensive catalogue of environmental and OSH risks. Pertinent EU regulations and directives (cf. Section 4.3) were also be taken into consideration.

The cited Guidelines cover four main Focus Areas (FAs) that reflect the life-cycles of extractive operations:

- FA1 – Exploration
- FA2 – Project development
- FA3.1 – Surface extraction
- FA3.2 – Underground extraction
- FA3.3 – Processing
- FA4 – Closure, remediation and long-term management

Of these, the Focus areas FA1, FA2, and FA3.3 are of particular relevance in the context of combined extraction. Combined extraction as such has not been covered by these Guidelines, although *in situ*-leaching (ISL) operations have been mentioned.

The exploration phase often is also the first moment, when a potential future project comes into contact with the local population. The exploration crew, therefore, needs to be prepared to enter into meaningful interaction with stakeholders in order to prepare the ground for a relationship built on trust (cf. Tost et al., 2021; CRM-geothermal Deliverable D4.2: Mitchell et al., 2025).

A key conceptual approach in all risk assessment is the ‘source – pathway – receptor’ paradigm, or in other words:

What is the cause of the risk? – how can it cause harm? – who or what can be affected?

Risk management can address any of the three elements, but the preference is for treating the source, then if the first is not feasible, the pathway. Removing receptors by, for instance, preventing the access of the public to zones (potentially) at risk should only be the last resort. However, (temporary) receptor removal is a typical risk management method in a technical context by e.g. limiting the amount of time an employee can spend in higher risk parts of a plant, fencing off certain areas, guard rails, etc. The discussions in the following section can all be seen conceptually in this way.

3.2.2 Exploration

Exploration activities have specific environmental and operational health & safety (OHS) risks associated with them, but at the same time allow to establish the baseline for environmental impact assessments (EIAs) and for planning the future safe operation of combined extraction. Exploration activities may include the following:

- Remote / desktop studies prior to entering the field to undertake Exploration;
- Planning for field operations with minimal impacts and environmental risks in view;
- Mapping and collection of exploration datasets without removing samples for analysis (including geological mapping, geophysical surveys, and any environmental or socio-economic baseline studies that can/should be undertaken at this stage);
- Collection of samples in the field for chemical analysis (including geological, mineralogical, and geochemical sampling);
- Invasive (explosive seismic) or non-invasive (hammer seismic, geoelectric, geomagnetic, geotelluric, etc.) geophysical surveys;
- Exploration drilling and sampling (via a variety of drilling techniques, incl. borehole geophysics);

- Drafting of the mineral and energy resource and reserve disclosure statement (in line with e.g. PERC (2021), UNECE (2021), and/or other applicable Codes and Standards) with respect to ESG requirements;
- Closure and remediation of the Exploration site(s) if needed.

Perhaps the most invasive operation during exploration is the drilling of boreholes. As boreholes for combined extraction are likely to be very deep, they will pass through various aquifers, which entails the risk of hydraulic short-circuiting and cross-contamination, if not carried out with the necessary care, such as casing. Drilling sites also need to be made safe, so that any spilled drilling fluids, potentially contaminated waters, or drill-chippings can be contained and eventually removed for safe disposal, if needed. The preparation of the drilling-site itself may impact the local flora and fauna and the soil properties. Drilling operations are often noisy and may disturb local fauna as well as people nearby. The construction of access roads and the use of public roads for the transportation of materials and equipment will have further impacts to consider.

Similar considerations apply to seismic reservoir exploration, where also disturbance by blasting or vibro-seismic vehicles may be an issue.

Particular care must be exercised in vulnerable and low-metabolism regions, such as the arctic, alpine, or semi-arid regions, where self-healing of damages to ecosystems will take a very long time.

Exploration will feed into an assessment of resources and reserves compliant with CRIRSCO-aligned standards, PERC for Europe, and/or UNFC. As will be discussed in more detail in Chapter 5, this kind of resource assessment or classification will also consider potential environmental and societal impacts as well as the governance context of any future exploitation project in form of so-called modifying factors. This means in practice, that the respective potential life-cycle risks for an extractive project should be outlined at this moment.

3.2.3 Project development

While the project development activities *per se* are not likely to entail any environmental or OHS impacts, their outcomes may well do. Planning for the whole life-cycle of the envisaged extractive operation is important in order to reduce its potential impacts in the ESG space. Such planning will encompass in the case of combined extraction of heat and minerals the construction of the various extraction- and injection wells, the siting and construction of the industrial facilities, namely the power-plant and the plant for the extraction of the metal value including storage areas for reactants and products, management facilities for extractive and processing wastes, transport routes for reactants and products, etc.

Lohne et al. (2018) undertook a comprehensive review of life-cycle risk and integrity assessments for high-temperature geothermal wells (see Figure 26 below) and also made suggestions for respective regulations. Of particular relevance during the planning phase is the casing design that intends to prevent short-circuiting between different water-bearing zones. Similarly, well-completion (casing, cementation) according to plan needs to be assured.

Figure 26: Different phases in the life-cycle of a well (Lohne et al., 2018).

Damien et al. (2023) have undertaken a comprehensive review of induced seismicity issues around the Upper Rhine Graben geothermal energy systems and the public and regulatory stance towards them. A seismic monitoring network will need to be set up before the actual drilling and well-enhancing begins. In any case, the development of such systems will be planned and supported by reservoir modelling similar to what is done in the hydrocarbon industry, also looking at the hydrogeochemical aspects.

One aspect during construction that may attract particular attention by the public are measures to increase the permeability, water/heat flows, and reactive surfaces down-hole. Such measures consist of pumping fluids at high pressure into the boreholes with a view to open up fractures and other discontinuities. The fractures etc. are kept open by pumping sand or zirconium spheres into the voids thus created. This technique is/was regularly used by the hydrocarbon industry to increase yield. Public concerns arose due to the use of flow-improving surfactants and the seismic activity caused or triggered. While in combined extraction facilities the use of reactants down-hole is generally not envisaged, there is the risk of seismic events due to the disturbance of the rock-stresses at depth by the extraction of waters or the ‘fracking’ process. Certain national regulations now forbid ‘fracking’ in the context of hydrocarbon exploitation, but explicitly permit it in the context of using geothermal energy.

The drilling of the various wells will give rise to a small amount of extractive waste, which will need to be managed according to the requirements of the Extractive Waste Directive (CEU, 2006a). Any inert components of these wastes probably can be re-used on site for construction purposes. Most other wastes arising from the operation will be typical urban or industrial wastes and have to be managed accordingly.

Project development will include the permitting application procedures, as these will be iterative with more detailed planning. At this moment also the final EIA will be developed together with the mitigation plans for any risks and impacts potentially arising.

OHS risks during plant construction are akin to those of other drilling operations and construction sites and the respective safety at the workplace regulations will apply (cf. Section 4.3.2, namely the Directives 89/391/EEC (CEU, 1989) and 92/91/EEC (CEU, 1992)). Interactions with (local) stakeholders will continue from the exploration phase, as stakeholder concerns or preferences may influence the design and mode of operation of the extractive operation.

While combined extraction projects are likely to have a rather long life-time, it is still necessary to make preliminary plans for closure, decommissioning, and long-term management of any extractive waste facilities constructed in particular.

Ideally, the combined extraction plant should also be integrated into the socio-economic fabric of the region.

3.2.4 Extractive operation and processing

Unlike for most other extractive operations, the risks and actual impacts from combined extraction operations are expected to be relatively small. Once the plant has been built, there will be little changes to the surface features during the operational phase. All processes take place in closed circuits and inside buildings with virtually no emissions and releases under normal operating conditions. As has been discussed in Chapter 2, there is no clear distinction between extraction and processing compared to conventional mining, although there may be distinct sections in the plant (cf. Figure 2). Therefore, the risks discussed separately in the *Guidelines* (Eco-efficiency et al., 2023) are discussed here together.

The main operating risks would be spills and aqueous releases due to pipe breakages. Safety measures typically encompass the construction of impervious basins around the plants to prevent releases into surface waters or sewers, as well as overflow tanks and similar. Whether the new Industrial Emissions Directive 2024/1785 (CEU 2024) would apply to such installations remains to be seen.

From the OHS perspective, the main operating risks are the accidental exposure to hot and/or acid/caustic fluids, reagent chemicals, and the exposure to steam due to mis-operation or malfunctioning of equipment. Such risks are covered by Directives 89/391/EEC (CEU, 1989) and the subsidiary national workplace regulations. The chemical compounds used in the extraction processes may need to be assessed according to Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 for any specific workplace or environmental hazards.

It may be debatable, whether the wastes from extracting the metal value from the geothermal fluids are extractive or processing wastes, in other words under which legislation they should fall. Safe management routes will depend on the contents of certain elements or compounds, such as heavy metals, radionuclides, arsenic etc., for which no further use or recycling routes are foreseen. Some of these materials may be used on site for further construction purposes. Compared to other types of extractive operations these quantities will be very small. Organic wastes, such as spent ion exchange resins will need to be managed as industrial waste at licensed disposal or incineration facilities, if they cannot be recycled.

3.2.5 Closure, decommissioning and after-care

Once the combined extraction facility has reached the end of its useful life, e.g. due to temperature draw-down, exhaustion of target minerals, or clogging of the open permeabilities, it will need to be closed in an orderly fashion. This may include a slow re-establishment of the original hydraulic regime, if the combined extraction operation resulted in any such change.

Upon closure, structures above and below ground need to be decommissioned so that they do not constitute any long-term risks and cause in impacts. Once the well-head installations have been removed, the wells need to be capped to prevent foreign items entering them and causing contamination. Depending on the well design, casings may need to be drawn and certain layers be sealed in order to prevent hydraulic short-circuiting and cross-contamination. Installations and structures above ground will need to be dismantled, if no further use for them is foreseen. Construction materials will be cleaned and decontaminated (if needed), so that they can be re-used or recycled.

Any contamination in the ground from spills etc. will need to be removed and the site remediated, if necessary. Unless there is contamination by heavy metals, hazardous chemicals, or radionuclides, it can be foreseen that most removed materials can be directed to recycling.

Any extractive waste facility constructed during the operation needs to be closed and made long-term stable, if not designed in this way already. Respective guidance can be found in MWEI-BREF (2018).

3.3 GUIDANCE ON THE INTERNALISATION PROCESS

3.3.1 Overview

Based on the work outlined above, a scheme for the internalisation of ESG requirements has been developed, to be implemented through a check-list that accompanies the development of combined extraction sites. The check-list takes prospective operators through several steps to help them identify ESG risks along the life-cycle of a facility. The operators are thus enabled to address these potential ESG risks before they become active risks. The check-list also helps to inform discussions with regulators and other (e.g. civil society) stakeholders.

This check-list consists of two parts, namely on a comprehensive project description that is based on the CRIRSCO reporting template (CRIRSCO, 2024; SAMESG, 2017) and on the extensive risk catalogue that was developed in the context of drafting the Guidelines for Risk Assessment in the Extractive Industries (Eco-Efficiency et al., 2023). This risk catalogue focuses on the environmental and OHS risks and less on societal or governance issues.

This check-list would be completed first at the project development stage and then updated periodically with the as-built information with a view to check, whether any of the original assumptions has changed.

3.3.2 Comprehensive project description

The SAMESG (2017) guidance intends to support ‘competent persons’, i.e. persons with relevant (risk) knowledge, rather than potential (combined extraction) project developers. Thus, the SAMREG guidance is written very much from the investors’ perspective and, thus, needed to be reformulated to cover ESG issues from a more general environmental and societal sustainability or strategic impact perspective (Table 5).

Table 5: ESG check-list, adapted from SAMESG (2017).

General
1. Provide a description of organisational structure, systems, policies, procedures and management plans, and governance procedures in place to manage ESG issues.
Key plans, maps and diagrams
1. Provide a map which identifies the locality of sensitive receptors to be included on maps within the project area and at least the zone of influence of the site. All surface water features to be included on maps.
2. Identify and describe the location of any sensitive areas within and around the project area and within the zone of influence of the site.

<p>Legal aspects</p>
<p>1. Outline the applicable ESG legal compliance requirements and any mandatory and/or voluntary standards or guidelines to which the project will (have to) subscribe.</p>
<p>2. Identify the ESG permits, authorisations and licences that will be required. Assess whether there is a reasonable basis to believe that all ESG permits, authorisations and licences can be obtained.</p>
<p>3. In case of an already existing geothermal plant, provide a description of any pending administrative enforcement action such as but not limited to directives or compliance notices instituted against the operation, including a notice received by the operator of an authority's intention to issue a directive or compliance notice, by any authority concerned with the regulation of ESG issues whether or not such pre-compliance notice or compliance notice has been suspended pending corrective action.</p>
<p>4. Provide a description of any known future financial liabilities that arise by virtue of recognised claims, penalties, fines, damages and administrative enforcement action that will become due and payable in future.</p>
<p>Environmental parameters</p>
<p>1. Provide an appropriate analysis of the environmental context within which the project is located (or provide the contents of the mandatory EIA). Give an appropriate analysis of the material aspects and impacts that may need consideration including how existing activities may exacerbate or mitigate existing aspects and impacts.</p>
<p>2. Describe, assess and prioritise the risks associated with any obvious environmental factors that may require modifications to the planned combined extraction project. Focus on issues that are likely to remain significant despite the implementation of proven and economically viable mitigation measures.</p>
<p>External societal and political parameters</p>
<p>1. Provide an appropriate analysis of the external societal and political context within which the project is located.</p>
<p>2. Describe and prioritise current societal and political risks, and potential risks that take into account how activities may exacerbate or mitigate existing risks.</p>
<p>3. Describe any societal and political issues that may have a material effect on the planned project. Include issues that are likely to remain material despite the implementation of proposed mitigation measures.</p>
<p>Internal social parameters</p>
<p>1. Describe and assess the risks associated with any obvious internal social factors and/or specific contextual details that could have a material effect on the planned project.</p>
<p>Conformance and compliance audits</p>
<p>1. Provide a description of legal compliance audits undertaken, including a summary of material findings and management plans to address these findings.</p>
<p>2. Provide a description of ESG management system conformance audits undertaken, including a summary of material findings and management plans to address these findings.</p>

ESG liability
1. Describe the closure, societal obligations, rehabilitation plan, activities, remaining liability and compliance costs.
2. Provide a description of mechanisms in place to address unplanned closure.
3. Describe the bonding obligations in place to ensure that these liabilities can be funded on a qualitative and quantitative basis.
Risk analysis
1. Provide a description of the existence of a risk assessment process which has been undertaken to identify material ESG issues. Describe programmes in place to monitor identified material ESG issues.
2. Describe how the risk assessment process is integrated with the overall risk management framework.

3.3.3 Risk catalogues

The potential risks to be considered during an assessment in Appendix 2 attempt to be fairly comprehensive. This does not mean that all these risks may be relevant for a given combined extraction operation at the same time. The list mainly serves a means to create awareness of potential risks and as a checklist. A considerable number of the risks listed are not specific to extractive operations, but would be associated with the various life-cycle phases of any industrial operation, such as chemical processing plants for instance. Risk arising from well-completion have been added according to Lohne et al. (2018). The tables of risks in Appendix 2 are organised by life-cycle phase and environmental compartment or other type of receptor potentially affected. This way of organisation means, that certain types of risks, for instance air emissions, reappear in different categories. It would have been also possible to organise this list by type of risk and then list their possible causes. However, the chosen structure allows to attribute risks more clearly to root-causes in each life-cycle phase for which different control measures might be appropriate. After having gone through the steps, the prospective operator should have a comprehensive overview over the potential ESG issues the operation may face.

3.3.4 Sustainability reporting

As noted above, extractive operations are now generally expected to not only provide financial and corporate responsibility reports, but to also report on sustainability aspects. Various reporting standards have been developed over time and the one by the Sustainability Accounting Standards Board (<https://sasb.org/>) for 'Metals & Mining' is outlined in Table 6 (below) as guidance.

It should be noted that that the SASB standards presented in Table 6 are designed to be applicable world-wide and some elements may not be all relevant in a European context, while for instance OHS-related aspects are covered by the respective directives and regulations of the European Commission, e.g., Directives 89/391/EEC, 92/91/EEC, and 92/104/EEC, as well as Regulations (EC) Nos. 1272/2008 (CLP) and 1907/2006 (REACH) – see also Table 3 and references in Appendix 3.

Table 6: Topics covered by the ‘Metals & Mining’ sustainability accounting standard by SASB (<https://sasb.org/standards/download/>).

TOPIC	METRIC	CATEGORY	UNIT
Air Quality	Air emissions of the following pollutants: (1) CO, (2) NOx (excluding N2O), (3) SOx, (4) particulate matter (PM10), (5) mercury (Hg), (6) lead (Pb), and (7) volatile organic compounds (VOCs)	Quantitative	t
Waste & Hazardous Materials Management	Total weight of non-mineral waste generated	Quantitative	t
	Total weight of tailings produced	Quantitative	t
	Total weight of waste rock generated	Quantitative	t
	Total weight of hazardous waste generated	Quantitative	t
	Total weight of hazardous waste recycled	Quantitative	t
	Number of significant incidents associated with hazardous materials and waste management	Quantitative	Number
	Description of waste and hazardous materials management policies and procedures for active and inactive operations	Discussion and Analysis	n/a
Biodiversity Impacts	Description of environmental management policies and practices for active sites	Discussion and Analysis	n/a
	Percentage of mine sites where acid rock drainage is: (1) predicted to occur, (2) actively mitigated, and (3) under treatment or remediation	Quantitative	%
	Percentage of (1) proved and (2) probable reserves in or near sites with protected conservation status or endangered species habitat	Quantitative	%
Security, Human Rights & Rights of Indigenous Peoples	Percentage of (1) proved and (2) probable reserves in or near areas of conflict	Quantitative	%
	Percentage of (1) proved and (2) probable reserves in or near indigenous land	Quantitative	%
	Discussion of engagement processes and due diligence practices with respect to human rights, indigenous rights, and operation in areas of conflict	Discussion and Analysis	n/a
Community Relations	Discussion of process to manage risks and opportunities associated with community rights and interests	Discussion and Analysis	n/a
	(1) Number and (2) duration of non-technical delays	Quantitative	No., Days
Labour Practices	Percentage of active workforce employed covered under collective bargaining agreements	Quantitative	%
	(1) Number and (2) duration of strikes and lockouts	Quantitative	No., Days
Workforce Health & Safety	(1) OHS all-incidence rate, (2) fatality rate, (3) near miss frequency rate (NMFR) and (4) average hours of health, safety, and emergency response training for (a) direct full-time employees and (b) contract employees	Quantitative	Rate
Business Ethics & Transparency	Description of the management system for prevention of corruption and bribery throughout the value chain	Discussion and Analysis	n/a
Tailings Storage	Tailings storage facility inventory table: (1) facility name, (2) location, (3) ownership status, (4) operational status, (5)	Quantitative	Various

Facilities Management	construction method, (6) maximum permitted storage capacity, (7) current amounts of tailings stored, (8) consequence classification, (9) date of most recent independent technical review, (10) material findings, (11) mitigation measures, (12) site-specific EPRP		
	Summary of tailings management systems and governance structure used to monitor and maintain the stability of tailings storage facilities	Discussion and Analysis	n/a
	Approach to development of Emergency Preparedness and Response Plans (EPRPs) for tailings storage facilities	Discussion and Analysis	n/a

3.3.5 Relationship to Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA)

The environmental and sustainability aspects will be also informed by the EIA that is certainly required as part of the permitting procedures as outlined in Ch. 4. These, together with the site-specific risk catalogues will shape the narratives to address any SLO issues as part of addressing the societal and governance aspects. In some jurisdictions environmental and social impact assessments may be collected together in an ESIA. A publicly available comprehensive example for an ESIA for a combined extraction project can be found here: ERM (2024).

The weight to be given to each issue will depend on the outcomes of the stakeholder interaction processes (cf. Deliverable D4.2; Mitchell et al. 2025). However, the key messages to stakeholder are likely that the overall environmental impacts and nuisances during the operational phase are likely to be small in comparison to conventional mining operations.

Mousavinezhad et al. (2024) pick up on an aspect that is rarely discussed in the present context, namely the footprint of the operation per tonne of Li produced. The information on land-use varies across the literature. For a typical hard rock plant (such as Greenbushes and Mt. Catlin mines and Tianqi lithium plant in Western Australia), approximately 335 m² per tonne of Li₂CO₃ are used, including open-pit mining areas, tailing dams, and lithium refineries. In brine evaporation pond systems, land is needed for evaporation ponds, wellfields, processing plants, and disposal areas. Direct land use for a brine evaporation pond resource is estimated to be approximately 3656 m² per tonne of Li₂CO₃ (based on Atacama). Conversely, direct land use in a typical DLE setup is lower, averaging around 16 m² per tonne of Li₂CO₃ for processing plants, and, if the wellfield area is also taken into account, approximately 493 m² per tonne of Li₂CO₃. Additionally, if the source of electricity shifts to solar panels, the land required for solar panel installation must be added to the total land use of DLE.

From an overall sustainability and hence environmental point of view the key message is likely that the CO₂-footprint, the amount of embedded carbon, and the physical footprint (including extractive waste management facilities) will be small in comparison to other extraction techniques.

4 ASSESSMENT OF REGULATORY REQUIREMENTS AND CONSTRAINTS

4.1 METHOD AND CAVEATS

The combined extraction of minerals and heat is likely subject to a complex regulatory regime in the various EU Member States and adjacent countries.

In a first step for each country information about the regulatory regime applied in practice has been collated in order to understand the current situation.

The necessary regulatory mining licences and provisions (e.g. for extractive waste management) have been reviewed on the basis of *inter alia* the MinLex (2017) data for a range of European countries. However, the MinLex project was completed nearly ten years ago and regulations in the relevant European countries since have evolved.

Another valuable source of information on the various regulatory regimes is the legal database (FAOLEX) maintained by the UN Food and Agricultural Organisation (FAO), which provides country profiles and also covers legislation on a variety of natural resources (<https://www.fao.org/faolex/country-profiles/en/>). In many cases English translations of the respective acts are available. While FAOLEX may not be completely up-to-date it provides a valuable starting point for targeted searches on the Internet.

These reviews were undertaken in the course of the project, cognisant of the fact that regulatory systems constantly evolve. Where a revision was known to be imminent, the country profiles (Section 0, Appendix 1) were revisited in Spring 2025.

The dimension of extracting minerals then has been added to the dimension of heat extraction in order to understand in what way and by what regulations such extraction may be covered in a given country. These analyses allow to prepare future sites for the regulatory challenges, but also to points out certain regulatory pitfalls and shortcomings.

4.2 GEOTHERMAL ENERGY SYSTEM REGULATORY FRAMEWORK

A comprehensive review of the regulatory system for geothermal energy projects was undertaken for France, Germany and the Netherlands by Goodman et al. (2009). On this basis, they made recommendation for regulatory systems that covered:

- Legal Guidelines
 - Definition and classification of geothermal energy
 - Geothermal resource ownership
 - Geothermal energy licensing system
 - Simplify regulations and administrative procedures
 - Geothermal energy licensing authority
 - Geothermal resources inventory and statistics
- Financial Incentives Guidelines
 - Regulatory costs/License fees/Royalties
 - Developing financial incentives schemes
 - Notes on financial incentives parameters

- General Guidelines for Flanking/Supporting Measures
 - Education, Training, and Certification
 - Promotion of geothermal energy
 - Standards and Codes
 - Research and Development

The regulatory systems of Belgium, France, Hungary, Iceland, Italy, and Turkey for geothermal projects were described in detail in the course of the H2020 Project GEOENVIE (Valkering, P. et al. 2020). This assessment focuses on energy harvesting and considers wastes generated, such as scales, not as extractive waste, but as industrial wastes covered by the respective regulations. However, once the objective is metal extraction, it is likely that the Extractive Waste Directive (CEU 2006a) will apply.

The number of reports and papers that are concerned with making recommendations for the improvement of the regulatory systems across Europe seems to indicate that there are still shortcomings. The need to streamline and simplify licensing procedures across Europe thus was recognised and respective proposals were made by e.g. Batini (2021).

A position paper by the European Geothermal Energy Council (EGEC 2022) indicates, that at EU level many of the above points have begun to be addressed, but that the current situation has not changed significantly yet. The complexity of licensing procedures was noted: *“Geothermal energy is regulated by many entities and regulations, dealing with mining in the underground and the surface as an industrial application, but also for the environmental, water and energy regulations. As illustrated in the delegated acts on EU taxonomy, geothermal resource is combined with several engines: turbine for Combined heat and power plants, District heating and Cooling systems, Heat pumps, Underground Thermal Energy Storage. Each engine has additional regulations and technical standards.”* Combined extraction will add an additional layer to this and there is uncertainty as to which regulatory body will take the lead in a given country and for a given project.

EGEC (2022) also noted a lack of capacities and capabilities on the side of regulators. This is not unique to geothermal projects or combined extraction, but the decline in mining across most Member States has also led to a severe reduction in mining regulators' staffing or their amalgamation with e.g. environmental regulators. As a result, many regulators do not have staff with knowledge in deep drilling technology, well completion, geothermal systems or mining in general, making them de facto incapable to assess and regulate adequately such projects. Large scale deployment of geothermal and combined extraction projects will require the rebuilding of adequate regulatory capacity. Poorly regulated projects can undermine public confidence in such projects. Where they still exist, regulators experienced in hydrocarbon drilling projects could be redeployed here. It appears that shallow geothermal systems, with which this project is not concerned, have found more attention, including the regulatory aspects with respect to water resources management. Rupprecht et al. (2017) for instance compare the regulatory systems for various central European countries.

It should be noted that the observations made by various geothermal energy stakeholders, such as the EGEC, concern both, shallow and deep geothermal systems. However, combined extraction would rather target deep geothermal systems than systems that may only reach down to a few tens of meters. The approaches for associated

EIAs and assessing potential competitions, as well as the regulatory bodies involved are different. In shallow projects the mining regulators would not normally be involved in. In the following, a number of the above points for which recommendations were formulated by Goodman et al. (CEU 2009) are taken up and their implications for combined extraction are discussed.

Definition and classification of geothermal energy

According to Directive 2009/28/EC (CEU 2009) “*geothermal energy* means energy stored in form of heat beneath the surface of solid earth”. Article 5 of this Directive stipulates “... that the final energy output significantly exceeds the primary energy input required to drive the heat pumps.”, which is a reference to a positive energy balance of the system concerned. Annex VII further specifies the mode of calculating the energy balance.

In combined extraction systems this can become an important economic and regulatory question, as the extraction system may shift the energy balance or make systems at the lower end of efficiency more attractive due to the added value of metal extraction.

Geothermal resource ownership

At the time of the review by Goodman et al. (2009) there has been no uniform practice across the EU for treating the ownership of deep geothermal resources from a regulatory perspective, which was confirmed again by EGEC (2022). Applicable legislation could come from the realms of water resources, mining, or hydrocarbon extraction. Depending on the specific system set-up, the major difference can be, that actually very little mass is extracted permanently, if the cooled-down water is being re-injected (rather than released to surface water courses). Only the heat-content is extracted.

The way how ownership of subsurface resources is treated varies from Member State to Member State. In general, shallow resources, down to a few metres below ground, are the property of the landowner, while deeper resources are owned by the state. The state may give permission to exploit such resources to private enterprises. For this, fees and royalties are payable to the state (see below).

It appears that currently in many cases ‘heat’ is not treated as a resource, but only as a source of potential environmental impact. The underlying reasoning presumably is that it is considered to be inexhaustible due to the radioactive decay in the earth’s interior.

Resource ownership is also related to the possibility to delimit the extension of the resource below ground. In the case of geothermal and combined extraction projects, this is complicated by the fact that we are dealing with flows of heat or matter, rather than with a static mineral resource. Without an appropriate 3D hydraulic flow-model or reservoir model, it is difficult to assess from which volume a geothermal borehole extracts heat and matter. Useful guidance on this can be found in the way how hydrocarbon exploration concessions are delimited.

Geothermal energy licensing system

Given the regulatory uncertainties discussed in the previous section, it is clear that this also affects the licensing and permitting of geothermal or combined extraction projects. Major issues to be considered are potential resources use conflicts between deep geothermal systems and deep mining, water resources use that may affect regional flow patterns, carbon capture and storage systems, and hydrocarbon extraction, although the

latter due to the limited onshore oil & gas exploitation in Europe and the progressive decarbonisation of our societies will become less of an issue.

It is important that licensing is based on a comprehensive system analysis that tries to understand how a project may impact the subsurface space and how other subsurface activities might influence in their turn the geothermal project.

While it is not very likely, that deep geothermal reservoirs would be used for drinking-water supply, use of shallower aquifers above may change flow-pattern and recharge rates, thus affecting the geothermal system. Water resources management considerations would also be relevant in case the produce waters were to be discharged into surface water courses, rather be reinjected. The Water Framework Directive 2000/60/EC (CEU 2000) provides guidance in this respect. Some MSs have also established orders of precedence, such that water resources take precedence over mineral resources. A systemic and modelling approach to licensing will help to understand the possible interference between geothermal energy systems and carbon capture and storage that may target similar deep formations. The risk is that injected CO₂ migrates towards geothermal projects and is brought to the surface again with the produced waters.

Regulatory costs/License fees/Royalties

According to the discussion in Goodman et al. (2009), no clear and uniform approach across EU Member States is in place for determining any licensing fees or royalties.

The underlying assumption presumably is that 'heat' is not (yet) defined as a resource. The tacit assumption is also that 'heat' is a renewable resource that is replenished from deeper geological strata and, compared to the theoretical total heat contained in the earth and regenerated through radioactive decay, the amount extracted by humans will be negligible on a global scale. However, on a local or regional scale there may be depletion, depending on the heat conducting processes.

If, as in most relevant cases of deep geothermal systems, the produced waters would be re-injected in nearby boreholes, there will be little net water extraction that may fall under the respective water resources regulations and attract permitting fees.

However, the situation may be different for combined extraction, where metal value is removed permanently from the subsurface space for commercial purposes. In this case, one would expect, that license fees and royalties similar to those for conventional mining could be applied. One could argue for a significant discount compared to conventional mining, as some of these fees and royalties normally would be used for environmental remediation or compensation measures, which in the case of combined extraction are significantly lower or not even necessary. In addition, combined extraction occurs in conjunction with the strategic objective of supplying low-carbon footprint energy.

Likewise, the usual instruments to finance environmental remediation of mine sites, such as bonds, probably could be largely waived. The remedial effort would mainly concern the decommissioning of the surface installations. No significant amount of soil remediation would be expected. It should be noted, that none the regulatory documents reviewed for CRM-geothermal discusses these points explicitly. The amount of post-mining remediation needed would normally be determined on the basis of the Environmental Impact Assessment. In the case of combined extraction comparatively little impact is to the be expected (see Section 3.2).

Standards and Codes

Geothermal energy projects have to adhere to the relevant EU and national standards (Goodman et al., 2009), including those on:

- Drilling safety procedures, cf. Directive 92/91/EEC (CEU 1992)
- Drilling equipment efficiency
- Borehole completion standards
- Environmental and groundwater protection
- Quality of borehole heat exchanger completion
- Manifolds and installation of surface equipment
- Sizing and design guidelines to ensure the sustainable and efficient operation
- Standards for individual system components

4.3 RELEVANT EUROPEAN REGULATIONS

4.3.1 Environmental and extractive industries related regulations

A frequent motivation to develop regulatory instruments in the EU is to address environmental, individual human or societal risk and impacts. Thus, achieving compliance with these EU regulations and their national subsidiaries (see below) are a major driver for environmental, safety & health, and societal impact assessment for planned projects. These regulatory instruments may be complemented by policy instruments that typically have a more proactive function by steering economic and societal activities into directions perceived as being for instance more sustainable, such as the EU 'Green Deal' (European Commission 2019) or the EU Raw Materials Act (CRMA, 2024).

The EU Directives and other regulations have to be transposed into or homologated with national legislation, which then become the enforceable legal instruments at EU Member State level. Compliance with EU regulations cannot be directly enforced by the EU at levels below the national level. This is the obligation of the MSs through their respective regulatory systems.

Typically, EU regulatory instruments only give the broad outline of the issues to be considered and actions to be taken. They set objectives, rather than describe the implementation, which usually is covered by national laws, by-laws, regulations, and codes. There is, however, EU guidance on specific fields through the collection of BREFs (Best Available Techniques Reference Documents (for an overview of available documents see <https://eippcb.jrc.ec.europa.eu/reference>).

EU Directives relevant to the combined extraction come from a wide variety of policy-making and regulatory realms, such as the environment s.s., water and air emissions, waste management, resources and energy conservation, nature conservation, work-place safety & health, etc. Some years ago, the European Commission initiated a study to summarise policy and legal instruments relevant to mining on both, EU and national level (MinLex, 2017). This study produced a large collection of country fact-sheets on (which are available from the EU Joint Research Centre's Raw Materials Information System (RMIS, <https://rmis.jrc.ec.europa.eu/topic/legislation>):

1. **Internal market legislation:** eight items, including the principal Directives relevant to the topic of the MinLex project: Professional Qualifications Directive, Services Directive, Concessions Directive, Public Procurement Directive, Utilities Procurement Directive, Market Surveillance Directive, Accounting Directive, and Transparency Directive.
2. **Environmental legislation:** 19 items, covering the principal environmental and industrial risk items (EIA, SEA, Environmental Liability, REACH, etc.).
3. **Waste legislation:** 13 items where the Extractive Waste Directive and related Commission Decisions are discussed, among other waste-related items (Waste Framework Directive, Landfill Directive).
4. **Water legislation:** six items, including surface water and groundwater topics.
5. **Nature conservation legislation:** the two major pieces, the Habitats and the Birds Directive.
6. **Noise and atmospheric pollution:** eight items.
7. **Health and safety:** 24 items covering different aspects of occupational health and safety.
8. **Statistics, nomenclature and information management:** seven different items.
9. **Other relevant legislation:** 11 items that are resource-related pieces and cover energy minerals or topics such as underground CO₂ storage. Court case analysis indicated that some cases from the energy minerals sector may be important and relevant to the project if the reason for appeal concerns some general internal market principle.

All these will also be relevant for the permitting stage and the operational supervision of combined extraction projects. Since the Min-Lex-study was completed in 2017, a number of additional EU regulatory instruments, such as the Energy Efficiency Directive 2023/1791 (CEU 2023), have been put into place and various national regulations have been revised.

There is no comparable compendium specifically on national environmental regulatory instruments. In order to better understand the relevance and potential and actual impacts of certain EU Directives and regulations, it is helpful to order these according to the life-cycle of extractive activities, namely exploration, extraction, beneficiation/processing, intermediates, final products, wastes (including those from de-scaling operations and other process wastes), recycling, and long-term management of former combined extraction sites and their potential extractive waste management facilities.

Certain host-rocks of combined extraction systems may contain heavy metals, (toxic) metalloids, and/or NORM (see Eggeling et al., 2013), which may appear in dissolved form in hydrothermal fluids. These elements will likely partition into by-products and/or residues/wastes during processing and then need to be managed adequately (see inter alia the Extractive Waste Directive 2006/21/EC). Relevant OSH aspects, including handling of contaminated equipment are discussed below summarily (see e.g. 2013/59/Euratom).

Table 2 below provides a non-exhaustive list of Environmental EU legislative acts (Directives / Regulations / Decisions) relevant to the extractive sector and potentially applicable to combined extraction systems. The operational health and safety aspects are discussed in Section 4.3.2. Links to the respective regulatory acts are given in Appendix 3.

Table 2: Extractive operation life-cycle relevance of EU Directives and Regulations.

Directive / Regulation	No.
Environment	
Strategic Environmental Impact Assessment (SEIA)	2001/42/EC
Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA)	2014/52/EU
Environmental Liability Directive	2004/35/EC
Hazardous Chemicals (CLP Regulation)	1272/2008
Water Framework	2000/60/EC
Groundwater	2006/118/EC
Seveso Directive III	2012/18/EU
IED	2024/1785
Habitat	92/43/EEC
Birds	2009/147/EC
Waste	
Waste Framework (WFD)	2008/98/EC
Extractive Waste (EWD)	2006/21/EC
Hazardous Waste Regulations	1357/2014, 2017/997
List of Waste (LoW) Decision	2014/955/EC
Landfill	1999/31/EC
Human Health	
Restrictions of Hazardous Substances (RoHS)	2011/65/EU
Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH)	1907/2006
Sustainability	
Renewable energy	2009/28/EC
Renewable energies (RES)	2018/2001
Energy efficiency	2023/1791
Eco-design	2009/125/EC
Eco-management audit Regulation	1221/2009
Societal	
Public participation	2003/35/EC

The European Emissions Trading System (EU ETS, https://climate.ec.europa.eu/eu-action/eu-emissions-trading-system-eu-ets_en) is a market-based mechanism that aims to reduce greenhouse gas emissions from industry and power generation. Geothermal energy is considered a low-carbon energy source and is eligible for emission credits under this system. The economic and business case aspects associated with the ETS, however, are discussed in Deliverable D4.3 of this project (Correia et al., forthcoming).

4.3.2 Regulations on Occupational Safety and Health (OSH)

Occupational Safety and Health (OSH) is not only relevant for the workers setting up and operating combined extraction facilities, but also for the surrounding communities and thus the social license to operate (see Deliverable D4.2; Mitchell et al., 2025). The reason is that the workers typically are members of the local communities and the image of the operating company is strongly shaped by its attitude towards OSH and the well-being of its employees.

The EU has developed a comprehensive set of general OSH regulations, but also specific ones for the extractive industries (see Table 3 below). The OSH Framework Directive (CEU, 1989) guarantees minimum safety and health requirements throughout Europe, while MSs may establish stricter requirements. It contains principles relating to the assessment, elimination and prevention of risks and accident factors, the protection of safety and health, the informing, consultation and balanced participation, and training of workers and their representatives.

Table 3: OSH relevant EU Directives

Subject area	Directive No.
Overarching instruments	
Introduction of measures to encourage improvements in the safety and health of workers at work – OSH Framework Directive	89/391/EEC
Minimum safety and health requirements for the workplace	89/654/EEC
Minimum requirements for improving the safety and health protection of workers in <i>surface and underground mineral-extracting industries</i>	92/104/EEC
Minimum requirements for improving the safety and health protection of workers in the mineral-extracting industries through <i>drilling</i>	92/91/EEC
Workplaces, equipment, signs, personal protective equipment	
Minimum safety and health requirements for the use of <i>work equipment</i> by workers at work	2009/104/EC
Minimum health and safety requirements for the use by workers of <i>personal protective equipment</i> at the workplace	89/656/EEC
Minimum requirements for the provision of safety and/or health <i>signs</i> at work	92/58/EEC
Minimum requirements for improving the health and safety protection of workers potentially at risk from <i>explosive atmospheres</i>	1999/92/EC
Workload, ergonomics, and psychosocial risks	
Minimum health and safety requirements for the <i>manual handling of loads</i> where there is a risk particularly of back injury to workers	90/269/EEC
Minimum safety and health requirements at <i>temporary or mobile construction sites</i>	92/57/EEC
Working time concerning certain aspects of the organisation of working time	2003/88/EC
On temporary workers	91/383/EEC
Chemical agents	
Chemical agents and its individual Directives 2000/39, 2006/15, 2009/161, and 2017/164 on lists of indicative occupational exposure limit values	98/24/EC
On the protection of workers from the risks related to exposure to carcinogens, mutagens or reprotoxic substances at work	2004/37/EC
Classification, labelling and packaging of substances and mixtures (CLP) of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2008 on classification, labelling and packaging of substances and mixtures, amending and repealing Directives 67/548/EEC and 1999/45/EC, and amending Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006	Regulation (EC) 1272/2008
Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH) of 18 December 2006 concerning the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH) and establishing a European Chemicals Agency	Regulation (EC) 1907/2006
Biological agents	
On the protection of workers from risks related to exposure to <i>biological agents</i> at work	2000/54/EC
Physical agents	
Minimum health and safety requirements regarding the exposure of workers to the risks arising from physical agents (<i>vibration</i>)	2002/44/EC
Minimum health and safety requirements regarding the exposure of workers to the risks arising from physical agents (<i>noise</i>)	2003/10/EC
Minimum health and safety requirements regarding the exposure of workers to the risks arising from physical agents (<i>electromagnetic fields</i>)	2004/40/EC
Minimum health and safety requirements regarding the exposure of workers to risks arising from physical agents (<i>artificial optical radiation</i>)	2006/25/EC
Radiation protection	2013/59/Euratom

On the basis of this Framework Directive, some 30 specific Directives were adopted (Table 3; <https://osha.europa.eu/en/safety-and-health-legislation/european-directives>), which are grouped according to the following categories: workplaces, equipment, signs, personal protective equipment; exposure to chemical agents and chemical safety; exposure to physical hazards; exposure to biological agents; provisions on workload, ergonomic and psychosocial risks; sector specific and worker related provisions.

Five of these directives have special importance for the extractive industries, namely 92/91/EEC (CEU, 1992a) setting minimum requirements for improving the safety and health of workers engaged in drilling operations in the extractive industries; 92/104/EEC

(CEU, 1992b) establishing minimum OSH requirements in surface and underground mineral-extracting industries; 2003/10/EC on the risks arising from physical agents such as noise (CEU, 2003) and 2002/44/EC on vibration (CEU, 2002) as well as 2004/37/EC on the exposure to carcinogens or mutagens at work (CEU, 2004), which include mineral dusts from e.g. silica and coal, or fibres of certain asbestos minerals.

The main risks that may arise during the various phases of an extractive project or its ancillary operations, will need to be defined and assessed in the Technical Operation Plan (TOP). Definition of health and safety rules are a substantial part of the permitting process. Risk assessment included in the TOPs will need to consider all possible health and safety factors, especially concerning the work equipment used, hazardous substances and mixtures, occupational exposure of workers to different substances, noise, vibration or ionising radiation, as well as the ergonomic set-up of the workplaces. A number of studies in recent years have summarised (e.g. Falck et al., 2017) and also critically evaluated the regulations (e.g. Min-Lex, 2017), where one can find more detailed information on these instruments.

4.4 SELECTED EUROPEAN STATES' LEGISLATION AND POLICIES

The Icelandic law firm BBA/FJELDICO (<https://www.bbafjeldco.is>) maintains an *Geothermal Transparency Guide* as an online database (<http://www.geothermal.bba.is>), which is intended to provide an insight into the legal frameworks governing exploration, exploitation and production of electricity from geothermal resources. It covers a variety of countries including some EU MSs (Table 4 below).

As noted above, the European Commission initiated a study to summarise policy and legal instruments on both, EU and national level (MinLex, MinPol, 2017). The fact-sheets produced by this study provided a good starting point for the following assessment, although they are now nearly ten years old.

The EU Raw Materials Information System (RMIS) maintained by the Joint Research Centre of the European Commission also provides legislative country profiles for the EU Member States: <https://rmis.jrc.ec.europa.eu/member-states-legislation-08b84e>. The data are based on the MinLex (2017) study, but also include the results from the MinGuide project. It is not known, whether the information in RMIS is updated periodically.

As noted earlier, particularly useful was the regulatory and policies database of the Food and Agriculture Organisation of United Nations (<https://www.fao.org/faolex/en/>). It covers all FAO Member States and provides links to either the original legislative/ policy documents or translations (both official and unofficial).

It may be also noted here that ChatGPT (<https://chatgpt.com>), which became fully operational during the course of this project, proved to be a very useful tool to get a first understanding of the regulatory framework of a specific country and to re-review work undertaken earlier. On the basis of these results, a targeted research for the original legislative documents could be undertaken to provide a solid reference framework.

The regulatory country review focused on the legislation that would be applicable in particular to the extraction of mineral value from deep geothermal waters and not on geothermal energy systems, particularly shallow ones, in general. The respective country profiles are given in Appendix 1.

Table 4: Overview over regulatory coverage in various European countries (from EGEC 2005?)

	Legislative framework							
	Geothermal energy explicitly treated in					Specific legislation on geo-thermal energy	Ownership of in situ geothermal energy	
	mining	water	environmental	energy or electricity	other legislation		state	land-owner
Albania	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes	No
Belgium	No	No	No	No	No	No		
Czech Republic	no	yes	no	yes	no	no	-	-
France	yes	no	no	no	no	yes	yes	no
Germany	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	yes	no
Germany II	yes	no	no	no	yes	no	yes	sometimes
Hungary	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	no	yes	no
Latvia	no	yes	no	yes	no	no	yes	no
Lithuania	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	no	yes	no
Poland								
Romania	yes	yes	no	yes	no	no	yes	no
Serbia and Montenegro	yes	no	no	no	no	no	yes	no
Slovakia	no	yes	no	no	no	no	yes	no
Slovenia	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	no	yes	no
Switzerland	no	yes	no	no	no	no	yes	no

4.5 REGULATORY CHALLENGES TO PERMITTING OF COMBINED EXTRACTION PROJECTS

There appear to be three different legal approaches to resource ownership across Europe: a) all resources in the ground belong to the land-owner, b) all resources in the ground belong to the state, c) deep resources belong to the state, while shallow (i.e. down to a few metres of depth) belong to the land-owner. In some European countries there may be also hybrid situations, where resources in the ground in principle belong to the land-owner with the exception of hydrocarbons or precious metals for instance. Given such situations, granting access to the resource and granting access to the land above the resource for the purpose of extraction may involve more than one entity.

Actual permitting processes for specific projects will be governed by the applicable national legislation. As can be seen In Appendix 1, in the majority of European countries, including those the EU MSs, (deep) geothermal projects are controlled by the national mining codes, which in most cases include drilling operations.

In practice, the domain of interest of a range of different regulators may be concerned, including the water (resources) authorities, mining and environmental regulators, regional/spatial planners, etc. *A priori* it may not be clear which one of these might be the leading regulator when it comes to assess the potential environmental impacts. ESGS (2021) recommended the setting up of 'one-stop shops' in the MSs to simplify the permitting procedures. However, regulator would need to be competent for both, shallow systems and deep systems with all the implications the latter have. For combined extraction, it would be desirable to have a regulator capable of a systemic assessment, encompassing the resource (conservation), environmental, technological, OHS, economic, and not the least the societal dimension of such projects. Other MSs *de facto* apply the

'one-stop-shop' principle by designating one of the regulatory authorities as the lead regulator that collates the processes.

A further challenge arises from the fact that in many EU MSs, due to the lack of mining in recent decades, mining authorities have been either closed for good or have been amalgamated with e.g. environmental authorities. The focus on the environmental aspects of mining has resulted in various cases in an erosion of the technical competence to adequately evaluate and regulate extractive projects, including deep drilling projects. The latter requires an understanding of drilling and casing technologies, as well as reservoir hydraulics, but positions may not have been filled with adequately trained staff. Given the fact that combined extraction projects might be close to urban centres, particularly, when they deliver heat, rather than electricity, a range of competing use interests for the subsurface space may exist. In general, the footprint of geothermal and combined extraction systems is small compared to conventional mining operation. Hence, surface use conflicts are less likely to arise.

In summary, it is probably safe to state that in any one given European country the regulatory treatment would depend on what the primary objective of the project is: extraction of heat or extraction of metal value. If the main objective is extraction of heat, in the first instance the regulations pertaining to geothermal energy systems would apply. If the main objective is extraction of metal value, the respective mining legislation would apply and the system may be treated as a solution mining project. While in practical terms this will not change dramatically the investigations necessary for an adequate environmental impact assessment, the main difference would be how resulting residues and wastes are treated from a regulatory point of view. If the project *de jure* is a mining project, the Extractive Waste Directive (CEU 2006a) would apply, otherwise wastes would be treated as industrial wastes under the Waste Framework Directive (CEU 2008b).

5 PROPOSAL FOR A UNFC/CRIRSCO COMPLIANT ASSESSMENT

5.1 OVERVIEW

A variety of stakeholders have an interest in accurate data on the occurrence and availability of mineral resources. Governments need such information for strategic decision- and policy-making. Investors, who fund extraction projects need to base their decisions on reliable data to determine the likely viability of projects. However, the data on the physical presence of mineral resources are not the only important facts, but also information on their extractability and any of the many peripheral circumstances that may pose an obstacle to their extraction. The dimension of time also plays a role in the decision making. In the early phases of a potential project the level of knowledge of the mineral occurrence is low and exploration activities aim to decrease the level of uncertainty for the data users and, hence, increasing the level of knowledge and confidence. It is essential that the industry communicates the risks associated with the potential investment effectively and transparently in order to earn the level of trust necessary to underpin its ongoing activities.

It is clear, that the information needs of governments and industry/investors are somewhat different. On the other hand, as mineral resources extraction and use are a global business, an alignment of the way how resources are assessed and reported is mutually desirable, both from a business as well as a strategic planning perspective.

5.2 INDUSTRY RESOURCE REPORTING – CRIRSCO ALIGNED CODES

The Committee for Mineral Reserves International Reporting Standards (CRIRSCO, <https://crirSCO.com/>), which was formed in 1994 under the auspices of the then Council of Mining and Metallurgical Institutes (CMMI), is a grouping of representatives from organisations that are responsible for developing mineral reporting codes and guidelines in Australasia (JORC), Brazil (CBRR), Canada (CIM), Chile (National Committee), Colombia (CCRR), Europe (PERC), India (NACRI), Indonesia (KOMBERS KCMI), Kazakhstan (KAZRC), Mongolia (MPIGM), Philippines (PMRCC), Russia (NAEN), South Africa (SAMREC), Turkey (UMREK) and the USA (SME). The combined value of mining companies listed on the stock exchanges of these countries is reported by CRIRSCO to account for more than 80% of the listed capital of the mining industry (www.crirSCO.com).

Figure 27: Mineral resources and reserves according to CRIRSCO definitions
(CRIRSCO, 2024a)

The international initiative to standardise market-related reporting definitions for mineral resources and mineral reserves (Figure 27) had its start at the 15th CMMI Congress at Sun City, South Africa in 1994. The mineral definitions working group (later called CRIRSCO) was formed after a meeting at that Congress with the primary objective of developing a set of international standard definitions for the reporting of mineral resources and mineral reserves. Figure 27 illustrates the classification of mineral resources and mineral reserves according to the increasing level of confidence in the available data and estimates as exploration and technical and economic evaluation studies progress.

The similarity of the various national reporting codes and guidelines has enabled CRIRSCO to develop an International Minerals Reporting Template ('the CRIRSCO Template') for the public disclosure of information on mineral deposit assessments - initially published in 2006 and updated several times since then - the most recent update of which was issued in 2024 (CRIRSCO, 2024a). The CRIRSCO Template can act as a "core code and guidelines" for any country wishing to adopt its own CRIRSCO-style reporting standard, after including provisions for country-specific requirements such as those of a legal and investment regulatory nature.

A key element of the CRIRSCO Template is the inclusion of standard definitions for key terminology used when reporting on estimates of the size and magnitude of mineral resources and mineral reserves. These definitions were originally agreed in 1997 and have been reviewed and updated periodically since then. The CRIRSCO standard definitions are

incorporated into the CRIRSCO Template (see: CRIRSCO 2024a,b), and are used by all of the CRIRSCO member organisations.

Accordingly, the *Pan European Reserves and Resources Reporting Committee* (PERC, <https://percstandard.org/>), the CRIRSCO member organisation that represents the European region, developed a Standard for Reporting of Exploration Results, Mineral Resources and Mineral Reserves, which sets out the minimum standards, additional guidelines and recommendations for the Public Reporting of Exploration Results (including Exploration Targets), Mineral Resources and Mineral Reserves (PERC, 2021).

A key aspect that determines, whether a mineral occurrence can become a viable extraction project relates to the so-called 'Modifying Factors' (cf. CRIRSCO, 2024b) that include, but are not limited to, mining, processing, metallurgical, infrastructure, economic, marketing, legal, environmental, societal and governance (ESG), and regulatory factors. In other words, they are also concerned with internalisation of the ESG aspect (see Ch. 3).

It should be noted that companies that report in compliance with a CRIRSCO Template aligned code or standard all generate additional internal estimates of sub-economic mineralisation. Unlike in a UNFC classification, the CRIRSCO Template does not allow for the public reporting of such estimates to investors (i.e. market disclosure) due to the high degree of uncertainty about their economic viability and potential value.

It also needs to be noted, that resource reporting under CRIRSCO-aligned codes and standards is limited to mineral projects, and does not cover non-mineral energy resources.

5.3 UNITED NATIONS FRAMEWORK CLASSIFICATION FOR RESOURCES (UNFC)

The United Nations Framework Classification for Resources (UNECE, 2019) provides countries, companies, financial institutions and other stakeholders a tool for sustainable development of energy and mineral resource endowments. UNFC applies to a wide variety of energy resources including oil and gas, renewable energy, nuclear energy, minerals, injection projects for the geological storage of CO₂, groundwater, and anthropogenic resources, such as secondary resources recycled from residues and wastes.

The emerging challenges in these sectors are the needs for sustainable, environment-friendly, carbon neutral and efficient development and production of energy and raw materials required for a growing population. Innovations in production, consumption and transportation are fundamentally challenging how energy and material sectors function today. As a unique tool for harmonising policy frameworks, government oversight, industry business process and efficient capital allocation, UNFC is designed for managing the natural resources required for the present and future needs of society and realising the objectives of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs, <https://sdgs.un.org/goals>).

UNFC, in its core principles, encompasses the comprehensive management of all socio-economic, technological and uncertainty aspects of energy and mineral projects. The project maturity and resource progression model of UNFC can de-risk projects from costly failures and thus protect the investments. UNFC fully integrates societal and environmental considerations and technology readiness required.

UNFC aims to provide clear and consistent specifications, guidelines and best practices for all energy and mineral sectors, which are of particular importance for the management of expanding demand of minerals for the ‘electrification’ of our societies. Application of the UNFC in these sectors is supported by the publication of sector-specific supplementary specifications, such as those for minerals (UNECE, 2021) and geothermal energy (UNECE, 2022a)

To help the application of UNFC uniformly worldwide, guidelines on requirements for competency of the personnel have been provided in supplementary guidance documents (cf. UNECE, 2022b). UNFC provides case studies and implementation examples, not only to improve the consistency in the usage but also to enhance the system through innovative applications.

Sustainable management of energy and raw material resources in a rapidly changing global economic landscape requires accurate mapping of supply and demand. The recoverable resources available on our planet need coherent and consistent definition and categorisation at global, regional, national and local levels. For this reason, the European Commission has been advocating the use of UNFC in all mineral raw materials related projects.

UNFC is a principles-based system through which a resource project is classified on the basis of the three fundamental criteria (UNECE, 2019) of

- environmental-socio-economic viability (E),
- technical feasibility (F), and
- degree of confidence in the estimate (G),

using a numerical coding system. Combinations of these criteria create a three-dimensional system (Figure 28). Categories (e.g. E1, E2, E3) and, in some cases, Sub-categories (e.g. E1.1) are defined for each of the three criteria.

Figure 28: UNFC Categories and Example of Classes

The first set of Categories (the **E Axis**) designates the degree of favourability of environmental-socio-economic and governance (ESG) conditions in establishing the viability of the project, including consideration of market prices and relevant legal, regulatory, societal, environmental, and contractual conditions.

The second set (the **F Axis**) is a measure of the maturity of technology, studies, and commitments necessary to implement the project. These projects range from early conceptual studies through to a fully developed project that is producing and reflects standard value-chain management principles.

The third set of categories (the **G Axis**) designates the degree of confidence in the estimate of the quantities of products can be obtained from the project. The degree of confidence will increase, as the project progresses.

The Categories and Sub-categories are the building blocks of the system and are combined in the form of “Classes”. UNFC can be visualised in three dimensions, as shown in Figure 28, or represented in practical two-dimensional abbreviated versions.

For more details, the reader should consult the *Supplementary Specifications for the Application of the United Nations Framework Classification for Resources to Minerals* (UNECE, 2021).

The same type of classification can be applied to energy resources, including geothermal energy resources, for which *Supplementary Specifications for the application of the United Nations Framework Classification for Resources (Update 2019) to Geothermal Energy Resources* (UNECE, 2022) have been developed.

Also of interest are the *Guidelines for the extraction of uranium* (UNECE, 2017), in particular the section on extraction by *in situ*-leaching (ISL). ISL is confronted with a similar challenge as combined extraction of energy and metals concerning the determination of the recovery factor.

5.4 APPLICATION OF UNFC TO COMBINED EXTRACTION PROJECTS

The European Commission has been advocating the use of UNFC in resource-related projects *inter alia* to make classifications compatible with the Raw Materials Information System (RMIS, <https://rmis.jrc.ec.europa.eu>) developed by the Commission’s Joint Research Centre (JRS). The use of the UNFC in this context is favoured due to the need to aggregate data from multiple different systems as used by the different Member States in collating national mineral inventory data. More recently, the European Commission has also required the use of the UNFC in the Critical Raw Materials Act (CRMA, 2024) as a useful tool for comparing and monitoring critical minerals projects across a wide range of sectors (e.g. extraction, processing, recycling and substitution). This caused concern in the minerals industry, where publicly listed companies are normally obliged to use CRIRSCO-aligned reporting standards to comply with stock market legislation and regulation. Mineral companies feared a doubled burden of having to report to governments also using UNFC. Under these circumstances, a certain competition between the systems was perceived. However, an updated version of the CRIRSCO Template to UNFC ‘bridging’ document in 2024, together with an accompanying guidance note on its usage (CRIRSCO and UNECE, 2024), highlighted the complementary nature of the two systems, which have been developed to meet different purposes. The bridging document has since been updated (UNECE, 2025), in order to align with the most recent versions of the CRIRSCO standard definitions (CRIRSCO, 2024b). In practice, estimates for a large proportion of

exploration, development and operating mineral projects in Europe are assessed and disclosed in compliance with one of the CRIRSCO-aligned reporting codes, but estimates for these projects can be readily mapped to the UNFC using the bridging document.

An expert roundtable was organised by INTRAW on 24 January 2023 in collaboration with the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE) and the Pan-European Reserves and Resources Reporting Committee (PERC), and it brought together a small group of invited experts to discuss how to reinforce data confidence and transparency in assessments of mineral resources, resource potential and certainty of assessment of geothermal brines (INTRAW, 2023). The experts noted that the UNFC provides a broader high-level overview of potential opportunities and is applicable to a wide range of sectors, while CRIRSCO-aligned reporting provides a selective perspective of mineral endowments as only 'viable' projects are effectively reported. Participants agreed that the UNFC is well tailored for resource inventories, since it encompasses all ('viable' and 'unviable') deposits / projects, and that it provides the possibility of assessing the combined feasibility of energy and mineral resources. As a result of the discussions, the experts concluded that combined estimates of energy and mineral potential should be subject to testing within the working groups "geothermal" and "minerals" of the UNECE Experts Group on Resource Management (EGRM) supporting UNFC.

While the CRIRSCO reporting template (CRIRSCO, 2024a) discussed above is explicitly applicable to extraction of metals from brines (Clause 2.4) and the EGRM has developed reporting guidance for energy harvesting from geothermal systems (UNECE, 2022a), neither of them yet has developed guidance for assessing and reporting on combined extraction systems.

Such guidelines for assessment of the combined extraction of heat and minerals are needed in order to fully evaluate the potential of such systems. It can be easily imagined that there are examples where neither the extraction of heat nor minerals alone would be commercially viable, but the combination of both would result in a viable project. It could be also conceivable that the ESG assessment would give different results for heat and minerals. This might be as simple as different regulatory systems applicable (see discussions in Section 4.3) or more complex public attitudes to renewable energy and 'mining' projects respectively.

Differing reservoirs for heat and minerals - The extraction of heat and of minerals may have different time-lines, meaning that the amount of accessible minerals could become exhausted before the heat reservoir is drawn down. There could be various reasons for this, including the precipitation of secondary minerals and the clogging of certain fractions of the pore-space or dissolution kinetics. There is also likely a difference between the reservoir volumes from which heat and from which brine can be extracted, together with different replenishment timelines (if any). The problem has been addressed in a recent paper (Pugh et al., 2023).

Treatment of multiple commodities - However, the UNECE also published a case-study (EGRM, 2024a) that discusses the UNFC-classification for a multi-commodity mine, where each commodity has different time-lines. The classification of each commodity depends on market conditions and can even result in shifts in primary product.

The UNFC Supplement on Geothermal Energy (UNECE, 2022) acknowledges the possibility that other products, such as minerals, in addition to energy may be obtained from a project (§ B.10). The Supplement stipulates that such other products should be classified

according to the relevant UNFC specifications. In this case it would require those applied to minerals. Both revenue streams need to be combined for the final economic evaluation. Conceptually, combined extraction could be considered a cascaded project (cf. § D.21), as mineral extraction would follow heat extraction (compare Figure 2). Additional complexities must also be considered, as there may be certain pre-treatment processes to remove constituents from the geothermal fluids, such as those needed to prevent scaling, that could result in secondary value-streams. In such a case, the extraction of minerals is an integral part of the geothermal energy system with material flows reflected as a revenue stream rather than a cost factor (due to disposal costs). A conceptual model of the various material and revenue streams would need to be drawn up in order to decide, which UNFC specifications would need to be applied to which part of the project. To complicate the question further, a project of this nature might not sell energy on the market, but consumes the energy internally to reduce the buy-in of energy for mineral extraction. Under such circumstances, the 'Reference Point' for economic evaluation (§ E.23) would be within the boundaries of the project. § E.25 specifies that *"An Intermediate Node might be necessary to reference where a relevant quantity, different from the Geothermal Energy Source, enters the Project or occurs in between the energy process. Depending upon the specific Project, it could be necessary to report additional energy and/or mass fluxes associated with Intermediate Nodes in order to provide a clear description of the Project operation. ... In general, these additional quantities should be disclosed together with a clear description/ definition of the Intermediate Node."*

Although Section J of the UNFC Supplement is designed for multiple energy products, e.g. heat and electricity, it could be extended to cover energy and non-energy products. Namely:

§ J.41 states *"Where a Project produces more than one Geothermal Energy Product (e.g., heat and electricity), the corresponding Geothermal Energy Resources shall be estimated and classified separately but included in a single report for the Project. Quantities of different Geothermal Energy Products cannot be aggregated."* In other words, separate assessments for energy and minerals will need to be prepared, including the respective technology, economic and ESG aspects. The assessments would then be combined in an overall evaluation weighing potentially conflicting conclusions and/or emphasising the synergistic aspects.

§ J.42 notes *"When a Project requires significant input energy fluxes (e.g., electrical energy to drive heat pump compressors or well production/injection pumps), these quantities should be estimated and reported along with, but separately to, the Geothermal Energy Products unless they are generated by the project itself and consumed in the project operation, in which case they can be classified separately as E3.1. Any energy or mass quantity that is considered relevant within the Project may be explicitly identified as separate and reported, together with its Intermediate Node. These quantities are not separately classified but are considered within the classification of the estimated Geothermal Energy Resource."* For exactly this reason the materials and energy flow assessments outlined in Chapter 2 are to be undertaken. They inform the assessments on the basis of the chosen extraction technology and plant layout.

§ J.43 states *"Quantities estimated at different Intermediate Nodes or Reference Points in the same Project can be aggregated. The Evaluator shall ensure coherence of the aggregation. UNFC, Part II, Section II provides additional guidance on the issue of aggregation of estimated*

quantities. In general, aggregated quantities must have the same nature (e.g., heat or electricity). For example, similar applications (e.g. estimates of heat delivered from a single borehole along two different pipes to two different heat exchangers could be aggregated, but heat delivered to one of those heat exchangers cannot be aggregated with heat delivered to a room via a GSHP downstream from the second heat exchanger)." The aggregation can be extended to allow for different minerals being extracted potentially at different stages of the combined extraction project. Thus, it is conceivable that certain (marketable) minerals may already be extracted at certain purification steps before the thermal water reaches the heat exchanger. Further minerals then may be recovered in the actual extraction step. The classification according to the three axes E, F, and G will need to be carried out separately for the aspects of energy and minerals. Evaluating a geothermal resource that could be suitable for combined extraction of heat and minerals is likely to be a multidisciplinary effort, involving not only the assessment of the reservoir, but also the extractability and marketability of the mineral value. The categorisation for minerals needs to be carried out according to the UNFC supplementary specifications for minerals (UNECE, 2021) and geothermal energy (UNECE, 2022a).

Qualified experts - This will require a group of evaluators with specific qualifications. § O.84 of the UNFC supplementary specifications for geothermal energy resources provides in principle for such complex situations (UNECE, 2022a). One qualified expert will take the lead and sign off the report responsible after obtaining assurance that the contributions by other specialists are of sufficient quality.

CRMA relevance - This type of a co-production process would meet the goals of EU policy (CRMA 2024) to recover as much mineral value as possible from material extracted from underground.

§ L.51 discusses certain framework conditions, such as subsidies, that may influence the economic viability of a project. In the case of combined extraction, the provisions of the CRM-Act (CRMA 2024) may also be relevant. For instance, the Commission may consider certain projects as 'strategic' and offer support to secure financing. Similar support may be(come) available at national level.

Different regulatory regimes - As has been discussed in Ch. 4, the regulatory regimes across Europe for deep geothermal heat extraction and even more so that for combined extraction in most cases is not very well developed. The extraction of geothermal waters as such and the extraction of dissolved substances from those waters thus may be governed by different licenses. While in some jurisdictions one regulator would be appointed to lead and coordinate the licensing process covering multiple areas of regulation, this may not be the case everywhere. In consequence, both licenses may have different time-frames in consequence, which will have repercussions for the economic assessment of the project.

Technology Readiness Levels - Combined extraction is an emerging field, where the extraction technologies for metals are under development, which may have repercussions on the respective classification along the F-axis. This can mean that the technology readiness levels (TRL) for the geothermal and mineral parts may be different. While the commercialisation of DLE is rapidly advancing and the extraction technologies are rapidly maturing, they may still face challenges for other metals, e.g. the stability of ion-exchange resins and membranes high-temperature environment, or sufficient selectivity in highly saline waters. Project development thus will always include an

experimental or optimisation phase for the metal extraction technology, which would be reflected in the F-axis classification. It is likely that this aspect dominates the classification, given that heat-exchange is a mature technology.

Multiple ownership - Both, CRIRSCO-aligned reporting and UNFC-classification are project specific, meaning that they report on a resource that is owned by a specific owner. It would be conceivable that in the case of adding a mineral extraction project to an existing geothermal project that there would be two distinct owners. In this case, a joint reporting or classification will not be so straightforward, although both are linked and the minerals part will depend on the operation of the geothermal part. This would need to be reflected in the description of the logic for the G-axis classification.

5.5 DECISION-MAKING IN A UNFC EVALUATION

UNECE (2022) proposes a decision-making tree for each of the 'axes' during the evaluation of resources (Figure 29-31). These decision trees offer a systematic approach to classifying projects according to the guidelines. A limitation of these tools is that they are designed for application to standard single resource projects. Their application to more complex situations requires additional considerations.

For combined extraction projects involving both geothermal energy and minerals, the evaluation process should be conducted separately for each product while recognising their interdependencies. This means the decision-making process must be repeated for each 'product', whether it is heat or extracted metal(s). For each of the three axes (E, F and G), a separate decision tree is provided. By following the arrows from decision box to decision box, the user will end up in a box giving the most suitable classification at the highest hierarchical level for the given axis.

- 'End boxes' have a green colour fill. In some cases, the end box is red, suggesting that additional information is required to fully classify the project.
- The arrows connecting the boxes are coloured: red represents the direction for decision NO; green represents the direction for decision YES; with a blue arrow, no decision has to be made (passing information only).
- For the E Axis, a loop is required because there are potentially a suite of issues pertaining to the 'license to operate' in the environmental, societal, economic, legal, etc. domains, that need to be resolved. As a consequence, there will usually be multiple contingencies for each of the iterations of the loop and the overall project E-classification should be based on the lowest ranking one.

When applying these decision trees to a combined extraction project, evaluators should:

1. Begin by assessing each axis separately for both geothermal energy and mineral resources.
2. For the E-axis evaluation (Figure 27), assess all environmental-socio-economic factors including market conditions, regulatory frameworks, and social licence to operate for both energy and mineral extraction.
3. For the F-axis evaluation (Figure 30), consider the technical feasibility and maturity of both the geothermal energy extraction and mineral extraction technologies. The F-axis classification reflects the project activities with the lowest maturity, which for geothermal applications include:

Figure 29: UNFC E-axis decision-making tree

Figure 31: UNFC G-axis decision-making tree

- a. Geological studies
 - b. Geophysical studies
 - c. Geochemical studies
 - d. Geomechanical studies
 - e. Reservoir/subsurface modelling studies
 - f. Well/borehole drilling and completion studies
 - g. Surface equipment/infrastructure studies
 - h. Siting/logistics
4. For the G-axis evaluation (Figure 31), evaluate confidence levels in the estimates for both geothermal resources and mineral content separately.
 5. After separate evaluations, determine the overall project classification, recognising that different products from the same project may have different UNFC classifications.

While the UNFC supplementary specifications for minerals (UNECE 2024) do not include comparable decision-making trees, it is conceivable that the decision trees developed for geothermal resources are also applicable to minerals. As stipulated in the guidance note on the use of the CRIRSCO Template to UNFC bridging document (CRIRSCO and UNECE, 2024), the sub-category coding for the E and F axes should be determined by checking the documentation supporting the CRIRSCO estimates against the detailed specifications for each axis.

5.6 MAPPING CRIRSCO-ALIGNED RESOURCE REPORTING TO UNFC CLASSIFICATION

As noted earlier, industry typically uses reporting that aligned to the CRIRSCO standards as it is this style of a report that is expected by capital allocators. As has been noted further, the CRIRSCO-aligned resource reporting to date only covers minerals, but not (geothermal) energy resources. On the other hand, for the purpose of strategic assessments, the European Commission and some national governments require a classification of the resources in question according to UNFC. Guidance for both, mineral and geothermal resource classification under UNFC is available. A bridging document between the two systems is available (UNECE, 2025), together with a more extensive guidance note on its usage (CRIRSCO and UNECE, 2024).

When mapping estimates from CRIRSCO-aligned reports (such as JORC) to UNFC classification, a structured process should be followed as outlined in the CRIRSCO-UNFC Bridging Document (UNECE, 2024). This process provided in the bridging document and summarised in Table 7 below, ensures consistency and prevents double-counting of resources.

This mapping will consist of three steps:

1. A conversion of the CRIRSCO-compliant report for the mineral aspects based on the bridging document and accompanying guidance note on its usage (CRIRSCO and UNECE, 2024);
2. A classification of the geothermal part according to the UNFC supplementary specifications for geothermal energy resources (UNECE, 2022);
3. A combination of both assessments into an overall classification of the project.

Table 7: Standard mapping of CRIRSCO Template aligned estimates to UNFC Categories (from UNECE, 2025)

CRIRSCO Template		Corresponding UNFC Category ^c	UNFC Class
Public Report and Study Types ^a	Standard Definitions		
Feasibility Study or Life of Mine Plan ^b (for an operating mine)	Mineral Reserves	Proved Probable	Viable Projects
Pre-feasibility Study ^d	Mineral Reserves	Proved Probable	Potentially Viable Projects
Feasibility Study, Life of Mine Plan ^b (for an operating mine) or Pre-feasibility Study ^e	Mineral Resources (exclusive of Mineral Reserves)	Measured	G1
		Indicated	G2
		Inferred	G3
Scoping Study report or other Public Report on a Mineral Resource estimate ^f	Mineral Resources	Measured	G1
		Indicated	G2
		Inferred	G3
Public Report on exploration stage projects	Exploration Target	E3 F3 G4	Prospective Projects
	Exploration Results	Estimates not published	
Not applicable ^g	Estimates obtained from historical reports ^h		Non-viable Projects

The responsibility for the content of reporting according to a CRIRSCO aligned code rests with a Competent Person (CP), who has proven experience with the type of mineralisation in question. Conversely, the classification according to UNFC is carried out by a Qualified Expert (QE). Their roles and responsibilities are not identical (UNECE, 2025).

In the case of combined extraction, as there are two or more resource types, more than one QE may be required, with expertise in geothermal systems and with expertise in metal extraction and reservoir calculation for such systems. The necessary qualifications and experience are discussed in (CRIRSCO and UNECE, 2024).

When determining the Mineral Resources and Reserves for a combined extraction project, it is essential that each category of resource is tracked individually to avoid double-counting. The reservoir estimation also has a bearing on the distinction between resources and reserves. In accordance with the bridging document (UNECE, 2024), only Mineral Resources reported as exclusive of Mineral Reserves should be used when mapping to UNFC to prevent overlapping estimates.

UNECE (2025) states that in UNFC, estimates in classes such as 221 are always exclusive of other classes, such as 111, to avoid double-counting of quantities. Where classes are aggregated, this must be documented explicitly (e.g., 111 + 221). To the contrary, the CRIRSCO Template allows for both, Mineral Resources and Mineral Reserves to be reported for a project at the same time. Such reports must include a statement that clearly indicates, whether the Mineral Resources are inclusive of, or exclusive of (i.e. additional to), the Mineral Reserves. When assigning UNFC codes to such estimates, only the estimates for Mineral Resources reported exclusive of Mineral Reserves should be used to avoid double counting of the estimated volumes (CRIRSCO and UNECE, 2024). The reservoir estimation also has a bearing on the distinction between resources and reserves (cf. Figure 27).

Another aspect that is important to identify is the reference point - a defined location within the development at which the reported estimate is made. This point must be clearly specified in the UNFC classification. For geothermal energy, this might be at the point of heat transfer or electricity generation, while for minerals it might be an *in situ* estimate at the processing plant input or at the point of refined product output.

UNECE (2025) also discusses the transposition of exploration targets of CRIRSCO into a UNFC classification. The process will be somewhat different for combined extraction systems, as this depends on the reservoir estimation that is discussed e.g. by Pugh et al. (2023). This reservoir estimation is inspired by the practice in the oil & gas industry and based on various geological, hydrological and geohydraulic parameters.

UNECE (2025) states that in UNFC, estimates in classes such as 221 are always exclusive of other classes, such as 111, to avoid double-counting of quantities

An additional consideration of the internally consumed energy by the mineral extraction side and for heating buildings, impacts the classification of the geothermal part of the project and influences the economic assessment of the mineral extraction part. This interdependency must be accounted for in the overall project classification.

5.7 RECOMMENDATIONS FOR UNFC EVALUATIONS OF COMBINED EXTRACTION PROJECTS

As noted above, § J.41 of the UNFC supplementary specifications on geothermal energy resources (UNECE, 2022a) provide for cases where not only heat is extracted. There is no difficulty in accommodating such situations in principle. However, the challenge remains that the reservoirs accessed for the extraction of heat and of mineral value will be different with different time-lines to depletion. This needs to be considered, when evaluating times to amortisation and returns of investment vs. time.

In addition, the extractable mineral value will depend on a variety of process-related factors that determine the assessment of the F-axis and indirectly, through the extraction efficiency and effectiveness, also the G-axis assessment.

The evaluation of such projects will require a multi-disciplinary team with one lead Qualified Expert taking overall responsibility for the final UNFC coding.

Based on the guidance in the CRIRSCO-UNFC Bridging Document and the specific challenges of combined extraction projects, the following integrated approach is recommended:

1. **Separate Product Classification:** Qualified Experts should classify geothermal energy and mineral products separately, as recommended in § J.41 of the UNFC supplement on geothermal energy (UNECE 2022a), but include them in a single comprehensive project report.
2. **Comprehensive Conceptual Model:** Project developers should develop a conceptual model that encompasses all relevant processes. Such models will facilitate the delineation of the 'energy' and 'minerals' components that must be assessed according to the respective UNFC guidance documents (UNECE, 2021, and UNECE, 2022a) and will facilitate the sub-project definition as per point 6 below.
3. **Detailed Materials and Energy Flow Assessment:** Qualified Experts should conduct a detailed analysis of all material and energy flows within the system. This assessment will inform the E-axis evaluation by identifying potentially harmful mass flows (e.g.,

- hazardous chemicals and waste streams). Such modelling will likely be required for environmental impact assessments and permitting procedures.
4. **Process Interdependencies:** Qualified Experts should recognise that separating energy extraction assessment from mineral value extraction may not be straightforward, as these processes may be intertwined and influence each other. For instance, as Figure 6 and 7 indicate, pre-treatment steps before heat extraction may give rise to solid precipitates containing valuable minerals. These may need to be assessed as mineral raw materials streams rather than waste.
 5. **Internal Energy Utilisation:** Classification should account for harvested energy that is not sold as a product but instead used to power mineral extraction processes (see explanation of E3.1 in UNECE, 2019, and UNECE, 2022a). From an economic perspective, this represents a cost saving as external energy does not need to be purchased. The UNFC classification should reflect both commercially sold energy and internally utilised energy.
 6. **Depletion Time-lines:** Qualified Experts must address the technical and economic implications of different depletion rates between heat and mineral resources in the overall UNFC classification of the project.
 7. **Double-Counting:** When mapping CRIRSCO-reported resources to UNFC, Qualified Experts must ensure that Mineral Resources are reported exclusive of Mineral Reserves to prevent double-counting.
 8. **Competency Requirements:** Project sponsors should ensure assessments are performed by Qualified Experts with appropriate experience in geothermal energy and mineral resource assessment respectively. In case of a single investment decision it would be strongly recommended that there is a lead Qualified Expert who takes overall responsibility and ensures that there are not any mutual contradictory assumptions in the separate assessments of energy and minerals resources.
 9. **Reference Point Specification:** Qualified Experts should clearly define reference points for each product stream to ensure clarity in what the reported quantities represent.
 10. **Sub-Project Definition:** Where appropriate, Qualified Experts should define sub-projects within the overall project to facilitate a more accurate classification of different resource components, namely heat and minerals. Precise sub-project definition also will allow to define the component that is critical for the TRL evaluation along the F-axis.
 11. **Cascaded Project Consideration:** Qualified Experts should evaluate, whether the combined extraction should be treated as a cascaded project, with mineral extraction following heat extraction.

5.8 INFORMING THE UNRMS

The United Nations Resource Management System (UNECE, 2022c) in essence provides a template for a structured statement about the properties of a resource and its socio-economic, environmental, and socio-political context. This structured statement then can form the basis for its management on both, an operational as well as a strategic level. The ESG requirements formulated in this report and the proposed guidance for the UNFC classification of combined extraction of metal value and heat will provide the core of information for describing a resource according to the UNRMS.

Table 8: Step-by-Step Application of UNRMS (cf. UNECE, 2022c)

1. Define the Objective
<p>Clarify what you’re trying to manage:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A specific project (e.g. a combined extraction project), • A national or regional resource inventory, • A sectoral strategy (e.g. minerals for the energy transition), • Or a cross-sector integration plan (e.g. mining, land, water).
2. Identify and Classify the Resource
<p>Use the UN Framework Classification (UNFC) to assess:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Geological knowledge (G axis), • Project feasibility (F axis), • Socio-economic and environmental viability (E axis).
3. Map Against the 11 UNRMS Principles
<p>These include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrated and inclusive management, • Circular economy and zero-waste approaches, • Climate and SDG alignment, • Just transition and social equity, • Lifecycle thinking. <p><i>Action:</i> Assess how your resource aligns with each principle. Identify gaps or risks (e.g. lack of community consent, water scarcity, or poor energy efficiency).</p>
4. Apply the 54 Measurable Requirements
<p>These serve as “checkpoints” across four domains:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy and governance (e.g. legal clarity, permitting), • Social and environmental performance (e.g. emissions, land use), • Financial and technical planning (e.g. capex/opex, innovation), • Institutional capacity (e.g. data systems, training, local participation). <p>Use UNECE’s template or guidance to check which requirements are met or need development.</p>
5. Build a Resource Management Plan
<p>Using the above inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set short-, medium- and long-term objectives, • Define stakeholders, roles, and engagement plans, • Align with national/international policy goals (e.g. Paris Agreement, SDGs, EU Critical Raw Materials Act), • Plan for data collection, monitoring, and reporting. <p><i>Optional tools:</i> GIS, mine planning software, life-cycle assessment tools, stakeholder mapping (cf. Mitchell et al. 2025).</p>
6. Implement and Monitor
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operationalise the plan with KPIs and adaptive governance mechanisms, • Engage in periodic evaluation using UNRMS principles, • Report results in a structured and transparent way (to investors, government, public).

To apply the United Nations Resource Management System (UNRMS) in a practical case – for example, managing a combined extraction project in the context of a national raw materials strategy – one follows the structured, modular process that combines technical data, governance principles, and stakeholder inputs as outlined in Table 8.

6 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

Impact assessment of combined extraction

The Environmental, Societal, and Governance (ESG) assessment started out from three working hypotheses, namely that

- a) every flux of energy or mass constitutes a potential source of environmental risk,
- b) the combined extraction of heat and metals is likely to have less impacts than conventional metal mining, and
- c) lower mass movements are likely to entail lower societal impacts, both objectively and subjectively.

The key instrument for assessment is a careful stock-tacking of all flows of mass and energy and the associated carbon-footprints. The embodied energy and associated carbon-footprint for ancillary processes and materials, such as reactants or sorption substrates also have to be taken into consideration. Mass-flow diagrams for the extraction processes investigated under CRM-geothermal were developed. Owing to the still low Technology Readiness Levels (TLR) of these processes, the diagrams had to remain qualitative and could not be developed into full Sankey-diagrams. A somewhat more complete data-set was available for the Cornwall-site with ongoing demonstration-scale development.

However, it is evident that the mass-movements are by orders of magnitude lower than for conventional mining. Most notable is the absence of significant extractive waste, a major source of potential impact in conventional mining.

The method presented will allow to construct convincing case-studies that will eventually be able to demonstrate the low impact of such combined extraction projects quantitatively, once mass-flow diagrams are constructed and populated with the respective data.

Regulatory challenges of combined extraction

At the time of writing, the majority of European countries do not have explicit regulations for the combined extraction of heat and mineral value. It is probably safe to state that in any one given European country the regulatory treatment would depend on what the primary objective of the project is: extraction of heat or extraction of metal value. If the main objective is extraction of heat, in the first instance the laws pertaining to geothermal energy systems would apply. If the main objective is extraction of metal value, the respective mining legislation would apply and the system would be treated as a solution mining project. While in practical terms this would not change the investigations necessary for an adequate environmental impact assessment, the main difference would be how resulting residues and wastes are treated from a regulatory point of view.

Internalisation of ESG requirements

Although it has been shown that any environmental impacts from such projects will be low, this has to be demonstrated not only to the regulatory authorities, but also to public stakeholders (see CRM-geothermal Deliverable D4.2, Mitchell et al., 2025) with a view to create trust.

A key element of trust-building is a comprehensive assessment of potential risks and impacts together with proposals for their adequate management. In other words, the ESG requirements have to be fully internalised into the project planning process.

In consequence, a scheme for the internalisation of ESG requirements (cf. Section 4.3) has been developed, to be implemented through a check-list to accompany the development of combined extraction sites. The check-list takes prospective operators through several steps that help them identify ESG risks along the life-cycle of a facility. The operators are thus enabled to address these potential ESG risks before they become active risks.

The check-list helps to inform discussions with regulators and other (e.g. civil society) stakeholders as part of the trust-building processes, eventually leading to a social license to operate (SLO).

This check-list consists of two parts, namely a comprehensive project description that is based on the CRIRSCO reporting template or UNFC classification and on the extensive risk catalogue that is provided in Annex 2 to this report. This risk catalogue focuses on the environmental and OHS risks and less on societal or governance issues. However, levels of governance in European countries in general are high and give little rise of concern. Separate procedures for taking into consideration societal issues have been developed for CRM-geothermal D4.2 (Mitchell et al., 2025).

UNFC/CRIRSCO Compliant Resource Assessment

Resource assessments under CRIRSCO-compliant procedures (namely PERC in Europe) and classifications under UNFC serve to provide information on the viability of a proposed project. The viability is assessed in three dimensions, the availability of the target minerals, the technical and economic feasibility of extraction, and the compliance with ESG expectations.

Industry and in particularly stock-markets require CRIRSCO-aligned assessments as basis for allocating capital, but the European Commission expects projects to provide a resource classification according to UNFC for their CRM projects. A 'bridging' document jointly developed by CRIRSCO and UNECE intends align the two methods (UNECE, 2025; CRIRSCO and UNECE, 2024).

While the UNECE provides supplementary specifications on the application of the UNFC guidance to minerals and geothermal energy resources (UNECE, 2021, 2022a), there is no explicit guidance on the combined extraction of heat and energy. Implicitly, however, both guidance documents cover this case, as they require that the classification is being undertaken for each commodity separately. In other words, the extraction of heat for commercialisation in total or partially would be covered by the UNFC supplementary specifications on classifying geothermal projects, while the extraction of metal value from the produced fluids would be covered by the UNFC supplementary specifications on minerals, which already foresees the possibility that this may be done by 'solution mining'. Separating the assessment of the energy extraction assessment from that for the mineral value extraction, as stipulated by the UNFC guidance, may not be straightforward, as the processes may be intertwined and influencing each other. There may be also (pre-)treatment steps before the actual heat extraction that give rise to solid precipitates which could contain mineral value of interest. Rather than as a waste-stream these solids would need to be assessed as raw materials streams.

The classification of the geothermal energy aspect of the project must also account for quantities of product (i.e. heat) that are not sold for profit but used internally for instance in the extraction process. From an economic point of view, it may constitute a saving, as this heat does not need to be bought in form of fuels or electricity.

These considerations indicate that the UNFC assessment needs to be based on

- a) A conceptual model that encompasses all the relevant processes, and
- b) A detailed materials and energy flow assessment for the whole of the system.

The conceptual model allows the delineation of the 'energy' part and 'minerals' parts, which have to be subject to the assessment according to the respective UNFC guidance. The materials flow analysis based on the conceptual process will also inform the assessment along the E-axis, as potentially harmful mass flows (e.g. hazardous chemicals and waste streams) are identified.

A technical and economic difficulty arises from the fact, that the reservoirs from which heat and minerals are extracted are not necessarily the same and will not deplete at the same rate. This will need to be considered in the initial technical and economic viability assessment and hence in the overall UNFC classification of the project.

Given the increasing interest in combined extraction projects and their specific technical and economic complexities, it is recommended that the UNECE develop a dedicated guidance document that adequately addresses the case of combined extraction of heat and dissolved mineral value. Additionally, it would be useful if PERC and/or CRIRSCO could develop guidance on the reporting of estimates of mineral product quantities for this type of project and to include some commentary on this aspect in future updates of the CRIRSCO Template to UNFC bridging document.

7 REFERENCES

- ADESINA, A. (2021): Performance and Sustainability Overview of Sodium Carbonate Activated Slag Materials Cured at Ambient Temperature.- Resources, Environment and Sustainability, 3: 16 p., <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resenv.2021.100016>.
- ARRIZABALAGA, I. ET AL. (2019): Geothermal Energy Use, Country Update for Spain.- Proc. European Geothermal Congress, Den Haag, The Netherlands, 11-14 June 2019: 9 p., <https://europeangeothermalcongress.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/10/EGC2019.pdf> (accessed 24.09.25).
- BATINI, F. (2021): Proposal for a Harmonized European Geothermal Licensing Guidelines.- Report for the H2020 GEOENVIE Project: 7 p., https://www.geoenvi.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/European-Geothermal-Licensing-guidelines_FINAL-DRAFT_HE31052021.pdf (accessed 24.09.25).
- BINDSCHEDELER, S., LAURENT, G., SCHMID, E., JUNIER, P. (2025): Proof-of-concept oxalogenesis-oxalatrophy pathway for biorecovery of Li and Sr.- CRM-geothermal Deliverable D3.4: 19 p., <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15075346>.
- BINDSCHIEDLER, S., LAURENT, G., JUNIER, P., BRILL, F. (forthcoming): Effectiveness of microbial biorecovery of metals from geothermal brines.- CRM-geothermal Deliverable D3.5: x p.
- CORREIA, V., et al. (forthcoming): Market analysis & decision support of the combined extraction of CRM + energy.- CRM-geothermal Deliverable D4.3: x p.
- CRIRSCO COMMITTEE FOR MINERAL RESERVES INTERNATIONAL REPORTING STANDARDS (2024a): International Reporting Template for the Public Reporting of Exploration Targets, Exploration Results, Mineral Resources and Mineral Reserves, June 2024.- 78 p., https://crirSCO.com/wp-content/uploads/woocommerce_uploads/2024/06/CRIRSCO_International_Reporting_Template_June2024_Update_Approved_for_Release_20240627-dl8515.pdf (accessed 24.09.25).
- CRIRSCO COMMITTEE FOR MINERAL RESERVES INTERNATIONAL REPORTING STANDARDS (2024b): Environmental, Social & Governance (ESG) Definitions Guide in Support of the Public Reporting of Exploration Targets, Exploration Results, Mineral Resources and Mineral Reserves.- 21 p., https://percstandard.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/02/CRIRSCO-ESG-Guide_2024_Final_Approved.pdf (accessed 24.09.25).
- CRIRSCO & UNECE (2024): Guidance Note on the use of the Bridging Document between the CRIRSCO Template and UNFC.- EGRM-15/2024/INF.3, 8 April 2024: 36 p., https://unece.org/sites/default/files/2024-04/EGRM-15-2024-INF.3_UNECE_CRIRSCO_Guidance_Note_Use_of_CRIRSCOTemplate-UNFC_BridgingDoc.pdf?utm_source=miragenews&utm_medium=miragenews&utm_campaign=news (accessed 24.09.25)
- CRMA EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND COUNCIL (2024): Regulation (EU) 2024/1252 of 11 April 2024 establishing a framework for ensuring a secure and sustainable supply of critical raw materials and amending Regulations (EU) No 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, (EU) 2018/1724 and (EU) 2019/1020.- OJ L Series, 03.05.24, 67 p., https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=OJ:L_202401252.

- DALMAIS, E., RAVIER, G., MAURER, V., PANDÉLIS, B., FRIES, D., GENTER, A. (2022): Environmental and Socio-Economic Impact of Deep Geothermal Energy, an Upper Rhine Graben Perspective.- In: González Acevedo, Z.I., García Zarate, M.A. [Eds.] Geothermal Energy - Impacts and Improvements, <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.107395>.
- DI NOTO, V., NEGRO, E. (forthcoming): Report on the development of ion-exchange membranes and extraction fluids to selectively separate Li, Rb or Sr from the brines.- CRM-geothermal Deliverable D3.2: xx p.
- DROBE, M. (2000): Lithium – Sustainability Information.- 13 p., Hannover (Bundesanstalt für Geowissenschaften und Rohstoffe), https://www.bgr.bund.de/SharedDocs/Produkte/Downloads/Informationen_Nachhaltigkeit/lithium.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=1 (accessed 24.09.25).
- DUCOLI A , S., FAHIMI, A., MOUSA, E., YE, G., FEDERICI, S., FRONTERA, P., BONTEMPI, E. (2022): ESCAPE approach for the sustainability evaluation of spent lithium-ion batteries recovery: Dataset of 33 available technologies.- Data in Brief, **42**: 1-21, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.130493>.
- DUMAS, P. (2014): Developing Geothermal District Heating in Europe.- Report GEODH project: 60 p., http://geodh.eu/wp-content/uploads/2012/07/GeoDH-Report-2014_web.pdf (accessed 24.09.25).
- DUMAS, P., SERDJUK, M., KUTSCHICK, R., FRASER, S., REITH, S., KOELBEL, T. (2013): Report presenting proposals for improving the regulatory framework for geothermal electricity.- Deliverable 4.1 – Annex 1: Overview of national regulations for geothermal electricity, Project GEOELEC, 40 p., <http://www.geoelec.eu/wp-content/uploads/2011/09/4.1.pdf>, <http://www.geoelec.eu/wp-content/uploads/2011/09/D4.1-A.1-Overview-of-National-Rules-of-Licensing.pdf> (accessed 24.09.25).
- ECO-EFFICIENCY ET AL. (2023): Study supporting the elaboration of guidelines for best risk management approaches in the extractive sector.- Study prepared for the European Commission, DG ENV. awaiting publication.
- EGEC – EUROPEAN GEOTHERMAL ENERGY COUNCIL (2005?): K4RES-H - Key Issue 3 : Regulations for Geothermal Energy.- Report K4RES-H Project: 37 p., http://geodh.eu/wp-content/uploads/2012/11/K4RES-H_Geothermal_Regulations.pdf (accessed 24.09.25).
- EGEC – EUROPEAN GEOTHERMAL ENERGY COUNCIL (2022): Guidance on Licensing and Permitting – Case Geothermal Energy.- 40 p., <https://www.egec.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/08/Guidance-on-licensing-and-permitting-of-geothermal-projects-EGEC.pdf> (accessed 24.09.25).
- EGGELING, L., GENTER, A., KÖLBEL, T., MÜNCH, W. (2013): Impact of natural radionuclides on geothermal exploitation in the upper Rhine graben.- Geothermics, **47**: 80-88, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geothermics.2013.03.002>.

- EGRM EXPERT GROUP ON RESOURCES MANAGEMENT (2024a): Classifying the production of lithium, caesium and tantalum from the Tanco Mine, Manitoba, Canada, according to the United Nations Framework Classification for Resources – A Case Study.- ECE/ENERGY/GE.3/2024/12: 33 p., Geneva (UNECE), https://unece.org/sites/default/files/2024-04/Tanco%20Lithium%20CS_ECE-ENERGY-GE3-2024-12.pdf (accessed 24.09.25).
- EGRM EXPERT GROUP ON RESOURCES MANAGEMENT (2024b): Guidance Note on the use of the Bridging Document between the CRIRSCO Template and UNFC.- EGRM-15/2024/INF.3: 36 p., Geneva (CRIRSCO/UNECE), https://unece.org/sites/default/files/2024-04/EGRM-15-2024-INF.3_UNECE_CRIRSCO_Guidance_Note_Use_of_CRIRSCOTemplate-UNFC_BridgingDoc.pdf (accessed 24.09.25).
- ERM ENVIRONMENTAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT (2024): Zero Carbon Lithium™ - Environmental and Social Impact Assessment (ESIA).- ERM Report 0699805: 470 p., https://v-er.eu/app/uploads/2024/09/Vulcan-Zero-Carbon-Lithium-Project_ESIA-Report_Final_16092024_EN-4.pdf (accessed 24.09.25).
- EUROPEAN COMMISSION, DIRECTORATE-GENERAL FOR ENVIRONMENT, VAN KEER, I., LAENEN, B., BRONDERS, J. ET AL. (2021): Study supporting the development of general guidance on the implementation of the Extractive Waste Directive: Final Report.- 777 p., Publications Office of the European Union, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2779/147984>.
- FALCK, W.E., TIESS, G., MURGUÍA, D., MACHACEK, E., DOMENECH, T., HAMADOVÁ, B. (2017): Raw Materials Intelligence Tools and Methods.- H2020 Project MICA, Deliverable D5.1: 238 p., http://mica.eurogeosurveys.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/02/D5.1_Raw-Material-Intelligence-Methods-and-Tools.pdf (accessed 24.09.25).
- FELDBUSCH, E. et al. (forthcoming): Report on modified polymers as adsorbents and their effectiveness under geothermal conditions.- CRM-geothermal Deliverable D3.3: xx p.
- FRANKLIN ASSOCIATES (2022): Cradle-To-Gate Life Cycle Analysis of General Purpose Polystyrene (GPPS) Resin, Final Report.- Report submitted to American Chemistry Council (ACC) Plastics Division: 46 p., <https://www.americanchemistry.com/content/download/10598/file/Cradle-to-Gate-Life-Cycle-Analysis-of-General-Purpose-Polystyrene-Resin.pdf> (accessed 24.09.25).
- FRENZ, W. (2020): The Current Legal Framework for Geothermal Drilling – Geothermiebohrungen im aktuellen rechtlichen Kontext.- Mining Report Glückauf, 156(6): 567-577, https://mining-report.de/wp-content/uploads/pda/2020/12/MRG_2006_Rechtlicher_Kontext_Geothermie_Frenz_201204.pdf (accessed 24.09.25).
- FRIDRIKSSON, T., MATEOS MERINO, A., ORUCU, A.Y., AUDINET, P. (2017): Greenhouse Gas Emissions from Geothermal Power Production.- Proc. 42nd Workshop on Geothermal Reservoir Engineering, Stanford University, Stanford, California, February 13-15, 2017 SGP-TR-212, <https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/875761592973336676/pdf/Greenhouse-Gas-Emissions-from-Geothermal-Power-Production.pdf> (accessed 24.09.25).
- GATT, P. GRECH, P., DIERENDONCK, A. VAN (2022): Geology for Energy in Malta. Discussion paper published by the Malta Chamber of Geologists.- <https://www.mgeol.org/geology-for-energy-in-malta-discussion-document> (accessed 24.09.25).

- GEHLIN, S., ANDERSSON, O. (2016): Geothermal Energy Use, Country Update for Sweden.- European Geothermal Congress, Strasbourg, France, 19-24 Sept 2016: 11 p., https://media.geoenergicentrum.se/2017/02/Gehlin_Andersson_2016_-EGC-2016-CU-Sweden.pdf (accessed 24.09.25).
- GOLDBERG, V., KLUGE, T., NITSCHKE, F. (2022): Herausforderung und Chancen für die Lithiumgewinnung aus geothermalen Systemen in Deutschland – Teil 1: Literaturvergleich bestehender Extraktionstechnologien.- Grundwasser, 27(4): 239-259, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00767-022-00522-5>.
- GOLDBERG, V., NITSCHKE, F., KLUGE, T. (2022): Herausforderung und Chancen für die Lithiumgewinnung aus geothermalen Systemen in Deutschland – Teil 2: Potenziale und Produktionsszenarien in Deutschland.- Grundwasser, 27(4): 261-275, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00767-022-00523-54>.
- GOODMAN, R., ET AL. (2009): Geothermal Regulation Framework.- Final report from the Geothermal Regulation-Heat (GTR-H) project: no pagination, http://www.geoelec.eu/wp-content/uploads/2012/11/GTRH_final_Framework_Nov09.pdf (accessed 24.09.25).
- GRANT, A., DEAK, D., PELL, R. (2020): The CO₂ Impact of the 2020s Battery Quality Lithium Hydroxide Supply Chain.- 14 p., [https://static1.squarespace.com/static/5c9aa323c46f6d499a2ac1c5/t/5fe8ae081c123d7f84d3211d/1609084425044/The+CO₂+Impact+of+the+2020s+Battery+Quality+Lithium+Hydroxide+Supply+Chain.pdf](https://static1.squarespace.com/static/5c9aa323c46f6d499a2ac1c5/t/5fe8ae081c123d7f84d3211d/1609084425044/The+CO2+Impact+of+the+2020s+Battery+Quality+Lithium+Hydroxide+Supply+Chain.pdf) (accessed 24.09.25).
- GUTOWSKI T.G., SAHNI S., ALLWOOD J.M., ASHBY M.F., WORRELL E. (2013): The energy required to produce materials: constraints on energy-intensity improvements, parameters of demand.- Phil Trans R Soc A, 371: 20120003. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2012.000>.
- HANNONEN, K. (2020): Regulatory Framework on Geothermal Energy in Finland - Lessons learned from the Deep Heat-project in Otaniemi, Espoo.- Thesis, Itä-Suomen Yliopisto Environment and Climate Change Law: 55 p., https://erepo.uef.fi/bitstream/handle/123456789/22939/urn_nbn_fi_uef-20200855.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y (accessed 24.09.25).
- IEA INTERNATIONAL ENERGY AGENCY (2021): Spain 2021 – Energy Policy Review.- 242 p., <https://iea.blob.core.windows.net/assets/2f405ae0-4617-4e16-884c-7956d1945f64/Spain2021.pdf> (accessed 24.09.25).
- INTRAW (2023): Summary report from Expert roundtable on UNFC and CRIRSCO standards.- International Raw Material Observatory, published 1 March 2023: 4 p., https://intraw.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/02/Summary-Document-UNFC_CRIRSCO-roundtable.pdf (accessed 24.09.25).
- ISO INTERNATIONAL STANDARDIZATION ORGANIZATION (2006a): ISO 14040:2006 - Environmental management - Life cycle assessment - Principles and framework.- <https://www.iso.org/standard/37456.html> (accessed 24.09.25).
- ISO INTERNATIONAL STANDARDIZATION ORGANIZATION (2006b): ISO 14044:2006 - Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Requirements and guidelines.- <https://www.iso.org/standard/38498.html> (accessed 15.05.24).

- KARRECH, A., AZADI, M.R., ELCHALAKANI, M., SHAHIN, M.A., SEIBI, A.C. (2020): A review on methods for liberating lithium from pegmatites.- *Minerals Engineering*, **145**: 106085, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mineng.2019.106085>.
- KAYMAKCI, E., KÖLBEL, T. (2022): Geothermal Energy & Lithium Production. The „UnLimited Project“.- 17 p., <https://www.deutsche-rohstoffagentur.de/DERA/DE/Downloads/vortrag-lithium-koelbel-22.pdf> (accessed 24.09.25)
- KELLY, J.C., WANG, M., DAI, Q., WINJOBI, O. (2021): Energy, greenhouse gas, and water life cycle analysis of lithium carbonate and lithium hydroxide monohydrate from brine and ore resources and their use in lithium ion battery cathodes and lithium ion batteries.- *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, **174**(November 2021, 105762), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2021.105762>.
- LAGROU, D., PETITCLERC, E., HOES, H., DUPONT, N., LAENEN, B. (2019): Geothermal Energy Use, Country Update for Belgium.- *European Geothermal Congress 2019, Den Haag, The Netherlands, 11-14 June 2019*: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/335466240_Geothermal_Energy_Use_Country_Update_for_Belgium#fullTextFileContent (accessed 24.09.25).
- LÈBRE, E., STRINGER, M., SVOBODOVA, K., OWEN, J.R., KEMP, D., CÔTE, C., ARRATIA-SOLAR, A., VALENTA, R.K. (2020): The social and environmental complexities of extracting energy transition metals.- *Nature Communications*, **11**, Article No. 4823, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-020-18661-9>.
- LOHNE, H.P., FORD, E.P., MAJOURERD, M.M., RANDEBERG, E., BARRÉ, AS., WILDENBORG, T., BRUNNER, L. (2018): Foundations for well integrity and risk assessment.- *H2020 Project GeoWell, Deliverable D6.4*: 45 p., https://www.researchgate.net/publication/324573628_Well_integrity_risk_assessment_in_geothermal_wells_-_Status_of_today (accessed 24.09.25).
- MARCHEGIANI, P., MORGERA, E., PARKS, L. (2019): Indigenous peoples' rights to natural resources in Argentina: the challenges of impact assessment, consent and fair and equitable benefit-sharing in cases of lithium mining.- *The International J. of Human Rights*, **24**(2-3): 1-17, <https://doi.org/10.1080/13642987.2019.1677617>.
- MCCAY, A.T., FELIKS, M.E.J., ROBERTS, J.J. (2019): Life cycle assessment of the carbon intensity of deep geothermal heat systems: A case study from Scotland.- *Sci. total Env.*, 685: 208-219, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.05.311>.
- MENG, F., MCNEICE, J., ZADEH, S.S., GHAREMAN, A. (2019): Review of Lithium Production and Recovery from Minerals, Brines, and Lithium-Ion Batteries.- *Mineral Processing and Extractive Metallurgy Review*, **42**(2): 123-141, <https://doi.org/10.1080/08827508.2019.1668387>.
- MILLS, R. (2011): Brine mining the Puna for potash and lithium.- *www.mining.com – Ahead of the Herd, June 24, 2011*: <https://www.mining.com/brine-mining-the-puna-for-potash-and-lithium/> (accessed 24.09.25).
- MITCHELL, P., GOULET, L., TAYLOR, F., TUFO, R. (2025): Social Licence to Operate - Guidelines for Combined Geothermal – Metal Extraction Projects.- *CRM-geothermal Deliverable D4.2*: 41 p., <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15541803>.

- MOUCHOT, J., PRALLE, N., GIRARD, B., BRAND, S. (2023): Do Look Down! Sourcing Critical Material Lithium and Renewable Energy with Minimal Environmental Impact in Europe.- The Fourth EAGE Global Energy Transition Conference and Exhibition, Nov 2023, Volume 2023: 1-5, <https://doi.org/10.3997/2214-4609.202321107>.
- MTECT MINISTÈRE DE LA TRANSITION ÉCOLOGIQUE ET DE LA COHÉSION DES TERRITOIRES (2023): Réforme du code minier: Intégration des travaux miniers dans l'autorisation environnementale, servitudes d'utilité publique, garanties financières et police résiduelle.- 62 p., https://www.ecologie.gouv.fr/sites/default/files/Mardi_DGPR_18%20avril%202023_réforme%20code%20minier.pdf (accessed 24.09.25).
- MINLEX - MINPOL GMBH ET AL. (2017): Study - Legal framework for mineral extraction and permitting procedures for exploration and exploitation in the EU.- Report to the European Commission, DG GROW: 1920 p., <https://doi.org/10.2873/920344>.
- MOUSAVINEZHAD, S., et al. (2024): Environmental impact assessment of direct lithium extraction from brine resources: Global warming potential, land use, water consumption, and charting sustainable scenarios.- Resources, Conservation and Recycling, 205: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2024.107583>.
- MWEI-BREF GARBARINO, E., ORVEILLON, G., SAVEYN, H.G.M., BARTHE, P., EDER, P. (2018): Best Available Techniques (BAT) Reference Document for the Management of Waste from Extractive Industries in accordance with Directive 2006/21/EC.- JRC Science for Policy Report, EUR 28963 EN: 722 p., <http://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC109657> (accessed 24.09.25).
- NGUYEN, T.H., LEE, M.S. (2018): A Review on the Separation of Lithium Ion from Leach Liquors of Primary and Secondary Resources by Solvent Extraction with Commercial Extractants.- Process, 6, 55: 15 p., <https://doi.org/10.3390/pr6050055>.
- ORKUSTOFNUN & EIHP (2017): Geothermal Energy Utilisation Potential in Croatia Field and Study Visits' Report.- Orkustofnun (National Energy Authority, Iceland) and Energy Institute Hrvoje Požar, Croatia): 57 p., <https://orkustofnun.is/gogn/Skyrslur/OS-2017/OS-2017-02.pdf> (accessed 24.09.25).
- PELL, R., LINDSAY, J.J. (2021): Comparative Life Cycle Assessment Study of Solid State and Lithium-Ion Batteries for Electric Vehicle Application in Europe.- Report prepared for the European Federation for Transport and Environment: p., https://www.transportenvironment.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/2022_07_LCA_research_by_Minviro.pdf (accessed 24-09.25).
- PERC Pan European Reserves and Resources Reporting Committee (2021): Pan-European for the Public Reporting of Exploration Results, Mineral Resources and Mineral Reserves.- 98 p., https://percstandard.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/PERC_REPORTING_STANDARD_2021_RELEASE_01Oct21_full.pdf (accessed 24.09.25).
- PUGH, K., KENNEDY, J., MORRIS, N. (2023): Whitepaper: Mining a Liquid - A Novel Approach for Lithium Resource Estimation in Confined Saline Aquifers.- E3 Lithium: 13 p., Calgary, Alberta, <https://www.e3lithium.ca/resources/reports/technical/Whitepaper-20231023.pdf?v=070504?v=0.794> (accessed 24.09.25).

- PRASANACHANDRAN, R., THAYUMANASUNDARAM, S. (forthcoming): Effectiveness of microbial biorecovery of metals from geothermal brines.- CRM-geothermal Deliverable D3.7: x p.
- RAZMJOU, A. (2024): Direct Lithium Extraction (DLE): An Introduction. A report exploring the various technologies used for direct lithium extraction (DLE).- 24 p., <https://lithium.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/06/Direct-Lithium-Extraction-DLE-An-introduction-ILiA-June-2024-v.1-English-web.pdf> (accessed 24.09.25).
- RITCHIE, H. (2022): How does the land use of different electricity sources compare?.- Available from OurWorldinData.org, 'https://ourworldindata.org/land-use-per-energy-source' (accessed 08.09.25)
- RUPPRECHT, D., STEINER, C., HEIERMANN, M., RIEDEL, P. (2017): Summary of National Legal Requirements, Current Policies and Regulations of Shallow Geothermal Use.- INTERREG Project GEOPLASMA-CE, Deliverable T2.4.1: 127 p., <https://programme2014-20.interreg-central.eu/Content.Node/GeoPLASMA-CE/CE177-GeoPLASMA-CE-D.T2.4.1-Summary-of-national-legal-requr.pdf> (accessed 24.09.25).
- SAMESG SOUTH AFRICAN ENVIRONMENTAL, SOCIAL AND GOVERNANCE COMMITTEE (2017): The South African Guideline for the Reporting of Environmental, Social and Governance Parameters Within the Solid Minerals and Oil and Gas Industries.- 19 p., <https://www.samcode.co.za/samcode-ssc/samesg> (accessed 24.09.25).
- SANKEY, H.R. (1896): The Thermal Efficiency of Steam-Engines.- in: M.P.I.C.E. **125**: 182–242.
- SCHMIDT, M. (2023): Rohstoffrisikobewertung – Lithium.– DERA Rohstoffinformationen, **54**: 81 p., Berlin (Deutsche Rohstoffagentur), https://www.deutsche-rohstoffagentur.de/DE/Gemeinsames/Produkte/Downloads/DERA_Rohstoffinformationen/rohstoffinformationen-54.pdf (accessed 24.09.25).
- SCHOMBERG, A.C., BRINGEZU, S. & FLÖRKE, M. (2021): Extended life cycle assessment reveals the spatially-explicit water scarcity footprint of a lithium-ion battery storage. Commun. Earth & Environ., **2**(11): 10 p., <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-020-00080-9>.
- SOUTHON, M., KRUMDIEK, S. (2013): Energy Return on Investment (EROI) for Distributed Powergeneration from Low-Temperature Heat Sources Using Theorganic Rankine Cycle.- Proc. 35th New Zealand Geothermal Workshop, 18-20 November 2013, Rotorua, New Zealand: 8 p., <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/259953342> (accessed 24.09.25).
- SQM Sociedad Quimica y Minera (2021): Sustainability Report 2021.- 330 p., https://sqm.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/SQM-Reporte-2021-ingles_Final_compressed.pdf (accessed 24.09.25).
- STEELE-SCHOBER, T., ALLINGTON, R., GORDON, S. (2020): ESG - An overview for CRIRSCO Opportunities and challenges for trustworthy and relevant minerals reporting.- https://percstandard.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/CRIRSCO_AGM-ESGpresentation17Sept2020slidesandnotes_compressed.pdf (accessed 24.09.25).
- STRAUCH, B., ZIMMER, M. (2025): Report on Membrane-Based Gas Extraction from Brine.- CRM-geothermal Deliverable D3.6: 14 p., <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15606928>.

- SULLIVAN, J.L., CLARK, C.E., HAN, J., WANG, M. (2010): Life-Cycle Analysis Results of Geothermal Systems in Comparison to Other Power Systems.- Argonne National Laboratory, Report ANL/ESD/10-5: 60 p., https://greet.es.anl.gov/files/geothermal_and_other_power (accessed 24.09.25).
- SZALEWSKA, M. (2021): Legal Aspects of Geothermal Energy Use in Poland.- Comparative Law Review, **27**: 385-406, <https://doi.org/10.12775/CLR.2021.017>.
- TADESSE, B., MAKUEI, F., ALBIJANIC, B., DYER, L. (2019): The beneficiation of lithium minerals from hard rock ores: A review.- Minerals Engineering, **131**: 170-184, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mineng.2018.11.023>.
- TOST, M., LESSER, P., POELZER, G., AKHOURI, U., GUGERELL, K. (2021): Social Licence to Operate (SLO) Guidelines For Europe.- H2020 Project MIREU, Deliverable D4.3: 27 p., <https://mireu.eu/sites/default/files/2021-05/D%204.3.pdf> (accessed 24.09.25).
- TZEFERIS, P.G. (2018): The Licensing System for Mines and Quarrying Works in Greece, 2018.- 7 p., <http://www.latomet.gr/ypan/Hypertrak/BinaryContent.aspx?pagenb=18560> (accessed 24.09.25).
- UNECE – UNITED NATIONS ECONOMIC COMMISSION FOR EUROPE (2017): Guidelines for Application of the United Nations Framework Classification for Resources (UNFC) to Uranium and Thorium Resources.- UNECE Energy Series, **55**: 64 p., https://unece.org/DAM/energy/images/pub/1734723E_WEB.pdf (accessed 24.09.25).
- UNECE – UNITED NATIONS ECONOMIC COMMISSION FOR EUROPE (2019): United Nations Framework Classification for Resources - Update 2019.- UNECE Energy Series, **61**: 20 p., https://unece.org/fileadmin/DAM/energy/se/pdfs/UNFC/publ/UNFC_ES61_Update_2019.pdf (accessed 24.09.25).
- UNECE – UNITED NATIONS ECONOMIC COMMISSION FOR EUROPE (2021): Supplementary Specifications for the Application of the United Nations Framework Classification for Resources to Minerals.- 27 p., <https://unece.org/sites/default/files/2022-01/UNFC%20Mineral%20Specifications%202021.pdf> (accessed 24.09.25).
- UNECE – UNITED NATIONS ECONOMIC COMMISSION FOR EUROPE (2022a): Supplementary Specifications for the application of the United Nations Framework Classification for Resources (Update 2019) to Geothermal Energy Resources.- 26 p., https://unece.org/sites/default/files/2022-12/UNFC_Geothermal_Specs_25October_2022.pdf (accessed 24.09.25).
- UNECE – UNITED NATIONS ECONOMIC COMMISSION FOR EUROPE (2022b): Guidance Note on Competency Requirements for the Estimation, Classification and Management of Resources.- Prepared by the Competency Working Group of the Expert Group on Resource Management, 25.10.2022. https://unece.org/sites/default/files/2022-11/Guidance_Note_on_Competency_Requirements_25_October_2022.pdf (accessed 24.09.25).
- UNECE – UNITED NATIONS ECONOMIC COMMISSION FOR EUROPE (2022c): United Nations Resource Management System - Principles And Requirements.- UNECE Energy Series, **74**: 20 p., https://unece.org/sites/default/files/2023-02/2229237_E_ECE_ENERGY_144_WEB.pdf (accessed 24.09.25).

- UNECE – UNITED NATIONS ECONOMIC COMMISSION FOR EUROPE (2025): Bridging Document between the Committee for Mineral Reserves International Reporting Standards Template and the United Nations Framework Classification for Resources.- UNECE Report ECE/ENERGY/GE.3/2025/6: 20 p., Geneva, https://unece.org/sites/default/files/2024-04/CRIRSCO_Template_UNFC_BD_ECE_ENERGY_GE.3_2024_5_ENG.pdf (accessed 24.09.25).
- UNFCCC UNITED NATIONS FRAMEWORK CONVENTION ON CLIMATE CHANGE (1992): United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change.- 33 p., https://unfccc.int/files/essential_background/background_publications_htmlpdf/application/pdf/conveng.pdf (accessed 24.09.25)
- UNFCCC UNITED NATIONS FRAMEWORK CONVENTION ON CLIMATE CHANGE (1997): Kyoto Protocol to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change.- FCCC/CP/1997/L.7/Add.1: 24 p., <https://unfccc.int/documents/2409> (accessed 24.09.25).
- VALKERING, P. ET AL. (2020): Decision-Making Process Mapping.- H2020 Project GEOENVIE, Deliverable D.4.1: 240 p., <https://www.geoenvi.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/D4.1-Decision-making-process-mapping.pdf> (accessed 24.07.25).
- VOLT LITHIUM CORP. (2023): Volt Lithium Corp. Announces successful pilot project, confirming 90% lithium recovery, commercial economics and unprecedented breakthrough.- Press release, 24.05.23, <https://voltlithium.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/Volt-Lithium-Corp.-Announces-Pilot-Project-Results.pdf> (accessed 24.09.25).
- VULCAN ENERGY (2023): Empowering a Carbon Neutral Future.- Sustainability Report 23: 67 p., <https://api.investi.com.au/api/announcements/vul/04ca21c8-1b4.pdf> (accessed 24.09.25).
- WRI & WBCSD World Resources Institute & World Business Council for Sustainable Development (2004): GHG Protocol Corporate Accounting and Reporting Standard (Revised ed.).- 114 p., <https://ghgprotocol.org/corporate-standard> (accessed. 24.09.25).
- ZOTZMANN, J. et al. (forthcoming): Report on adsorption of Li and Sr by ion sieves: Tested adsorption materials and upscaling.- CRM-geothermal deliverable D3.1: xx p..

APPENDIX 1 – COUNTRY REGULATORY SYSTEMS FOR COMBINED EXTRACTION

While most of the review work was undertaken in 2023, the work was revisited in June 2025 in order to assure that recent regulatory and policy developments are captured that may be relevant for combined extraction projects.

7.1 AUSTRIA

Geothermal exploration and exploitation are governed by a range of laws and regulations at both, the federal and regional level. At the federal level, the main laws and regulations that apply include the Federal Mining Act (Bundesberggesetz), the Federal Environmental Impact Assessment Act (UVP-G), and the Federal Waste Management Act (AWG). The Geothermal Energy Act (Geothermiegesetz) sets out the legal framework for the exploration, exploitation, and use of geothermal energy. It defines the conditions and procedures for obtaining permits and licenses for geothermal activities, as well as the environmental and safety standards that must be met.

Metal ores in general are 'free to mine' ('bergfrei'), but require a mining license by the government (MinLex 2017). The same applies to geothermal resources, which also belong to the land-owner (<https://www.360ee.at/energie-aus-der-tiefe-rechtliche-grundlagen-der-geothermie/>).

Drill-holes below 300 m depth require a license under the mineral resources act (MinroG) by the competent mining regulator. If water is to be extracted, this requires a license under the water resources act (WRG 1959), which also regulates the re-injection. If the amount extracted exceed 10^6 m³ annually, an environmental impact assessment is required per UVP-G.

The Renewable Energy Act (Erneuerbaren-Ausbau-Gesetz) promotes the development of renewable energy sources, including geothermal energy. It establishes the framework for feed-in tariffs, incentives, and subsidies for renewable energy projects, as well as the targets and objectives for the development of renewable energy in Austria.

Commercial use for the extraction of heat requires a license under the trade regulations (Gewerbeordnung 1994), if electricity is to be generated, the licenses are issued under the electricity trade and organisation act (Elektrizitätswirtschafts- und organisationsgesetz 2010, EIWOG). Combined heat and electricity projects are treated under the EIWOG 2010. In such licensing procedures also the necessary water resources licenses are issued.

It thus conceivable that this provides also a simple framework for the combined extraction of heat and metals.

At the regional level, each of Austria's nine states has its own laws and regulations governing geothermal exploration and production. These laws may impose additional requirements and standards for geothermal projects, such as zoning and land use regulations, and may also require consultation with local communities and stakeholders. While policy developments over the past couple of years signal a shift toward de-risking and promoting deep geothermal energy harvesting (<https://www.bmf.gv.at/themen/klimapolitik/tiefen-geothermie.html>), the June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

7.2 BELGIUM

Belgium is a Federal State composed of three Regions (Flanders, Wallonia, and Brussels). Following a constitutional reform in 1980 that increasingly divulges federal competencies to the regions, in 2013 the Federal Mining Law was suspended and the competencies for environment, energy and economy (including natural resources) came under regional jurisdiction. While there are different governing laws on permitting and extraction for Flanders and Wallonia, metal ores on the continental shelf are owned by the state and exploration and exploitation requires licenses (MinLex 2017). Deep geothermal systems fall mainly into the competences of the Regions.

In **Flanders** the 'Decree on deep subsurface' of 2009 and its implementation regulation of 2011 (<https://navigator.emis.vito.be/detail?wold=40324>) explicitly concern also the exploitation of geothermal energy. Flanders also has implemented in 2018 an insurance system against geological risks (Lagrou et al., 2019). Deep geothermal projects hence need an exploration/exploitation permit according to this Decree, as well as a (Flemish) environmental permit according to the 'Decree on the environmental permit' of 2014 (<https://navigator.emis.vito.be/detail?wold=63105>). Shallow geothermal projects only need an environmental permit. Geothermal projects (shallow and deep) in Flanders do not require any permit at federal level.

Currently, there is no law to claim a concession for exploring/exploiting ore deposits or (metallic) mineralisations. No such projects exist in Flanders at the moment, but in case there would, they would fall under regional competence (i.e. natural resources). In practice, at this moment only an environmental permit would be needed for such projects (as is the case for quarries or clay and sand pits).

For metal extraction from geothermal brines, it appears (pers. comm) that regulators currently take the approach that they are inevitable 'by-products' from the exploitation of geothermal energy (Decree on the Deep Subsurface, article 63/8 §1), i.e. they fall under the exploration/exploitation license for geothermal projects. If in the future projects would be developed with a main focus on metal extraction from the brine a new regulation would be needed.

In **Wallonia** the legal framework evolves in the same direction, with a new project decree for underground resources management and a similar insurance system (Valkering et al. 2020). The Décret relatif à la gestion des ressources du sous-sol (<https://environnement.wallonie.be/legis/Codeenvironnement/codesoussoledecret.html>) has been adopted on 14 March 2024 and specifically includes deep geothermal resources (Section 4), but does not consider explicitly combined extraction. According to the Website of government of Wallonia, the processes for the application of the new mining legislation is still under revision (<https://www.wallonie.be/en/demarches/applying-grant-transfer-merger-rent-or-lease-mining-concessions#endetail>). It is interesting to note that 'fracking' is prohibited in the case of hydrocarbon exploitation, but explicitly permitted for deep geothermal systems.

However, for such projects also a Permis d'environnement according to the decree of 11 March 1999 (https://environnement.wallonie.be/legis/pe/PE001.htm?gad_source=1&gbraid=0AAAAA-BK1fbAuBWJw4J6mX76N_eYnmEdl&gclid=CjwKCAjwvr--BhB5EiwAd5YbXg9wuUbWsfyLLJ9NwT77z1IVEueEfyZ5TPrfUDPai3ULBFbPYLBVcxoCcongQAvD_BwE) will

be required. Further, if the produced waters are to be reinjected, a Water Use and Discharge Permit under the federal Code de l'eau of 12 February 2009 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/bel227524.pdf>) will be required.

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

7.3 BULGARIA

All underground ore resources are state owned and exploration and exploitation requires licenses. Mining in Bulgaria is regulated by the Concessions Act (SG No. /36/2.05.2006, <https://www.me.government.bg/en/files/download?hash=e357b9ee3f401efbee64d6a3995ac311a49da805>) and the Subsurface Resources Act (No. 23/12.03.1999, <https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/bul155639.pdf>). However, this Act explicitly does not apply to geothermal waters and the energy contained therein. The Law on Renewable Energy of 2011 (<https://lex.bg/laws/ldoc/2135728864>) has been last amended 18 February 2025 and now mentions geothermal resources.

Other laws of relevance for permitting procedures include the Waste Management Act (53/13.07.2012); the Environmental Protection Act, the Nature Protection Act; the Protected Areas Act (133/11.11.1998); the Act for the protection of the environment (SG 91/25.09.2002, <https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/bul52883.pdf>); the Water Act (67/27.07.1999, <https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/bul33607.pdf>), which also concerns groundwater in geothermal activities, as well as the requirements for monitoring and reporting of groundwater usage; the Law on Biological Diversity (SG/77/09.08.2002, <https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/bul154432.pdf>); and the Protected Areas Act (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/bul67271.pdf>) among others. Bulgaria has a centralised regime where all licenses for all kind of commodities are processed after a written application to the Ministry of Energy (<https://www.me.government.bg/en>). Other relevant co-authorities are the Ministry of Environment and Waters (<https://www.moew.government.bg>) and the Regional Inspectorates on Environment and Water, which coordinate the environmental permitting with the Ministry of Environment. Permits for exploration are granted by the Ministry of Energy upon approval by the Council of Ministers or for the continental shelf and the EEZ by the Council of Ministers (MinLex 2017).

Bulgaria appears to have considerable geothermal potential: <https://www.bage.bg/geothermal-bulgaria>.

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

7.4 CROATIA

All underground ore resources are state owned and exploration and exploitation requires licenses. Croatia has a centralised permitting regime (MinLex 2017).

According to Orkustofnun & EIHP (2017), geothermal waters belong to the mining or mineral resources of the Republic of Croatia and are described in the Mining Act (OG NN 56/13, 14/14, <https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/cro138122.pdf>) as “geothermal waters” that can be used for the accumulation of heat for energy purposes. Geothermal waters that are used for medical, biological and recreational purposes are regulated by the Water Act (OG 153/09, 130/11, 56/13, 14/14, <https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/cro216398.pdf>).

Croatia has a centralised permitting regime and the authorities involved include the Ministry of Economy (issues permits/licenses for exploration and extraction, <http://www.javnabava.hr/>), the Ministry of Environmental and Nature Protection (determines specific conditions, restrictions and consent, impact assessment, <https://mingor.gov.hr/>), the Ministry of Construction and Physical Planning (spatial planning documents necessary to start the procedure for granting a concession, <https://mpgi.gov.hr/>), the Ministry of Finance (provides financial and legal documents necessary to start the procedure for granting a concession, <https://mfin.gov.hr/>) and the Ministry of Agriculture (determines specific conditions relating to exploration and exploitation of mineral resources in forests, water management and agricultural land, <https://poljoprivreda.gov.hr/>).

For the exploitation of mineral resources, a concession is needed for the economic use of a common good according to the Act on Concessions. Concessions for exploitation are given on the basis of a public procurement using a bidding procedure.

Orkustofnun & EIHP (2017) detail the procedure for obtaining an exploitation license and this includes an Environmental Impact Study (EIS). According to the Environmental Protection Act (OG 80/13, 153/13, 78/15, <https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/cro170097.pdf>), before submitting a Request for Determining Environmental Impact a Request for giving instructions on the content of an environmental impact study is made. An EIS is an integral part of a Request for Determining Environmental Impact.

In 2025 amendments to the Renewable Energy Sources Act (RESA, https://narodne-novine.nn.hr/clanci/sluzbeni/2025_05_78_1017.html), along with updates to the Water Act, Underground Resources Act, and Spatial Planning Act, were enacted. Deep geothermal was newly defined as a mineral resource, now regulated under the Underground Resources Act. Permitting was unified: one single authority (Minister of Energy) issues permits for geothermal, replacing dual regimes.

7.5 CYPRUS

Cyprus is one of the EU countries with the longest metal mining history, going back to before the Bronze Age, but there is very little metal mining today.

Cyprus can be considered as a poor country regarding the availability of geothermal resources, since it is located in an inactive tectonic area with no high- or low- enthalpy resources (<http://europeangeothermalcongress.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/07/CUR-07-Cyprus.pdf>).

All underground ore resources are state owned and exploration and exploitation requires licenses and a centralised permitting regime is in place (MinLex 2017).

The legislative framework for the mineral sector in Cyprus is provided by the Mines and Quarries Law of 1965 as amended in 1995, 2001, and 2003 ([https://www.moa.gov.cy/moa/mines/minesSrv.nsf/All/CF7BCA66EE5FDBCDC22574B90035C157/\\$file/Mines%20and%20Quarries%20\(Regulation\)%20Law.pdf](https://www.moa.gov.cy/moa/mines/minesSrv.nsf/All/CF7BCA66EE5FDBCDC22574B90035C157/$file/Mines%20and%20Quarries%20(Regulation)%20Law.pdf)). The Mines Service is the competent authority of the administration of the Mines and Quarries Law and Regulation and the Explosive Substances Law and Regulation ([https://www.moa.gov.cy/moa/mines/minesSrv.nsf/All/C41AB897D6FD4079C22574B20039F5FE/\\$file/Annual%20Report%202018.pdf](https://www.moa.gov.cy/moa/mines/minesSrv.nsf/All/C41AB897D6FD4079C22574B20039F5FE/$file/Annual%20Report%202018.pdf)).

A Town-planning Permit by the Department of Town Planning and Housing is a pre-required document to apply for a Mining Lease or a Quarry Licence

(https://www.moi.gov.cy/moi/tph/tph.nsf/home_en/home_en?openform#). Likewise an Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) study is required according to national law of 2005 on Environmental Impact Assessment from Certain Plans and/or Programmes Law 102(I)/2005 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/cyp87147.pdf>), which seems to mirror the respective EU Directive 2001/42/EC (CEU, 2001).

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

7.6 CZECHIA

All underground ore resources are state owned and exploration and exploitation requires licenses. Mining legislation in the Czech Republic distinguishes between “reserved” minerals, which are state-owned, and “non-reserved” minerals (or deposits) which are owned by the landowner. All minerals, with the exception of building stone, gravel, and clays are “reserved” minerals.

The primary legal basis of mineral extraction activity is the Mining Law (Mining Act) No. 44 of 1988, as amended by Law No. 186 of 2006 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/cze126493.pdf>). For prospecting and exploration for reserved mineral deposits the most relevant law is the one No. 62/1988 Coll., on Geological Work (the Geological Act) as amended. Other important national Acts are the Act on the Environment (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/cze4757.pdf>), the Water Act (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/cze124878.pdf>), the EIA Act (https://www.mzp.cz/en/environmental_impact_assessment). In the field of exploration of mineral deposits, the Ministry of Environment is the most important authority, i.e. the Ministry lays down the exploration areas. In the sphere of exploitation, the District Mining Authorities are the most important state bodies. The District Mining Authorities (eight in total) are part of the State Mining Administration (SMA), which is composed also by the Czech Mining Office in Prague (central mining authority), establishing a centralised permitting regime.

The Energy Act (<https://www.fao.org/faolex/results/details/en/c/LEX-FAOC067101>) also discussed geothermal energy sources. The government commissioned a study on the geothermal potential that was completed in 2022 (<https://www.mpo.cz/en/energy/research-and-development-in-energy-sector/ongoing-completed-projects-and-their-results/analysis-of-the-geothermal-energy-potential-at-medium-and-large-depths-in-the-czech-republic-on-the-basis-of-available-data--260656/>, https://mapy.geology.cz/geotermalni_potencial/#). The ownership and use of deep geothermal resources appeared to be unregulated as of 2014 (Dumas et al. 2014), but it is not clear, whether this still is the case.

With respect to exploitation, the District Mining Authorities are the most important state bodies. The eight Authorities are part of the State Mining Administration (SMA), which includes also by Czech Mining Office in Prague, thus establishing a centralised permitting regime. (MinLex 2017).

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

7.7 DENMARK

All land-based mineral resources belong to the landowner, while off-shore resources belong to the state (MinLex 2017).

The production of geothermal energy is governed by the Subsoil Act and a licence is required for both the exploration for and production of geothermal energy. Licences are provided through a tender by the Danish Environment Agency (DEA). Licences are usually awarded as a sole concession for the applied-for area. Exploration licences last for six years but can be extended for 10 years. Production licenses have a duration of 30 years, but will be limited to the area from which the geothermal energy is actually extracted and will not cover the entire area for which originally an exploration license was initially applied (<https://www.thinkgeoenergy.com/denmark-and-geothermal-district-heating-legal-framework-risk-and-current-development/>).

This seems to imply that it is the landowner's decision to permit the extraction of metal from geothermal energy systems.

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above, however, policy decisions led to a more favourable investment climate in deep systems.

7.8 ESTONIA

All underground ore resources are state owned and exploration and exploitation requires licenses under the Mining Act of 2003 (MinLex 2017). The main responsible authority for mining permitting is the Ministry of Environment (for mineral deposit of national importance), otherwise it is the Environmental Board.

The primary legal basis of mineral extraction activities is the Earth's Crust Act (<https://www.riigiteataja.ee/en/eli/507012019007/consolide>). The main responsible authority for mining permitting is Environmental Board (<https://keskkonnaamet.ee/>). The Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communications (<https://www.mkm.ee/>) is advised (in a non-binding way) by the Commission of Mineral Resources on issues of exploration and exploitation of mineral resources, validation of mineral reserves, among other topics. Supervision and monitoring are conducted by the Environmental Inspectorate (under the Ministry of Climate, <https://kliimaministeerium.ee/>). According to the Earth's Crust Act, holders of an exploration or extraction permit have to ensure that the plans for mining are prepared and the mining operations are conducted under the conditions set by the exploration or extraction permit.

The Water Act (https://www.riigiteataja.ee/en/compare_original/506072023011) permits the discharge of used geothermal waters back into the geological body from which it was taken, but this presumably concerns only shallow systems.

According to the Estonian Geothermal Association (EGA, <http://geothermal.org.ee/eng/>) to date very limited work on deeper resources has been undertaken and no information on the legal basis for exploration and exploitation has been found.

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

7.9 FINLAND

All ores are under the jurisdiction of the state, but royalties go to the landowners (MinLex 2017).

Currently there is no legislation in force for permitting geothermal projects (Hannonen, 2020) and there is a debate, whether these should fall under the building or the environmental regulations. The 2011 Mining Act <https://www.finlex.fi/api/media/>

[statute-foreign-language-translation/124987/mainPdf/main.pdf?timestamp=2011-06-10T00%3A00%3A00.000Z](https://www.finlex.fi/en/laki/kaannokset/2011/en20110610T00%3A00%3A00.000Z), including amendments up to 2023) does not mention any geothermal resources or their use, neither does the Environmental Protection Act (https://www.finlex.fi/en/laki/kaannokset/2014/en20140527_20200905.pdf), nor the Water Act (<https://www.finlex.fi/en/laki/kaannokset/2011/en20110587.pdf>), or the Land-Use and Building Act (https://www.finlex.fi/en/laki/kaannokset/1999/en19990132_20030222.pdf).

Owing to the shallow geothermal gradient in the Fennoscandian bedrock, only ultra-deep (> 6000 m) systems seem to be of interest, although medium deep systems are also being explored (<https://www.egt.ee/media/439/download>).

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

7.10 FRANCE

All underground ore resources are state owned and exploration and exploitation requires licenses (MinLex 2017).

The Geothermal Transparency Guide (<http://www.geothermal.bba.is>) states, that under French law, in principle, ownership of a plot of land includes the ownership of what is above and below such plot of land (Article 552 of the Code Civil, https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/codes/article_lc/LEGIARTI000006428953). As an exception, the exploration and exploitation of geothermal resources are subject to restrictive legislation (contained in the Mining Code). Exploitation of geothermal resources is subject to license in compliance with the Mining Code and Decree No. 78-498 dated 28 March 1978 (<https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/loda/id/LEGISCTA000041414462>). For high temperature resources, exploration and exploitation are subject to general mining licenses granted in principle by the prime minister or the minister for mines (Decree No. 2006-648 dated 2 June 2006, <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/loda/id/JORFTEXT000000790913>).

For high temperature geothermal resources (>150°C) (Decree No. 2006-648 dated 2 June 2006) an exclusive exploration permit (permis exclusif de recherches – PER) is required that contains *inter alia* an environmental impact statement (notice d'impact) indicating (i) potential impacts of the works on the environment and (ii) how the contemplated project includes environmental concerns. The consent of the respective land-owner to use the site is required.

Numerous administrative bodies are likely to be involved – such as:

- The Minister in charge of mines (i.e. currently the Ministre de la transition écologique et solidaire and the Ministre de l'économie et des finances) is the recipient of the application;
- The local representative of the State (préfet) examines the application form and organises the tender procedure;
- The heads of the interested civil and military services (chefs des services civils et de l'autorité militaire intéressés) are consulted;
- The regional environment, planning and housing agency (la direction régionale de l'environnement, de l'aménagement et du logement – DREAL) drafts a report;
- The municipalities concerned are consulted;

- The general council for the economy, the industry, the energy and the technologies (Conseil général de l'économie, de l'industrie, de l'énergie et des technologies) submits its opinion on the project.
- As far as the concession permit is concerned, the opinion of the Council of State (Conseil d'Etat) is also required, and the permit is delivered by the Prime Minister (Article 31 of the Decree No. 2006-648 dated 2 June 2006).

With effect of January 2023 the Mining Code was revised, integrating the mining permits with the environmental permits to allow for a streamlined procedure and ensure cohesive monitoring of the activities (Décret n° 2023-13 du 11 janvier 2023 relatif à l'autorisation environnementale des travaux miniers, <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/jorf/id/JORFTEXT000046971943>). Geothermal projects are explicitly mentioned therein. This also means that only one application is made to cover both mining and pollution control aspects (MTECT, 2023).

Water management is the subject of a framework for water planning and management (Schéma Directeur d'Aménagement et de Gestion des Eaux (SDAGE)). The SDAGE must be taken into account in any administrative decision, meaning that all mining authorisations would need to have regard to the scheme in accordance with the Environmental Code. The relationship between the mining permit and the SDAGE was clarified and confirmed with this New Mining Code (<https://codes.droit.org/PDF/Code%20de%20%27environnement.pdf>).

While France actively supports the development of deep geothermal projects, there have been no changes to the regulatory system by June 2025.

7.11 GERMANY

Regional mining authorities are competent for issuing licenses for the use of geothermal resources, such as exploration licenses (Aufsuchungserlaubnis), exploitation licenses (Gewinnungsbewilligung) or mining property rights (Bergwerkseigentum) (see below). In detail, the provisions regarding the competence depend on the federal state. Prior to making a decision on the application, the competent mining authority shall ensure that the authorities responsible for safeguarding the public interest are given the opportunity to express their opinion. For research activities on the continental shelf the Federal Maritime and Hydrographic Agency (Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie – BSH) has to be involved (EGEC 2022).

According to the German mining law (BBergG, <https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/bbergg/>) geothermal heat is not a mineral resource and, therefore, not controlled by this law. Shallow geothermal boreholes that serve only the need of the buildings on the plot on which they are located do not require a license. However, drilling below 100 m depth for commercial purposes, namely the extraction of mineral value or heat for electricity generation or district heating, requires a license (Frenz 2020). An impact assessment per Immission Law (BlmSchG, <https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/bimschg/BlmSchG.pdf>) is likely to be required, in particular also for the re-injection of abstracted waters. The later would also be regulated under the Water Management Act (WHG, <https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/bimschg/BlmSchG.pdf>).

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

7.12 GREECE

All 'metallic' minerals are state owned and exploration and exploitation requires licenses. The Greek Legislation (the Mining Code, namely L.210/1973) distinguishes mineral raw materials into two broad categories: a) 'Metallic Minerals' which, either on the surface or underground, do not belong to the landowner, and b) 'Quarry Minerals', which belong to the landowner (Tzeferis, 2018). 'Metallic Minerals' include (native) metals, all metallic compounds, precious stones, radioactive and energy minerals, sulphur, talc, fluoride, asbestos, dolomites with MgO content >21 %, feldspars, mineral salt, organic sediments, and others, as well as those 'Quarry Minerals' that may be treated in order to produce 'Metallic Minerals'. At the national level, the Ministry of Environment and Energy (YPEN) and, at the regional/local level, the 7 Decentralised (Regional) Administrations (tiers of ministries) and the 13 Administrative Regions (L.3852/2010) are concerned with issuing permits. Who issues which permit depends on the mineral type, size of the project/activity, any land use peculiarities of the area of intervention (i.e. frontier area, protected area), or/and the land ownership legal status (MinLex 2017).

The use of geothermal energy is regulated by the law on *Exploitation of Geothermal Potential* (Law 1475/84). This law asserts that the exclusive right of exploitation of geothermal energy belongs to the state, which, in turn, reserves the right to assign this to other public sector entities. In such cases, these entities have to prove the benefits of such investments. It must be assured that water quality will not be affected and rights cannot be undertaken for less than 15 years (<https://www.iea.org/policies/3971-exploitation-of-geothermal-potential-law-147584>).

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

7.13 HUNGARY

All minerals are state owned and exploration and exploitation requires licenses (MinLex 2017). Thermal waters and geothermal energy are also state owned and covered by the Mining Act (Valkering et al. 2020).

The primary legal basic of mineral extraction activity is Act No. XLVIII of 1993 on Mining (https://rmis.jrc.ec.europa.eu/uploads/legislation/Hungary_MiningAct_ENGLISH.pdf).

Important pieces of law for permitting procedures are Governmental Decree No. 203/1998. (XII.19.) (detailed permitting rules), Government Regulation No. 161/2017. (VI. 28.) on the Mining and Geological Survey of Hungary (MBFSZ), Government Regulation No. 53/2012 on mining construction permitting (<https://net.jogtar.hu/jogszabaly?docid=A1200312.KOR>), Government Regulation No. 314/2005 on EIA and IPPC (<https://net.jogtar.hu/jogszabaly?docid=A0500314.KOR>), Act No. LIII of 1996 on nature conservation (<https://net.jogtar.hu/jogszabaly?docid=99600053.TV>), Government Regulation No. 275/2004 on Natura 2000 sites (<https://net.jogtar.hu/jogszabaly?docid=A0400275.KOR>), and Government Regulation No. 312/2012 on construction permitting (<https://net.jogtar.hu/jogszabaly?docid=A1200312.KOR>). For permitting procedures, Act No. CL of 2016 on the General Order on Administration is also important (<https://net.jogtar.hu/jogszabaly?docid=A0400140.TV×hift=20170101&xtreferer=A1100190.TV>).

Environmental impact assessments fall under the Governmental Decree No. 314/2005 (XII.25.) regarding the procedures of environmental impact assessment and the single procedure of authorization of utilization of the environment (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/hun109029.pdf>). Water-related matters are regulated under the Act No. LVII of 1995 on water management (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/hun5203.pdf>).

Hungary has a considerable geothermal potential (<https://www.ceer.eu/documents/104400/-/-/c1f4719e-55bb-2141-c234-cacc411dba6e>) All issues related to geothermal energy fall into the remit of the water (resources) regulators (Regional Directorates for Disaster Management) if above 2500 m depths, while concessions for resources below that depth are issued by the mining regulator (https://mbfsz.gov.hu/ogre_modul/data/licensing_pdfs/Annex4.pdf). Recent legislation puts high priority on geothermal power production without water abstraction and improvement of reinjection technologies, and also addresses the mitigation of financial risks of geothermal investment (Valkering et al. 2020).

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

7.14 ICELAND

The Geothermal Transparency Guide (<http://www.geothermal.bba.is>) observes that ownership of natural resources, including geothermal, is governed by the Act on the survey and utilisation of ground resources no. 57/1998 ('Natural Resources Act', <https://www.government.is/media/atvinnuvegaraduneyti-media/media/acts/Act-No-57-1998-on-survey-and-utilisation-of-ground-resources.pdf>). The ownership of resources in the ground is attached to private land. Resources under public land are the property of the state. Resources are defined in the Natural Resources Act as “any element, compound and energy that can be extracted from the earth, whether in solid, liquid or gaseous form, regardless of the temperature at which they may be found”.

The National Energy Authority (NEA) is permitted to take the initiative in and/or give instructions for the exploration of resources in the ground anywhere in Iceland, regardless of whether the owner of the land has initiated such exploration or permitted others to initiate such exploration. In the same way, the NEA may permit other private or public parties to explore, in which case an exploration license shall be issued to such other parties. If, however, the landowner holds a valid exploration license, the NEA cannot interfere, and the landowner can either explore himself or allow third parties to explore, without interference from the NEA. A landowner is required to grant exploration license holders unrestricted access to the private land involved.

The utilisation of resources is subject to a license from the NEA, whether on private or public land. This license permits the holder to extract and use the resource during the term of the license to the extent and on the terms laid down in the Natural Resources Act. Before the NEA issues a utilisation license, the opinions of certain administrative bodies shall be gathered. This includes the opinion of the Environment Agency of Iceland, the Icelandic Institute of Natural History, the Marine and Freshwater Research Institute, if applicable, as well as the opinion of the local municipality.

The Icelandic Master Plan for Nature Protection and Energy Utilisation (“Master Plan”) is a tool to reconcile often competing interests on a national scale and at the earliest planning stages. The Master Plan is currently in its fourth phase, which was due to be completed in

2021. All work on the Master Plan focuses on classifying power plant options into energy utilisation-, on hold-, or protection categories. Expert committees established under the Master Plan demarcate the area of impact for the planned power plant construction work and evaluate the value of numerous factors within the area by use of a rating system based on the conditions of the area pre-power plant.

The Master Plan involves to a certain extent innovation and when the work on the plan began there was no fully formulated methodology available that would suit Icelandic conditions. The methodology has therefore gone through continuous development and will probably continue to undergo some adjustments, although most of these will probably be minor.

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

7.15 IRELAND

All underground ore resources are state owned and exploration and exploitation requires licenses (MinLex 2017).

The fundamental law is the Minerals development Act of 2017 (<http://www.mineralsireland.ie/files/MineralsDevelopmentAct2017.pdf>), which, however, does not mention geothermal waters.

It appears that the assessment by Dumas et al. (2014) is still correct and that there are no specific legal controls on geothermal energy development and ownership of the resource is unregulated. According to EGEN (2022) non-specific regulations influences the geothermal activity:

Planning permission (according to The Planning and Development Acts 2000/2021, <https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/2021/act/18/enacted/en/pdf>) is needed for any building associated with the geothermal system and it may be needed for deep drilling.

Mineral exploration boreholes need to be drilled under a license granted by the Exploration and Mining Division (EMD) of the Department of Communications, Marine and Natural Resources

Open loop systems need a Discharge License from the Environmental Protection Agency, especially since deeper systems may produce brines.

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

7.16 ITALY

All underground ore resources are state owned and exploration and exploitation requires licenses (MinLex 2017). Specifically, the Geothermal Transparency Guide (<http://www.geothermal.bba.is>) states, that ownership of natural resources, including geothermal, is governed by the Italian Civil Code

(<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/ita197336.pdf>).

Namely Article 826, para. 2, provides that: "The forests that by applicable laws constitute the forested domain of the State, mines, quarries and turf pits when their disposability is taken from the owner of the land [...] are part of the non-disposable patrimony of the State".

Article 840, para. 1, provides that: "Ownership of the soil extends to the subsoil, with all that is contained therein, and the owner can perform any excavation or work that does

not cause harm to a neighbour. This provision does not apply to that which is the object of laws on mines, quarries and turf pits [...]”.

Article 1, para. 6, of Legislative Decree No. 22/2010 (<https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/gu/2010/02/24/45/sg/pdf>), provides that geothermal resources qualify as mineral resources that fall under the non-disposable patrimony of the Italian State or of the relevant region depending on the national or local interest of such resources. Only the government of Italy can grant exploitation rights.

The exploitation of geothermal resources is subject to a specific license. Article 6 of Legislative Decree No. 22/2010 of 11 February 2010 (https://www.astrid-online.it/static/upload/protected/Dlgs/Dlgs_22_2010.pdf) sets out the procedure to obtain a license, which entails the involvement of all the authorities concerned (e.g. the Ministry for the Environment, Land and Sea, the Ministry of Economic Development and the local authorities). The license also includes the final approval of the works programme and the geothermal project.

According to article 1, § 7 of Decree No. 22/2010, the administrative bodies involved in the licensing of geothermal resources are the Regions or other entities delegated by the former which are entitled also to carry out monitoring and surveillance activities.

The protection of geothermal energy resources is provided for by Article 5 of the Legislative Decree 181/2023 (<https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/gu/2023/12/09/287/sg/pdf>).

Landowners cannot object against licenses, but the authorities will take note of any opposition and may amend the project in question. Finally, pursuant to Article 15 of Legislative Decree No. 22/2010, the works necessary for the exploration and the exploitation of geothermal resources qualify as public utility, and, therefore an expropriation procedure under Presidential Decree No. 327/2001 can take place, if necessary.

The Regions (Reggione) of Italy also have considerable regulatory power. Thus, the Regional laws of Tuscany and Lazio establish the regulatory framework for geothermal activities in these regions, which are home to most of Italy's geothermal power plants. These laws establish the requirements for environmental permits, as well as the requirements for the protection of local communities and the environment.

While the Legge 8 agosto 2024, n. 115 (<https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/id/2024/08/13/24G00131/SG>) did not fundamentally change the regulatory regime, it implements some of the stipulations of the EU CRMA (CRMA, 2024), namely the acceleration of permitting processes for critical raw materials extraction. No further changes were detected by June 2025.

7.17 LATVIA

██████████ All onshore mineral resources belong to the landowner, who might be the State, local authorities, private individuals, or legal entities. The State has the right to limit the rights of legal and physical entities regarding the land and the subsoil belonging to them by imposing the limitations of the right to use the property (MinLex 2017).

The Law on Subterranean Depths (with amendment up to 2021, <https://likumi.lv/ta/en/en/id/40249>) regulates the extraction of underground resources including minerals and water. However, this law does not mention geothermal energy systems. Environmental Impact Assessment are regulated by the law of 14.10.1998 (with amendments up to 2023,

<https://likumi.lv/ta/en/en/id/51522>). Cabinet Regulation No. 696 of 6 September 2011 on the Procedure for the Issue of Licences for the Use of Subterranean Depths and Authorisations for the Extraction of Widespread Mineral Resources (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/lat174595.pdf>) also regulates the extraction of groundwaters, but does not specifically mention the utilisation of (deep) geothermal waters.

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

7.18 LITHUANIA

All underground ore resources are state owned and exploration and exploitation requires licenses (MinLex 2017).

The main law is the Underground Law No. I-1034/1995 (<https://e-seimas.lrs.lt/portal/legalAct/lt/TAD/TAIS.29464?jfwid=bkaxlrq2>) and its implementing Government Resolutions (No. 1433/2001, No. 198/2002, No. 584/2002), which regulate the exploration and extraction permits. Other important laws regulating necessary permits and licences for the authorisation of exploration and extraction activities include the Environment Protection Law I-2223/1992 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/lit4748E.pdf>), the Environmental Impact Assessment Law No. XIII-595/2017 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/lit181537.pdf>), the Protected Areas Law No. I-301/1993 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/lit180792.pdf>), the Water Law No. VIII-474/1997 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/lit41412.pdf>), and the Spatial Planning Law No. I-1120/1995 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/lit19457.pdf>).

There are no regulations covering deep geothermal systems. The Law on Energy from Renewable Sources No. XI-1375 of 12 May 2011 (<https://e-seimas.lrs.lt/portal/legalAct/lt/TAD/648259603c3b11e68f278e2f1841c088?jfwid=rivwzvpvg>) is more of a policy document. The statement that systems of less than 30 kW do not require a license, implicates that industrial scale systems do, but no more details are laid down in this legislation.

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

7.19 LUXEMBOURG

According to MinLex (2017) the main legislation governing permitting procedures for extraction is the law of 21 April 1810 (last amended in 1994,

https://www.stradalex.lu/fr/slu_src_publ_leg_mema/toc/leg_lu_mema_181001_2/doc/mema_1810A000Z), the law of 10 June 1999 relative to the classification of potentially dangerous establishments (<https://www.legilux.public.lu/eli/etat/leg/loi/1999/06/10/n5/jo>, amended by Grand Ducal regulation of 10 May 2012) which classifies the extractive industry as 'class 1' and makes it subject to an 'authorisation to operate' procedure following an investigation procedure called "commodo-incommodo". Other important laws are the amended law of 19 December 2008 on water (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/lux84420.pdf>) and the Law of 19 January 2004 on the conservation of nature and natural resources (<https://www.legilux.public.lu/eli/etat/leg/loi/2004/01/19/n1/jo>). Relevant authorities are the Ministry of Labour, Employment and Social and Solidarity Economy (<https://mteess.gouvernement.lu/fr.html>) and the Ministry of Sustainable Development and Infrastructure (<https://mecdd.gouvernement.lu/fr.htm>)

which are the competent authorities for issuing the “authorisation to operate” supported by its Inspectorate of Labour and Mines (ITM, <https://itm.public.lu/fr.html>).

Geothermal drilling permits define the development and operating conditions deemed necessary to protect the environment and ensure the safety of workers, the public and the environment in general (<https://guichet.public.lu/en/entreprises/sectoriel/construction/forages-geothermiques.html>). Geothermal drilling permit applications must be submitted to the Environment Agency (Administration de l'environnement, <https://aev.gouvernement.lu/fr.html>). The Water Management Authority (<https://eau.gouvernement.lu/fr.html>) has established a detailed map, that lists the areas where drilling is not permitted and those which are subject to restrictions in terms of drilling depth <https://map.geoportail.lu/theme/eau>). An application for a class 1 classified establishment operating permit (see above), a water permit, and an environmental impact assessment are needed.

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

7.20 MALTA

 It appears that the geothermal energy sources of Malta are unexplored despite their potential. Malta lies on stretched continental crust which should result in a high geothermal gradient (Gatt et al., 2022). According to MinLex (2017) there are mainly quarrying activities on this island made up largely from limestone. The mineral extraction sector is regulated by the Mineral Resources Act (<https://legislation.mt/eli/cap/423/20150731/eng>), the Environment Protection Act (<https://legislation.mt/eli/cap/549/20230721/eng>), the Development Planning Act (<https://legislation.mt/eli/cap/552/20230526/eng>) when it comes to mineral extraction, extensions to existing quarries and remediation of disused quarries, and the Cultural Heritage Act (<https://legislation.mt/eli/cap/445/eng/pdf>). Legislation of indirect importance to which operations might be subject to includes the Land Acquisition Ordinance (<https://legislation.mt/eli/cap/88/20170425/eng>), the Strategic Environmental Assessment Regulations (<https://legislation.mt/eli/sl/549.61/eng/pdf>) and the Continental Shelf Act (<https://legislation.mt/eli/cap/194/20140808/eng>).

The Subsidiary Legislation 545.35 on the Promotion of Energy from Renewable Sources Regulations (<https://legislation.mt/eli/sl/545.35/eng>) does mention geothermal energy, but does not provide any specific regulations for its extraction.

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

7.21 THE NETHERLANDS

 State-owned minerals include off-shore minerals (shells, gravel, sand and clay of the Continental Shelf – Art. §4b Excavation Act) and on-shore non-surface minerals (e.g., salt). On-shore surface minerals (e.g., construction minerals) belong to the landowner (MinLex, 2017). An amendment to the Mining Act (Minebouwwet), which only applies to minerals resources below 100 m depth, came into force on 01.01.24 and now also includes deep geothermal resources below 500 m depth (Article 2.2, <https://wetten.overheid.nl/BWBR0014168/2024-01-01>). As Article 21.n also makes provisions for using old mine-works for the extraction of heat, one could conclude

that this would apply also to combined extraction. Chapter 2a of this law regulates the permission procedures for geothermal exploration and exploitation projects.

The State Supervision of Mines (SSM) is the agency within the Ministry of Economic Affairs that oversees the production of minerals and Netherlands' continental shelf. The agency is responsible for enforcing mining laws, mine safety, and mineral production regulations on and offshore. Netherlands has a mixed (centralised-decentralised) permitting regime in which the SSM grants the exploration and extraction permits, and the Ministry of Infrastructure and Environment grants the environmental and water extraction permits; however, the consent of the provincial governments is also mandatory whereas the municipalities and local water authorities only provide consultative (legally non-binding) opinions (MinLex 2017).

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

7.22 POLAND

The State is the owner of all on- and off-shore deposits of metal ores (with the exception of bog iron ores), native metals, native sulphur, rock salt, potassium salt, potassium-magnesium salt, gypsum and anhydrite, as well as gemstones (§10.1 of the Geological and Mining Law of 09.11.21, <https://isap.sejm.gov.pl/isap.nsf/DocDetails.xsp?id=wdu20111630981>). §10.2 specifies that thermal waters also are state property, while deposits of other minerals (e.g. sand and gravel, limestone, dolomite) belong to the landowner (Art. §10.3). In order to receive a prospecting or exploration licence, an environmental permit is needed (cf. Environmental Protection Law of 29.09.21, <https://isap.sejm.gov.pl/isap.nsf/DocDetails.xsp?id=WDU20210001973>). The Water Law of 16.09.23 regulates the discharge of abstracted thermal waters and brines, but does not seem to regulate their abstraction as such (<https://isap.sejm.gov.pl/isap.nsf/DocDetails.xsp?id=WDU20230001478>).

The competent authority is the Regional Director for Environmental Protection in the case of state-owned minerals — excluding medicinal waters, thermal waters and brines — and in case of investments located at the maritime areas of the Republic of Poland. Mining licences are granted by the Minister of the Environment for state-owned minerals, but the exact procedure and other authorities involved depends on the likely impact of the proposed mining operation (MinLex 2017).

In Poland, there is no uniform regulation directly dedicated to investments and projects related to the use of geothermal energy. The legal environment of these investments is shaped in particular by sector-specific environmental regulations, conditioned by the level of interference in particular environmental resources (minerals, water), and horizontal regulations, relating to the comprehensive regulation of environmental protection as such (environmental protection law, impact assessment) as well as administrative regulations on investment and construction process in general (construction law, spatial planning regulations) (Szalewska 2021).

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

7.23 PORTUGAL

Land- and mineral rights are covered by the Decree-Law No. 47344 of 1966 and amended up to 10.01.22, approving the Civil Code and regulating its application (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/por210029.pdf>). The primary legal basis for the extraction of state-owned minerals (metals and industrial minerals) is currently Law No. 54/2015 (<https://diariodarepublica.pt/dr/detalhe/lei/54-2015-67552498>). The Portuguese national mining authority for state-owned minerals is DGEG (under the Ministry of Economy) which acts as a 'one-stop shop' for mining permits in the exploration, extraction and post-extraction phases. Extraction (mining) activities are subject to a mandatory EIA to be evaluated by both National Environmental Institutions, the Portuguese Environmental Agency (APA) and the Regional Coordination and Development Commissions (CCDR), as well as the Geological Institutions of DGEG and LNEG (National Laboratory of Energy and Geology), depending on the location, dimension and type of resource to be mined (MinLex. 2107).

The regulatory framework for geothermal wells is established under the legal framework of Decree-Law No. 34/2016, which transposed the European Directive on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources. Under this law, the use of geothermal energy in Portugal is subject to a licensing process, which includes obtaining the necessary permits and authorizations from the Directorate-General for Energy and Geology (DGEG), the National Water Authority (ANA), and the Environmental Agency (APA). Also Decree-Law No. 84/2022 of 09.12.22 on the consumption of renewable energy makes reference to geothermal energy.

Geothermal wells are classified according to the type of geothermal resource they use, with shallow geothermal energy systems (SGES) being those that extract geothermal energy from depths of up to 400 meters, and deep geothermal systems (DGS) being those that extract geothermal energy from greater depths.

The licensing process for geothermal wells typically involves a comprehensive technical and environmental assessment of the proposed well site, including the geological characteristics of the area, the potential impacts on local ecosystems, and the risk of contamination of the water table. The licensing process also requires compliance with health and safety regulations, including measures to prevent accidents, fire, and explosion. In addition to the licensing process, the regulatory framework also establishes specific requirements for the operation and maintenance of geothermal wells, including regular inspections, monitoring of environmental impacts, and reporting to relevant authorities.

Water- and environment-related acts are the Water Act No. 58/2005 of 09.12.05 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/por62080.pdf>), the Environment Basic Law No. 19/2014 of 14.04.14 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/por132791.pdf>), the Decree-Law No. 151-B/2013 establishing the legal regime of environmental impact assessment of 31.01.13 with amendments up to 11.12.17 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/por132059.pdf>), and the Decree-law No. 147/2008 regulating environmental damages' liability of 29.07.08 (<https://www.fao.org/faolex/results/details/en/c/LEX-FAOC081800>). The uses of off-shore geological resources are covered by the Decree-Law No. 38/2015 implementing Law No. 17/2014 establishing the Policy on the National Maritime Areas Planning and Management. (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/por147367.pdf>).

The re-review of June 2025 indicated no fundamental changes to the regulatory system, though Decree-Law 99-2024 of 3 December 2024 aims at shortening permitting times for renewable energy systems including deep geothermal systems to two years.

7.24 ROMANIA

All mineral resources (also including coal, mineral water, therapeutic muds and geothermal resources) and hydrocarbon resources are public property of the state (Art. §1 of the Mining Law no. 85/18.03.2003, <https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/rom73606E.pdf>) and are administered by the National Agency for Mineral Resources (NAMR). The Romanian regulatory system for permits/licences can involve a variety of regulatory bodies and up to 6 permits, licences or approvals may be necessary for both, exploration and exploitation. However, the regulatory climate in Romania in general has been in favour of extraction (MinLex 2017).

Geothermal resources are considered part of the country's mineral resources and are therefore owned by the state. The exploration, development, and exploitation of geothermal resources are subject to licensing and regulation by the National Agency for Mineral Resources (ANRM) and governed by several laws and regulations, including: Law no. 155/2020, supplementing law 123/2012 sets out the regulatory framework for the energy sector, including geothermal energy (<https://www.climate-laws.org/geographies/romania/laws/law-on-electrical-energy-and-natural-gases-no-123-2012-and-amending-laws-no-155-and-no-290>).

Government Emergency Ordinance no. 33/2007 on the organisation of the National Agency for Mineral Resources (ANRM, https://www.ceer.eu/documents/104400/6693346/C19_NR_Romania-EN-Summary.pdf/563d871e-a29e-9998-f847-c05137da019c)

establishes the procedures for obtaining permits and authorizations for the exploration and exploitation of geothermal resources. ANRM is responsible for issuing exploration and exploitation licenses for geothermal resources and is also responsible for monitoring compliance with the licenses and ensuring that environmental regulations are followed. The application for an exploration license must include information about the location of the proposed project, the estimated geothermal potential, and the proposed drilling and testing methods. ANRM will review the application and may request additional information.

If a viable geothermal resource has been identified, the developer must then apply for an exploitation license. This application will include more detailed information about the proposed project, including the expected energy output and environmental impact. ANRM will review the application and may require an environmental impact assessment (EIA) before issuing the license (Law no. 292/2018, https://unece.org/sites/default/files/2021-06/frPartyVI.8h_25.06.2021_annex2.pdf). If an EIA is required, the developer must submit a comprehensive report that describes the potential environmental impact of the project and any measures that will be taken to mitigate those impacts. The report must be reviewed and approved by the National Environmental Protection Agency (NEPA).

In addition to these permits, the developer may also need to obtain permits and approvals from other regulatory bodies, such as the local municipality, the National Water Agency (Administrația Națională Apele Române, <https://rowater.ro>), and the National Energy Regulatory Authority (Autoritatea Națională de Reglementare în domeniul Energiei, <https://anre.ro>).

The regulatory instruments of relevance are the Law No. 292 of 03.12.18 regarding the assessment of the impact of certain public and private projects on the environment (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/rom216015.pdf>), Emergency Ordinance no. 195 of 22 December 2005 on environmental protection (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/rom197188.pdf>), the Law No. 122/2020 amending and supplementing the Water Law (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/rom201282.pdf>).

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

7.25 SLOVAKIA

The legal framework relevant for permitting procedures comprises mainly the Mining Law (Law No. 44/1988 Coll.1 with amendments, <https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/slo43134.pdf>) and the Geological Law (Law No. 569/2007 Coll. with amendments). Other important laws are Law No. 543/2002 Coll. on nature and landscape protection, Law. No. 24/2006 Coll. on the environmental impact assessment (Law No. 39/2013 Coll., <https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/slo183193.pdf>) on integrated prevention and environmental pollution control, and the Water Law (Law No. 364/2004 Coll., <https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/slo182215.pdf>). Competent authorities are the Ministry of Environment of the Slovak Republic, Ministry of Economy of the Slovak Republic, Main Mining Office and the Regional (or District) Mining Offices.

According to the Mining Law No. 44/1988 and its amendments, mineralised waters used to produce 'reserved' minerals (e.g., metals) belong to the state (MinLex, 2017, p. 480), which seems to imply that a concession for combined extraction would be required (MinLex 2017).

In Slovakia, the permitting process for deep geothermal projects is governed by the Energy Efficiency Act (Act No. 321/2014 Coll., https://www.mfsr.sk/files/sk/financie/ppp-projekty/garantovane-energeticke-sluzby/zz_2019_4_20190201.pdf), which sets out the legal framework for exploration, extraction, and utilisation of geothermal resources. The act defines the requirements for obtaining exploration and mining permits, including environmental and technical criteria, as well as public consultation requirements.

The Ministry of Economy of the Slovak Republic (<https://www.economy.gov.sk/>) is responsible for issuing licenses for the exploration, development, and operation of geothermal resources. The license application must include technical and economic feasibility studies, an environmental impact assessment, and a plan for the utilisation of the resource. The license is granted for a period of up to 30 years and can be extended by up to 10 years.

In order to obtain an exploration permit, a detailed exploration plan must be submitted that includes information on the proposed drilling locations, drilling methods, and the estimated resource capacity. The plan must also include a detailed environmental impact assessment on the local ecosystem and the surrounding community.

Once exploration has been completed, one needs to apply for a mining permit, which allows the extraction of heat. The mining permit also requires an environmental impact assessment, as well as compliance with technical and safety standards.

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

7.26 SLOVENIA

All metal ores are state owned. The competent authority for granting exploration and extraction rights for mineral resources is the Energy Directorate (within the Ministry of Infrastructure, <https://www.gov.si/en/state-authorities/ministries/ministry-of-infrastructure/>). The local municipalities are an important co-authority as they are responsible for the municipal spatial plans. All areas with a mining concession (or with mining rights) need to be included in the municipal spatial plans and designated as “mineral extraction areas”. For such plans strategic environmental assessment or at least screening is needed (MinLex 2017). Drillholes, deeper than 300 meters require a mining project and this also applies to the drillholes for the purpose of exploration/exploitation of geothermal energy.

Permitting for deep geothermal projects in Slovenia is regulated by the Environmental Protection Act and (ZVO-1, SOP-2004-01-1694, <https://www.eui.eu/Projects/InternationalArtHeritageLaw/Documents/NationalLegislation/Slovenia/environmentprotectionact.pdf>) and the Energy Act (Energetski zakon EZ-1, <https://www.climate-laws.org/geographies/slovenia/laws/energy-act-energetski-zakon-ez-1>). According to this act, the competent authority for permitting is the Ministry of the Environment and Spatial Planning, which assesses the environmental impact of proposed projects. The Energy Act establishes the basic legal framework for the promotion of renewable energy sources, including geothermal energy. It provides a legal basis for the promotion and development of geothermal energy in Slovenia and sets out the conditions for obtaining a permit for deep geothermal projects.

In order to obtain a permit for a deep geothermal project an application must be submitted to the Ministry of the Natural Resources and Spatial Planning that includes a detailed description of the project and an environmental impact assessment. The environmental impact assessment is prepared by an authorized expert, and must include a description of the potential impact of the project on the environment, as well as measures to mitigate any negative impacts. The Ministry of the Environment and Spatial Planning provides guidance and support to project developers throughout the permitting process.

Relevant regulatory instruments are the Environmental Protection Act of 07.05.20 as amended on 07.11.20 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/slv97886.pdf>), the Spatial management Act of 24.10.17 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/slv203422.pdf>), the Decree on waste of 15.12.11 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/html/slv130514.htm>), and the Water Act as amended on 08.05.20 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/slv61692.pdf>).

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

7.27 SPAIN

All mineral deposits and geological resources are state owned (Ley Minas of 21.07.73, <https://www.boe.es/buscar/act.php?id=BOE-A-1973-1018>).

However, the regulatory processes are highly fragmented between the state and the 17 Autonomous Regions, each with different environmental and land-use regulations, as well as different policy agendas. Each of the Regions may enact additional mining rules, provided the basic mining system governed by national provisions is respected. The permit/concession allowing extractive activities depends on the type of

mineral commodity ('mineral sections' A, B, and C). Thermal waters are included under Section B (MinLex 2017).

So, it is likely that combined extraction will fall under the mining law and the respective permitting procedures. For instance, the drilling of boreholes and installations would be covered by the General Regulation of Basic Standards of Mining Safety contained in Royal Decree 863/1985 (<https://www.boe.es/eli/es/rd/1985/04/02/863>).

Spain has a well-established geothermal industry, and the country has made significant progress in recent years to streamline the permitting process for deep geothermal projects. Deep geothermal energy is defined as the use of geothermal energy sources at depths greater than 400 meters. The permitting process for deep geothermal projects is regulated by various authorities, including the Ministry for Ecological Transition and Demographic Challenge (MITECO), the Spanish Geological and Mining Institute (IGME), and regional governments. The process generally involves several stages, including preliminary studies, environmental impact assessments, public consultations, and approval by the relevant authorities.

The permitting process can take several months to a few years to complete, depending on the complexity of the project and the requirements of the various authorities involved. However, there is still scope to simplify and expedite the processes (Arrizabalaga et al., 2019).

In 2019, the Spanish government approved a new regulatory framework for geothermal energy, which includes a simplified permitting process for projects with a capacity of up to 1 MW (IEA, 2021).

Regulatory instruments concerning extraction include the Royal Legislative Decree 1/2016, of December 16, which approves the consolidated text of the Law on Integrated Prevention and Control of pollution (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/spa161835.pdf>), the law no. 21/2013, last amended 09.12.18, on Environmental Impact Assessment (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/spa129010.pdf>), the Law 7/2022 of 08.04.22 on waste and contaminated soils for a circular economy (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/spa209455.pdf>), the Law 22/2011 of 28.07.11 on waste and contaminated soils (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/spa104715.pdf>), and particularly article 57 of the Royal Legislative Decree No. 1/2001 - Water Law - in its recast form of 09.04.22 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/spa28470.pdf>).

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

7.28 SWEDEN

All metal ores are state owned. In Sweden, the right to grant access to concession minerals and permits to extract mineral deposits is reserved to the state. The 'concession minerals' are legally defined and listed in the Minerals Act 1991:45 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/swe42438.pdf>) of 24.01.91, last amended 01.01.06, and comprise metallic ores, a wide range of industrial minerals, coal, oil, gaseous hydrocarbons and diamonds. The Swedish Environmental Code 1998:808 (https://www.government.se/contentassets/be5e4d4ebdb4499f8_d6365720ae68724/the-swedish-environmental-code-ds-200061) of 11.07.98, last amended 01.01.18, is particularly relevant, as permits for extraction must be granted under both the Minerals Act and the Environmental Code. The primary law concerning the extraction of 'non-concession minerals' is the Environmental Code (1998:808) (MinLex 2017).

Deep geothermal projects are regulated (by implication) under the Swedish Environmental Code, and permits are required from various authorities. The Swedish Environmental Protection Agency (SEPA, <https://www.naturvardsverket.se/en/>) is responsible for issuing permits for drilling and construction of deep geothermal projects. The EPA assesses the environmental impact (based on the Environmental Assessment Regulation 2017:966 of 02.11.17, last amended on 01.01.18, <https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/swe187160.pdf>) of the proposed project and ensures that the project complies with regulations related to water, waste, and emissions. The SEPA also consults with other relevant authorities, such as the Swedish Geological Survey and the Swedish Radiation Safety Authority in case of NORM (naturally occurring radioactive materials) that may appear in scales.

In addition to the EPA permit, deep geothermal projects also require a permit from the Swedish Mining Inspectorate (<https://www.sgu.se/en/mining-inspectorate/>), which is responsible for regulating mining and drilling operations. The Mining Inspectorate assesses the safety of the project, including the stability of the underground formations and the risk of earthquakes.

Other relevant regulations are the Land code 1970:994 of 17.12.70, last amended 12.11.20 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/swe202065.pdf>), the Act on the carrying into effect of the Water Act of 1983 of 01.01.94, last amended on 01.01.99 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/swe24831E.pdf>).

Before submitting an application for permits, project developers are encouraged to consult with local communities and other stakeholders to address any concerns and ensure that the project is compatible with local land use and other activities.

It appears that so far, the few deep projects undertaken have not been successful (Gehlin & Andersson, 2016).

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

7.29 TURKEY

The Geothermal Transparency Guide (<http://www.geothermal.bba.is>) explains that Article 4 of the Law on Geothermal Resources and Natural Mineral Waters no. 5686, published 3 June 2007, Law no. 26551 (the “Geothermal Resources Law”), and Article 5 of the Geothermal and Mineral Resources Implementation Regulation no. 26727, published on 11 December 2017, state that all geothermal resources belong to the State, independent from the ownership of the land under which they are located. Although exploration and exploitation licenses may be issued by the State for the operation of geothermal resources, the actual ownership of such resources may not be transferred under any circumstances.

The objective of the Minerals Act, No. 3213 of 04.06.85 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/tur50790.pdf>), amended by Law No. 6592 of 18.02.15 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/tur153084.pdf>) and last amended by Regulation on mining of 11.12.22 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/tur222940.pdf>) is to define the principles and methods of exploring and processing minerals, and to regulate the proprietary rights. Energy minerals, metal minerals, industrial minerals, precious minerals, and liquid and gas containing above minerals are listed in the act. Proprietary rights for minerals are defined in details. Turkish citizens and companies are eligible to explore for and process minerals. Minerals are explored under an exploration license, valid for 30 months. This license

cannot be renewed. This exploration period is followed by a preliminary operational license, which is valid for 3 years and also cannot be renewed. A final operational license is granted to mines having adequate reserves. This license is valid for a minimum of 10 years and is renewable and transferable.

The Ministry of Energy and Natural Resources sets forth the terms and conditions for obtaining exploration and exploitation licenses. According to such terms and conditions, the Special Provincial Administration or (if there is a metropolitan municipality in the relevant province) the Provincial Directorate of Planning and Coordination of Investment of the metropolitan municipality is responsible for the issuance of licenses. The Administration notifies the General Directorate of Mining Affairs regarding license applications and its approval thereof. Where necessary, the Administration may request the General Directorate of Mineral Research and Exploration's to conduct an evaluation of the planned project prior to the issuance of a license.

There are also various other state entities involved in the development, such as for environmental and land acquisition purposes.

There is inter-agency cooperation between the Administration and the General Directorate of Mining Affairs in the licensing process.

Other legislation of relevance includes the Environment Law No. 2872 of 09.08.83 last amended on 01.01.22 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/tur7700.pdf>), the Regulation regarding point source land pollution and soil contamination control of 08.06.10 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/tur130480.pdf>), Regulation on water allocation of 10.12.19 (where mining is mentioned specifically, <https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/tur196786.pdf>), Act No. 167 relative to groundwaters of 16.12. 60 (mining also mentioned, <https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/tur2564.pdf>), Regulation on water pollution control of 31.12.04 last amended on 17.12.22 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/tur89033.pdf>). It seems that the Zero Waste Regulation of 12.07.19 (<https://www.fao.org/faolex/results/details/en/c/LEX-FAOC187824>) does not apply to extractive waste.

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

7.30 UK

In general, onshore ores are privately owned (landowner), with the exception of gold and silver (MinLex 2017). Pre-Brexit laws and regulations in general emulate EU-Directives and -Regulations, where necessary. Following the European Union (Withdrawal) Act (2018 Ch.16) of 26.07.18 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/uk180139.pdf>) tens of thousands of pieces of legislation that made reference to the fact that the UK were an EU Member State were amended to remove such references and convert them into purely UK law.

The key piece of legislation with respect to mining is the Planning Act 2008 (Ch. 29) of 26.11.08 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/uk89714.pdf>), which is amended by the Environment Act 2021 (Ch. 30) of 09.11.21 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/uk209376.pdf>), and the Environmental Assessments and Miscellaneous Planning (Amendment) (EU Exit) Regulations 2018 (S.I. No. 1232 of 2018) of 08.11.18 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/uk181928.pdf>). The latter addresses in particular regulatory issues arising from Brexit. Other relevant legislation includes the Water Act 2014 (Ch. 21) of 14.05.14 last amended on 19.08.18 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/uk143276.pdf>), and the Planning (Hazardous

Substances) Act 1990 (c. 10) of 24.05.90 last amended on 22.07.20 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/uk75905.pdf>).

Dumas et al. (2014) state that the ownership of geothermal resources and regulations as to their use are unclear.

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

APPENDIX 2 – CATALOGUE OF LIFE-CYCLE RISKS FOR COMBINED EXTRACTION PROJECTS

Exploration		
	Risk category	Impact
Exploration Geologist in the field	Walking on the ground	Disturbance of plant cover and wild-life
	Stream sampling	Turbidity disturbing aquatic life
	Stranger(s) in the area	Inquietude and apprehension among locals
Airborne geophysics	Helicopters and drones	Hovering/low altitude flight disturb wild-life
		Inquietude and apprehension among locals
Ground-based geophysics	Vibroseismic trails	Severe disturbance of plant cover and wild-life due to heavy vehicles
		Loss of oils and hydraulic fluids in the environment
		Disturbance of locals by vibrations
	Explosive seismics	Severe disturbance of plant cover and wild-life due to heavy vehicles and explosions
		Disturbance of locals by vibrations and explosions
		Accidental damage to buildings (windows)
		Contamination from spilled drilling fluids
		Loss of oils and hydraulic fluids in the environment
		Risk from storage and handling of explosives
		Wild fire risk from explosions
	OSH risks from operating heavy machinery	
	Core drilling	Severe disturbance of plant cover and wild-life due to heavy vehicles and explosions
		Disturbance of locals by vibrations and explosions
		Contamination from spilled drilling fluids and chips
		Loss of oils and hydraulic fluids in the environment
Short-circuiting and cross-contamination between aquifers due to inadequate lining and sealing between aquifers upon completion		
Penetration of surface contamination into unsealed boreholes		
OSH risks from operating heavy machinery		
Transport of equipment and samples	Road vehicles	Road accidents, also involving locals
		Loss of oils and hydraulic fluids in the environment off-road and during maintenance in the field
		Loss of life due to accidents
	Helicopters	Crashes with loss of life
		Environmental contamination due to crashes
		Wild-fires due to crashes
		Loss of oils and hydraulic fluids when maintained in the field

Planning		
	Risk category	Impact
Strategic planning	Site selection	Location of surface facilities can cause more or less disturbances to the natural environment or human settlements
		Habitat fragmentation by surface installations and extractive waste management facilities
		Cumulative impacts from several mining and other industrial facilities

Construction of wells and surface facilities		
	Risk category	Impact
Site preparation	Removal of vegetation cover	OSH risks associated with vegetation clearance
		Loss of oils and hydraulic fluids from logging and brush cutting equipment
		Disruption and displacement of wild-life
		Accidental killing of wild-life
		Noise disturbance of locals
	Operation of earth-moving plant	Disturbance of plant cover and wild-life
		Loss of oils and hydraulic fluids from plant
		OSH of equipment operators
		OSH of on-site staff
		Increased surface erosion and stream turbidity
		Dust generation and off-site dispersal
		Accidents due to operator error
	Off-site transport	Road accidents involving lorries
		Accidents during transport of heavy plant
		Lost loads
	Buildings construction	OSH of crane operation
		OSH of scaffolding work
		OSH of stationary equipment (circular saws, mixers, rammers, ...)
		Dropping hazards (tools and materials form overhead)
		Dust and fibres from building materials (on-site and off-site)
Well preparation	Drilling	Noise and vibration
		Dust generation
		Spilling of drilling fluids
		OSH of drilling equipment operation
	Well completion	Casing failure (rupture, bulging, tearing, deformation, etc.)
		Grouting/cementing failure
	Water	Contamination of water-bearing strata
		Draw-down of groundwater levels
		Cross-contamination of aquifers
	Gas	Radon-release from open boreholes
		Release of noxious or toxic gases from fluids

Plant operation		
	Risk category	Impact
Geothermal plant operation	Operation	Contamination from spilled drilling fluids and chips
		Loss of oils and hydraulic fluids in the environment
		Short-circuiting and cross-contamination between aquifers
		Penetration of surface contamination into unsealed boreholes
		OSH risks from plant operations
		Failure of pressurised vessels and hot pipes
		Accidental spills of reactants or pregnant solutions
		Chemical spills during reactant preparation
	Geological	Seismicity due to re-equilibration of stresses
		Subsidence due to water extraction
	Water	Contaminated effluents
		Failure of hydraulic protection wells
		Failure of decant water treatment systems
	Electrical	Shock due to damaged electrical installations
Natural	Flooding of extraction site	

Extraction and Processing		
	Risk category	Impact
Extraction	Operation	Accidental spills of processing fluids in plant
		Chemical spills during processing fluid preparation
		OSH of plant operation
		Kinetic energy including dropped objects and falls from height
		Failure of pressurised vessels and hot piping
	Water	Accidental discharges of contaminated fluids
		Failure of pipes and tanks
		Failure of decant water treatment systems
		Regional water stress due to extraction of process water
	Air	Olfactory nuisances off-site
Biological	Biohazards e.g. from bacteria used in advanced processing techniques	
Radiation	Naturally occurring radioactive minerals (NORM)	
Electrical	Shock due to damaged electrical installations	
Products	Chemical	Hazardous impurities Hazardous processing agent residues
	Radiation	NORM in products
By-products	Chemical	Hazardous impurities Hazardous processing agent residues
	Radiation	NORM in by-products
Wastes	Chemical	Hazardous components Hazardous processing agent residues
	Radiation	NORM in wastes

Closure and Decommissioning		
	Risk category	Impact
Site abandonment	Operational	Collapse of built structures due to lack of maintenance
	Water	Cross-contamination of aquifers due to improperly lined boreholes
	Radiation	Radon release due to unsealed boreholes
	Electrical	Shock due to damaged electrical installations
	Public safety	Failure of access prevention (collapse of fences) Uncontrolled access to hazardous substances (reagents) remaining on site
Decommissioning	Operational	OSH of dismantling and demolition activities
		OSH of plant and machinery operation
		OSH of site staff
		Exposure to hazardous substances in buildings
		Noise and vibration from demolition activities
		Loss of oils and hydraulic fluids to the environment
		Loss of hazardous materials from structures being dismantled
		Kinetic energy including dropped objects and falls from height
	Accidents during on-site transport of materials	
	Water	Short-circuiting between aquifers due to changing hydraulic regime
		Leaching of alien substances during hydraulic re-equilibration
		Release of hazardous substances during demolition and dismantling
		Loss of oils and hydraulic fluids to groundwaters
	Air	Off-site dust from demolition activities
		Release of hazardous minerals (asbestos, silica, NORM,...)
		Dust generation from e.g. crushing of concrete
	Noise	Off-site noise and vibration due to demolition and dismantling activities
	Electrical	Shock due to damaged electrical installations
	Transport	Accidents during off-site removal of materials for recycling or re-use
		Release of hazardous substances during transport to off-site disposal
Societal	Nuisance of demolition activities	

Remediation		
	Risk category	Impact
Wells	Water	Residual lixiviants that cannot be removed by pump-and-treat
		Short-circuiting between aquifers
	Air	Radon leakage into buildings on site or into the surrounding environment
External risks	Natural hazards	Damages due to earthquakes
		Changing climatic boundary conditions (e.g. amount and intensity of precipitation)

APPENDIX 3 - REFERENCES TO EU REGULATIONS

- CEU Council of the European Union (1967): Council Directive 67/548/EEC of 27 June 1967 on the approximation of laws, regulations and administrative provisions relating to the classification, packaging and labelling of dangerous substances.- OJ No. 196/1, p. 234-256, 16.08.1967, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:31967L0548&from=EN>.
- CEU Council of the European Union (1985): Council Directive 85/337/EEC of 27 June 1985 on the assessment of the effects of certain public and private projects on the environment.- OJ L 175/40-48, 5.7.1985, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:31985L0337&from=EN>.
- CEU Council of the European Union (1989): Council Directive 89/391/EEC of 12 June 1989 on the introduction of measures to encourage improvements in the safety and health of workers at work.- OJ 183/1-183/8 of 26.06.89, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:31989L0391&from=EN>.
- CEU Council of the European Union (1991): Council Directive 91/689/EEC of 12 December 1991 on hazardous waste.- OJ L377/20-27, 31.12.1991, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:31991L0689&from=EN>.
- CEU Council of the European Union (1992): Directive 92/43/EEC on the conservation of natural habitats and of wild fauna and flora (Habitats Directive).- OJ L206/7-50, 22.7.92, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:31992L0043&from=EN>.
- CEU Council of the European Union (1992): Council Directive 92/57/EEC of 24 June 1992 on the implementation of minimum safety and health requirements at temporary or mobile construction sites (eighth individual Directive within the meaning of Article 16 (1) of Directive 89/391/EEC).- OJ L 245/6-22, 26.8.1992, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:01992L0057-20190726&from=EN>.
- CEU Council of the European Union (1992): Council Directive 92/91/EEC of 3 November 1992 concerning the minimum requirements for improving the safety and health protection of workers in the mineral-extracting industries through drilling (eleventh individual Directive within the meaning of Article 16 (1) of Directive 89/391/EEC).- OJ L348/9-24, 28.11.92, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:31992L0091&from=EN>.
- CEU Council of the European Union (1992): Council Directive 92/104/EEC of 3 December 1992 on the minimum requirements for improving the safety and health protection of workers in surface and underground mineral-extracting industries (twelfth individual Directive within the meaning of Article 16 (1) of Directive 89/391/EEC).- OJ L 404/10-25, 31.12.1992, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:31992L0104&from=EN>.
- CEU Council of the European Union (1996): Council Directive 96/61/EC of 24 September 1996 concerning integrated pollution prevention and control.- OJ L 257/26-40, 10.10.1996, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:31996L0061&from=EN>.

- CEU Council of the European Union (1996): Council Directive 96/82/EC of 9 December 1996 on the control of major-accident hazards involving dangerous substances (Seveso Directive).- OJ L 10/13-33, 14.01.97, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:31996L0082&from=EN>.
- CEU Council of the European Union (1997): Council Directive 97/11/EC of 3 March 1997 amending Directive 85/337/EEC on the assessment of the effects of certain public and private projects on the environment.- OJ L 073/5-15, 14.03.1997, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:31997L0011&from=EN>.
- CEU Council of the European Union (1999): Council Directive 1999/31/EC of 26 April 1999 on the landfill of waste.- OJ L 182/1-19, 16.7.1999, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:31999L0031&from=EN>.
- CEU Council of the European Union (1999): Directive 1999/45/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 31 May 1999 concerning the approximation of the laws, regulations and administrative provisions of the Member States relating to the classification, packaging and labelling of dangerous preparations.- OJ L200/1-68, 30.07.1999, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:31999L0045&from=en>.
- CEU Council of the European Union (1999): Council Directive 1999/92/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 1999 on minimum requirements for improving the safety and health protection of workers potentially at risk from explosive atmospheres (15th individual Directive within the meaning of Article 16(1) of Directive 89/391/EEC.- 8 p., <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legalcontent/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:31999L0092&from=EN>.
- CEU Council of the European Union (2000): Directive 2000/60/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 October 2000 establishing a framework for Community action in the field of water policy (Water Framework Directive).- OJ L 327/1-73, 22.12.2000, https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:5c835afb-2ec6-4577-bdf8-756d3d694eeb.0004.02/DOC_1&format=PDF.
- CEU Council of the European Union (2001): Directive 2001/42/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 June 2001 on the assessment of the effects of certain plans and programmes on the environment.- OJ L 197/30-37, 21.7.2001, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32001L0042&from=EN>.
- CEU Council of the European Union (2001): Regulation (EC) No 761/2001 of the European parliament and of the council of 19 March 2001 allowing voluntary participation by organisations in a Community eco-management and audit scheme (EMAS).- OJ L 114/1-29, 24.04.01, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2001:114:0001:0029:EN:PDF>.
- CEU Council of the European Union (2002): Directive 2002/44/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 June 2002 on the minimum health and safety requirements regarding the exposure of workers to the risks arising from physical agents (vibration) (sixteenth individual Directive within the meaning of Article 16(1) of Directive 89/391/EEC) - Joint Statement by the European Parliament and the Council.- OJ L 177/13-20, 6.7.2002, https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:546a09c0-3ad1-4c07-bcd5-9c3dae6b1668.0004.02/DOC_1&format=PDF.

- CEU Council of the European Union (2003): Directive 2003/35/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 May 2003 providing for public participation in respect of the drawing up of certain plans and programmes relating to the environment and amending with regard to public participation and access to justice Council Directives 85/337/EEC and 96/61/EC - Statement by the Commission.- OJ L 156/17-25, 25.06.2003. https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:4a80a6c9-cdb3-4e27-a721-d5df1a0535bc.0004.02/DOC_1&format=PDF.
- CEU Council of the European Union (2003): Directive 2003/10/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 6 February 2003 on the minimum health and safety requirements regarding the exposure of workers to the risks arising from physical agents (noise) (Seventeenth individual Directive within the meaning of Article 16(1) of Directive 89/391/EEC).- OJ L 42/38-44, 15.2.2003, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32003L0010&from=en>.
- CEU Council of Europe (2003): Directive 2002/95/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 January 2003 on the restriction of the use of certain hazardous substances in electrical and electronic equipment.- OJ L 37/19-23, 13.2.2003, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32002L0095&from=EN>.
- CEU Council of the European Union (2003): Directive 2003/105/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2003 amending Council Directive 96/82/EC on the control of major-accident hazards involving dangerous substances.- OJ L 345/97-105, 31.12.2003, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32003L0105&from=EN>.
- CEU Council of the European Union (2004): Directive 2004/35/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 April 2004 on environmental liability with regard to the prevention and remedying of environmental damage (Environmental Liability Directive).- OJ L 143/56-75, 30.04.04. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legalcontent/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32004L0035&from=EN>
- CEU Council of the European Union (2004): Directive 2004/37/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 29 April 2004 on the protection of workers from the risks related to exposure to carcinogens, mutagens or reprotoxic substances at work (Sixth individual Directive within the meaning of Article 16(1) of Council Directive 89/391/EEC) (codified version).- OJ L 158/50-76, 30.4.2004, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:02004L0037-20220405&from=EN>.
- CEU Council of the European Union (2006a): Directive 2006/21/EC of 15 March 2006 on the management of waste from extractive industries and amending Directive 2004/35/EC.- OJ L 102/15-33, 11.04.2006, https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:c370006a-063e-4dc7-9b05-52c37720740c.0005.02/DOC_1&format=PDF.
- CEU Council of the European Union (2006b): Directive 2006/42/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 May 2006 on machinery, and amending Directive 95/16/EC (recast).- OJ L 157/24-86, 6.9.2006, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32006L0042&from=EN>.
- CEU Council of the European Union (2006c): Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 December 2006 concerning the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH).- OJ L

396/1-520, 30.12.2006, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:02006R1907-20140410&from=EN>.

CEU Council of the European Union (2006d): Directive 2006/118/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 December 2006 on the protection of groundwater against pollution and deterioration.- OJ L 372/19-31, 27.12.2006, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32006L0118>.

CEU Council of the European Union (2008a): Directive 2008/1/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 January 2008 concerning integrated pollution prevention and control (Codified version).- OJ L24/8-29, 29.01.2008. <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2008:024:0008:0029:en:PDF>.

CEU Council of the European Union (2008b): Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 November 2008 on waste and repealing certain Directives (Waste Framework Directive).- OJ L 312/3-30, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32008L0098&from=EN>.

CEU Council of the European Union (2008): Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2008 on classification, labelling and packaging of substances and mixtures, amending and repealing Directives 67/548/EEC and 1999/45/EC, and amending Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006.- OJ L 353/1-1355, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2008:353:0001:1355:en:PDF>.

CEU Council of the European Union (2009): Directive 2009/28/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 April 2009 on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources and amending and subsequently repealing Directives 2001/77/EC and 2003/30/EC.- OJ L140/16-62, 5.6.2009, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32009L0028&from=EN>.

CEU Council of the European Union (2009): Directive 2009/104/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 September 2009 concerning the minimum safety and health requirements for the use of work equipment by workers at work (second individual Directive within the meaning of Article 16(1) of Directive 89/391/EEC).- OJ 260/5-19, 3.10.2009, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32009L0104&from=EN>.

CEU Council of the European Union (2009): Directive 2009/147/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 November 2009 on the conservation of wild birds.- OJ L 20/7-25, 26.1.2010, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32009L0147&from=EN>.

CEU Council of the European Union (2009): Regulation (EC) No 1221/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 November 2009 on the voluntary participation by organisations in a Community eco-management and audit scheme (EMAS), repealing Regulation (EC) No 761/2001 and Commission Decisions 2001/681/EC and 2006/193/EC.- OJ L 342/1-45, 22.12.2009, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32009R1221&from=en>.

CEU Council of the European Union (2010): Directive 2010/75/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 November 2010 on industrial emissions (Integrated Pollution Prevention and Control) (Recast).- OJ L 334/17-119, 17.12.2010, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32010L0075&from=EN>.

- CEU Council of the European Union (2012a): Directive 2012/18/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 4 July 2012 on the control of major-accident hazards involving dangerous substances, amending and subsequently repealing Council Directive 96/82/EC (Seveso III Directive).- OJ 197/1-L197/37, 24.07.2012, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32012L0018&from=HR>.
- CEU Council of the European Union (2012b): Directive 2012/19/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 4 July 2012 on waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE) - (recast).- OJ L197/38-71, 24.07.2012, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2012:197:0038:0071:EN:PDF>.
- CEU Council of Europe (2012c): Directive 2012/19/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 4 July 2012 on waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE).- OJ L 197/38-71, 24.7.2012, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32012L0019&from=EN>.
- CEU Council of Europe (2013): Council Directive 2013/59/Euratom of 5 December 2013 laying down basic safety standards for protection against the dangers arising from exposure to ionising radiation, and repealing Directives 89/618/Euratom, 90/641/Euratom, 96/29/Euratom, 97/43/Euratom and 2003/122/Euratom.- OJ L 13/1-73, 17.1.2014, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32013L0059&from=EN>.
- CEU Council of Europe (2014a): Directive 2014/52/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 April 2014 amending Directive 2011/92/EU on the assessment of the effects of certain public and private projects on the environment (Environmental Impact Assessment Directive).- OJ 124/1-18, 25.4.2014, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32014L0052>.
- CEU Council of Europe (2014b): Directive 2014/52/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 October 2014 amending Directive 2013/34/EU as regards disclosure of non-financial and diversity information by certain large undertakings and groups.- OJ L330/1-9, 15.11.24, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32014L0095>.
- CEU Council of Europe (2017): Council Regulation (EU) 2017/997 of 8 June 2017 amending Annex III to Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council as regards the hazardous property HP 14 'Ecotoxic'.- OJ L150/1-4, 14.6.2017, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32017R0997&from=EN>.
- CEU Council of Europe (2018): Directive (EU) 2018/2001 of The European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2018 on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources.- OJ L 328/82-209, 21.12.2018, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32018L2001&from=EN>.
- CEU Council of Europe (2019): Regulation (EU) 2019/1239 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 establishing a European Maritime Single Window environment and repealing Directive 2010/65/EU.- OJ L 198/64-87, 25.7.2019, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:32019R1239>.
- CEU Council of Europe (2023): Directive (EU) 2023/1791 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 September 2023 on energy efficiency and amending Regulation (EU) 2023/955 (recast) (Text with EEA relevance) PE/15/2023/INIT.- OJ L 231/1-111, 20.9.2023, https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ%3AJOL_2023_231_R_0001&qid=1695186598766.

- CEU Council of Europe (2024): Directive (EU) 2024/1785 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 April 2024 amending Directive 2010/75/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council on industrial emissions (integrated pollution prevention and control) and Council Directive 1999/31/EC on the landfill of waste.- OJ L, 15.07.2024, https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=OJ:L_202401785.
- European Commission (2001): Implementation of Directive 2001/42 on the Assessment of the Effects of certain Plans and Programmes on the Environment.- http://ec.europa.eu/environment/archives/eia/pdf/030923_sea_guidance.pdf
- European Commission (2006): Clarification of the Application of Article 2(3) of the EIA Directive.- ISBN 92-79-01036-0, 11 p., Luxembourg, http://ec.europa.eu/environment/archives/eia/pdf/eia_art2_3.pdf
- European Commission (2009): Commission Decision 2009/335/EC of 20 April 2009 on technical guidelines for the establishment of the financial guarantee in accordance with Directive 2006/21/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council concerning the management of waste from extractive industries (notified under document number C(2009) 2798).- OJ L 102/25, 21.04.09, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2009:101:0025:0025:EN:PDF>
- European Commission (2009): Commission Decision 2009/337/EC of 20 April 2009 on the definition of the criteria for the classification of waste facilities in accordance with Annex III of Directive 2006/21/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council concerning the management of waste from extractive industries (notified under document number C(2009) 2856).- OJ L 102/7-11, 22.04.09, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2009:102:0007:0011:EN:PDF>
- European Commission (2009): Commission Decision 2009/358/EC: of 29 April 2009 on the harmonisation, the regular transmission of the information and the questionnaire referred to in Articles 22(1)(a) and 18 of Directive 2006/21/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council on the management of waste from extractive industries (notified under document number C(2009) 3011).- OJ L 110/39-45, 01.05.09, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2009:110:0039:0045:EN:PDF>
- European Commission (2009): Commission Decision 2009/359/EC of 30 April 2009 completing the definition of inert waste in implementation of Article 22(1)(f) of Directive 2006/21/EC of the European Parliament and the Council concerning the management of waste from extractive industries (notified under document number C(2009) 3012).- OJ L 110/46-47, 01.05.2009, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2009:110:0046:0047:EN:PDF>
- European Commission (2009): Commission Decision 2009/360/EC of 30 April 2009 completing the technical requirements for waste characterisation laid down by Directive 2006/21/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council on the management of waste from extractive industries (notified under document number C(2009) 3013).- OJ L 110/48-51, 1.5.2009, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2009:110:0048:0051:EN:PDF>.
- European Commission (2014a): Commission Regulation (EU) No 1357/2014 of 18 December 2014 replacing Annex III to Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council on waste and repealing certain Directives.- OJ L365/89-96, 19.12.2014, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32014R1357&from=EN>.

- European Commission (2014b): Commission Decision 2014/955/EU of 18 December 2014 amending Decision 2000/532/EC on the list of waste pursuant to Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council.- OJ 370/44-86, 30.12.2014, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32014D0955&from=EN>.
- European Commission (2019): Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions: The European Green Deal.- COM(2019) 640 final of 11.12.2019: 24 p., https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:b828d165-1c22-11ea-8c1f-01aa75ed71a1.0002.02/DOC_1&format=PDF.
- European Commission (2023): Commission Delegated Regulation (Eu) 2023/2772 of 31 July 2023 supplementing Directive 2013/34/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council as regards sustainability reporting standards.- OJ L 2772/1-335, 22.12.2023, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:02023R2772-20231222>.
- European Parliament and Council of the Europe Union (2006): Directive 2006/21/EC of 15 March 2006 on the management of waste from extractive industries and amending Directive 2004/35/EC.- OJ L 102/15-33, 11.04.2006, https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:c370006a-063e-4dc7-9b05-52c37720740c.0005.02/DOC_1&format=PDF.
- EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND COUNCIL (2024): Regulation (EU) 2024/1252 of 11 April 2024 establishing a framework for ensuring a secure and sustainable supply of critical raw materials and amending Regulations (EU) No 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, (EU) 2018/1724 and (EU) 2019/1020.- OJ L Series, 03.05.24, 67 p., https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=OJ:L_202401252